

VALKYRIES

D2.12 Harmonization and Standardization Reports M24

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1. Executive Summary

WP2 provides the design, specifications, and requirements that need to be considered throughout the project life cycle. This includes an in-depth review of system requirements, out comes from consultations with stakeholders, and pre-standardization research.

The Deliverable 2.12 *Harmonization and Standardization Reports M24* presents the current status of the project in terms of standardisation and harmonisation.

The harmonization and standardization process are a multidisciplinary process where cross-sectoral experts with heterogeneous competence/knowledge shall contribute, providing support in multiple initiatives, such as literature identification, specific procedures (and their differences between regions/countries), evaluation and information exchange.

This deliverable is an update of the previously submitted document D2.11 - Harmonization and Standardization Reports M18 – A/0. The new content with respect to the last version submitted has been highlighted in yellow for easy review.

2. Identification

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The document presents the status of the project in terms of standardisation and harmonisation in month 24.

3. Introduction

This deliverable refers to the **last** harmonisation and standardisation report released at the end of the project.

The previous report presented (D2.11) an overview of the harmonisation and Standardisation actions. Some aspects have progressed since then. The project has advanced to the next steps of harmonisation.

The project has reached its final steps in the project in order to produce results.

One of the first deliverables on the harmonisation methodology D2.4, about the standardisation roadmap, provides an effective base for developing and controlling the harmonization process. It is necessary to keep it in mind for understanding the steps required on this deliverable.

The technology work packages are very important as they provide the most progress in terms of harmonisation. The tasks of WP4, WP5 and WP6 are develop the technological advance which has been tested in the use cases.

This deliverable D2.12 "Harmonisation reports" expose the results achieved in each of the harmonisation stages of the project following the methodology described in the deliverable D2.9 "Harmonization framework"

The methodology will not be detailed in this deliverable. It is described in the above-mentioned deliverable

4. Objectives

The main objective of the deliverable is to report the progress of standardisation and harmonisation of Valkyries.

The secondary objectives of this report are:

- Collect the standardization actions that the partners are carrying out.
- Expose in a clear and summarised way the harmonisation of the project.

As a final harmonisation and standardisation report of the Valkyries project let's do an overview of the objectives of the project in terms of harmonisations:

Main objective:

The primary objective of the VALKYRIES project is to develop, implement, validate and apply innovative theoretical foundations, methods, prototypes and their demonstration on a reference integration for supporting the ongoing/planned European actions for pre-standardisation and harmonisation technologies, procedures, preparedness and cross-sector/border cooperation for first aid response at disaster management by emergency health services, with the focus on their vehicular deployments.

To achieve this primary objective and address the challenges identified above, VALKYRIES establishes 9 specific and measurable objectives that are introduced below:

- **OBJ-1 (*Map of growing commercial and R&D opportunities*):** Analyse the existing/ongoing technological, procedural, education and collaborative opportunities of the first aid response supplier markets and related signs of progress beyond the state-of-the-art able to improve the EU disaster resiliency.
- **OBJ-2 (*Sustainable Regulation and ethical compliance*):** Analyse the first aid response cross-sector, cross-border and cross-hierarchy regulatory and ethical principles, identifying minimum standard requirements, lacunae and hurdles, and developing recommendations to policymakers and stakeholders to facilitate their enforcement through the consolidation of a harmonised regulatory framework and the implementation of new strategic schemes.
- **OBJ-3 (*Sustainable Pre-standardisation and Standardisation*):** Research and analyse the pre-standardisation opportunities concerning the first aid response enablers, resulting in recommendations, common requirements, guidelines and enforcement tools towards constituting a novel and sustainable reference model, being implemented at new standardisation actions.
- **OBJ-4 (*Sustainable certification and conformity assessment criteria*):** Analyse the accreditation and certification opportunities concerning the first aid response enablers, including the enforced conformity assessment criteria, evaluation procedures and facilities; resulting in recommendations, guidelines and strategies to prompt sustainable certification, accreditation and homogeneity assessment.
- **OBJ-5 (*Sustainable Harmonisation framework*):** Development of a holistic framework for supporting the standardisation/harmonisation of first aid response enablers assuming their cross-sector, cross-border and cross-hierarchy hybrid dimensions, bearing in mind the vertical/horizontal propagation of consequences of the decisions made between technical, procedural and collaborative domains.

- **OBJ-6 (Harmonisation of vehicular first aid technologies, procedures and collaboration):** Research, analyse and apply the VALKYRIES' recommendations, guidelines and harmonisation tactics on reference equipment, technologies, procedures, preparedness, raise awareness and related collaborative solutions.
- **OBJ-7 (Cross-sectorial collaboration, civilian protection, volunteering and military assistance):** Research, analyse and expand the harmonisation framework towards facilitating, guiding and enhancing the cooperation between vehicular first aid responders with other disaster management actors, among them firefighters, law enforcement agencies, civilian protection, military or heterogeneous volunteering.
- **OBJ-8 (Reference integration and interoperation):** Reference integration and interoperation of the harmonised technological, procedural and collaborative solutions based on the common requirements and gap mitigations prioritised by the committed end-users and practitioners.
- **OBJ-9 (Large EU scale cross-border demonstrations):** Evaluation and demonstration of the interoperability and enhancements derived from harmonising vehicular first aid related enablers at four cross-border and cross-sectorial scenarios: Spain-Portugal, Slovakia-Austria, Bulgaria-Greece and Norway-Netherlands.

4.1. Requirements traceability matrix

ID	Priority	Traceability with objectives	WBS Deliverables	Compliance	Result
REQ_BASE_T2.4_3	P1	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7	D2.4 D2.9	RECOMENDED	Collection and evaluation of relevant documentation, in a D2.12
REQ_COM_T2.4_1	P1	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7	D2.5 D2.12	REQUIRED	Review the current state of harmonization, identify opportunities and implement it, summarized in D2.9 and D2.12
REQ_COM_T2.4_3	P1	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7	D2.6 D2.10 D2.11 D2.12	RECOMENDED	Collect and evaluate relevant documentation about interoperability, summarized in D2.12
REQ_BASE_T2.5_2	P1	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7	D2.12	REQUIRED	Filling the gaps identified and proposing amendments, summarized in D2.12
REQ_COM	P2	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5	D2.12	REQUIRED	Suggestion of new standards and common

ID	Priority	Traceability with objectives	WBS Deliverables	Compliance	Result
T2.5_1		VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7			procedures, summarized in D2.12
REQ_COM_T2.5_3	P1	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7	D2.12 D7.5 D7.6 D7.7 D7.8	RECOMENDED	Definition of gaps and improvements for UC and test the, summarized in D.2

Table 1 - Requirements Traceability matrix

5. Reminder harmonization procedure

5.1. Landscape of the harmonization framework

In deliverable D2.4 the basis for harmonisation was created. It has been a tailor-made process that has been modified based on the needs of the project. The final methodology of the project is described in D2.12 “Harmonization Framework” Here the process is briefly described in order to understand the results below, but for a more extensive explanation, please refer to this deliverable.

As a brief summary of the harmonization framework. Novotec defined 3 phases for the harmonisation process. In this first harmonisation report we are understandably in the first harmonization phase.

At the first phase of the harmonization, the project collected information and standards. The state of the art was also analysed.

All the standards related to the project was collected and all the standards that directly affects VALYRIES in the Use Cases (UC) was be collected too.

Moreover, partners collect pre-identified gaps and commonalities. Some data, like the gaps and commonalities, can be detected before the meetings with the partners. This is because there is experience, literature and previous projects about these gaps and commonalities.

At the second phase of the harmonization, the 3 technology work packages studied the current standards and normative references, later the current capabilities of the technology area and then a gap between what is desired and what is in use.

Later an opportunity was then proposed for each gap or group of gaps. That is to say, a solution was proposed for each of the deviations that could potentially be solved in a cross border and multiple-victim disasters.

At the third phase the project produced suggestion and improvements for the detected gaps. Firstly, every technical opportunity was analysed in terms of feasibility and impact. This analysis was made by internal and external experts of the project. The final result of this analysis was a prioritisation list of opportunities. Some opportunities with better relation feasibility/impact were selected for being tested in the Use Cases

During the use cases, opportunities have been integrated to test the improvement produced by adapting them to a real scenario. Some of the improvements have been implemented fully, partially, mixed reality with real and simulated elements or fully simulated. Depending on the resources of the project and the partners, in some of the use cases and opportunities it has been possible to collect sufficient data to make an inter-comparison between the usual working procedures and the harmonised working procedures developed by Valkyries.

In the following *Figure 1* we can see the harmonisation process of the project.

Figure 1 - Valkyries harmonisation process

6. Harmonization outputs

6.1. Legal Standard identifications

This Valkyries outputs are a collection of legal and technical standards within the scope of the project.

This collection it is very extensive so that could be seen in annex.

6.2. Gaps

This Valkyries out are study looking for gaps between what the final respondents wanted and what the state of the art can provide.

The scope of the gaps was adapted to the scope task of de technological WP (WP4, WP5 and WP6) and the tasks within them. So that the gaps are grouped by task and by work packages

The total number of gaps detected is very extensive and can be seen in the annex.

A summary of the number of gaps detected in each work package can be found below.

Work Packages	Gaps detected
WP4	144
WP5	78
WP6	88
Total	310

Table 2 - Gaps detected

6.3. Opportunities

Each of the gaps is an inefficiency in the resolution of the emergency case presented by the project. Then, the project proposed solutions to these gaps called them opportunities.

The opportunities could provide a solution to one or more gaps. Resulting in fewer opportunities than gaps.

As in the gaps the opportunities were adapted to the scope of the technological WP and the tasks within them. So that the opportunities are grouped by task and by work packages

The total number of opportunities detected is very extensive and can be seen in the annex.

A summary of the number of opportunities detected in each work package can be found below.

Work Packages	Opportunities identified
WP4	139
WP5	69
WP6	47
Total	255

Table 3 - Opportunities Identified

6.4. Clustered opportunities

The project needed to prioritize the opportunities to find the best ones. However, a very large number of opportunities were provided, some of them were common to each other. It was too large an amount to be evaluated, it was not manageable.

Therefore, by following a methodology, similar opportunities were grouped together, reducing the number of opportunities by 67%.

The total number of clustered opportunities is very extensive and can be seen in the annex.

A summary of the number of opportunities and clustered opportunities in each work package can be found below.

Work Packages	Opportunities identified	Opportunities Clusters
WP4	139	56
WP5	69	15
WP6	47	11
Total	255	82

Table 4 - Clustered Opportunities

6.5. Selected opportunities

For the next steps of the harmonisation, it was necessary to further reduce the group of opportunities.

The project designed complete methodology to prioritise the opportunities with the highest feasibility/impact ratio.

The final selected opportunities can be seen below divided by work package:

WP4 Selected Opportunities
CO.WP4-15: Location of near/nearest vehicles
CO.WP4-28: Cross border data trace
CO.WP4-42: Reduce voice communication, digitalising most information
CO.WP4-55: Use of wearables to support triage
CO.WP4-21: Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms
CO.WP4-2: Logistics assistance using UAVs

Table 5 - WP4 Selected Opportunities

WP5 Selected Opportunities
CO.WP5-1: Standardisation of terms in planning, preparedness and execution of the emergency response
CO.WP5-2: Harmonization of emergency response plans
CO.WP5-7: Harmonization of operating procedures in emergency response
CO.WP5-12: Standardization of information sharing in emergency response
CO.WP5-13: Establishing a common federated system for sharing information in emergency response

Table 6 - WP5 Selected Opportunities

WP6 Selected Opportunities
CO.WP6-11: Minimum set of competencies and skills for volunteers and integration in the field operational procedures with adequate field exercise program and adequate protection with risk-free activities
CO.WP6-2: Use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data
CO.WP6-7: Use of Virtual Operation Support Teams (VOSTs)

WP6 Selected Opportunities
CO.WP6-5: Standardization of education and training for first aid responses (Creation of a Training kit: curriculum, methodology and training manual)
CO.WP6-10: Using common procedures and standards for training and civil-military actions

Table 7 - WP6 Selected Opportunities

6.6. Interdependencies

In the harmonisation process, there are dependencies, so that until one condition is met, the other cannot begin. These interdependencies are analysed by the project, both inside and outside the work package.

The interdependences inside and outside of the WP can be seen in the charts below:

Figure 2 - Interdependences WP4

Figure 3 - Interdependences WP5

Figure 4 - Interdependences WP6

WP	Clustered Opportunity	WP4					WP5					WP6						
		CO.WP4.15	CO.WP4.28	CO.WP4.42	CO.WP4.55	CO.WP4.21	CO.WP4.2	CO.WP5-1	CO.WP5-2	CO.WP5-7	CO.WP5-12	CO.WP5-13	CO.WP5-3	CO.WP6.2	CO.WP6.11	CO.WP6.7	CO.WP6.5	CO.WP6.10
WP4	CO.WP4.15: Location of near/nearest vehicles		X	-	-	-	X	-	-	-	X	X	-	X	-	-	-	-
	CO.WP4.28: Cross border data trace	X		X	X	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	X	-	-
	CO.WP4.42: Reduce voice communication, digitalising most information exchanges	X	X		X	-	-	-	-	X	X	-	X	-	X	-	X	-
	CO.WP4.55: Use of wearable to support triage	X	X	-		-	-	-	X	-	X	-	X	-	-	-	-	-
	CO.WP4.21: Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms	X	X	-	X		-	-	-	X	X	-	-	X	-	-	-	-
	CO.WP4.2: Logistics assistance using UAVs	X	X	-	-	X		-	-	X	X	-	-	-	X	-	X	-
WP5	CO.WP5-1: Standardisation of terms in planning, preparedness and execution of the emergency response	-	-	-	-	-	-	X	-	X	X	-	-	X	X	X	X	
	CO.WP5-2: Harmonization of emergency response plans	-	-	-	-	-	-	X		-	-	X	X	-	X	-	X	X
	CO.WP5-7: Harmonization of operating procedures in emergency response	-	-	-	-	-	X	X		X	-	-	-	X	-	X	X	
	CO.WP5-12: Standardization of information sharing in emergency response	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		-	-	-	-	X	-	-
	CO.WP5-13: Establishing a common federated system for sharing information in emergency response	X	X	X	X	X	-	-	-	-	X		-	X	-	X	-	-
	CO.WP5-3: Harmonization of alert and warning procedures in emergency response	-	-	-	-	-	-	X	-	X	-	X		-	X	X	X	X
WP6	CO.WP6.2: Use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	X	-	-	X	X	
	CO.WP6.11: Minimum set of competencies and skills for volunteers and integration in the field operational	-	-	-	-	-	-	X	X	X	-	-	X	-	-	-	-	
	CO.WP6.7: Use of Virtual Operation Support Teams (VOSTs)	-	X	X	-	-	-	X	-	-	X	X	-	-	-	-	-	
	CO.WP6.5: Standardization of education and training for first aid responses (Creation of a Training kit: curriculum, methodology and training manual).	X	X	-	X	-	-	X	X	X	-	-	X	X	-	-	-	X
	CO.WP6.10: Using common procedures and standards for training and civil-military actions	-	-	-	-	-	-	X	X	X	-	-	X	X	-	-	X	

Figure 5 - Whole opportunities interdependences

6.7. Roadmaps

The project produced an implementation roadmap of the selected opportunities. In this roadmap you can see in detail the next steps to implement these opportunities and for the end-users to benefit from them.

The study of the roadmaps for each opportunity is very extensive, so to see the detail it is necessary to refer to the deliverables below:

- D4.3 Roadmap for enhancing the pan-European technological capabilities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters

- D5.3: Roadmap for enhancing the pan-European operational and procedural capabilities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters
- D6.3: Roadmap for enhancing the pan-European preparedness and cross-sectorial collaboration for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters

6.8. SWOT

As a final deep analysis of the opportunities selected, the project was made a SWOT analysis (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats) in order to study if there are anything that make impossible the implementation or another more promising opportunity.

The SWOT analysis for each opportunity is very extensive, so to see the detail it is necessary to refer to the deliverables below:

- D4.4: VALKYRIES harmonisations on first aid response technologies and equipment
- D5.3: Roadmap for enhancing the pan-European operational and procedural capabilities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters
- D6.4: VALKYRIES harmonisations on first aid preparedness and cross-sectorial collaboration

6.9. Opportunities used in Use Cases

The selected opportunities have been tested in the use cases of the project and in the developed tools.

Not all opportunities have not been tested on all use cases and tools but have been divided by the scope of both and the availability of partners.

What opportunities and what tools have been used in each use case can be seen in the tables below:

		UC				Tools							
		UC1	UC2	UC3	UC4	iSafety	SIGRUN	Tasica Cards	Global COP	Application for digitalizing triage	TapOS Aratos	BlockChain Log	HTL
WP 4	CO.WP4.15: Location of near/nearest vehicles	X		X									
	CO.WP4.28: Cross border data trace		X	X	X		X						
	CO.WP4.42: Reduce voice communication, digitalising most information exchanges	X	X	X		X	X		X	X			X
	CO.WP4.55: Use of wearable to support triage				X						X		
	CO.WP4.21: Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms	X	X	X			X						
	CO.WP4.2: Logistics assistance using UAVs				X		X						

Table 8 - WP4 opportunities in Use Cases and Tools

		UC				Tools							
		UC1	UC2	UC3	UC4	iSafety	SIGRUN	Tasica Cards	Global COP	Application for digitalizing triage	TapOS Aratos	BlockChain Log	HTL
WP 5	CO.WP5-7: Harmonization of operating procedures in emergency response	X	X	X	X			X					
	CO.WP5-13: Establishing a common federated system for sharing information in emergency response	X	X	X		X	X		X	X			
	CO.WP5-3: Harmonization of alert and warning procedures in emergency response		X				X		X	X			
	CO.WP5-1: Standardisation of terms in planning, preparedness and execution of the emergency response		X	X			X						
	CO.WP5-2: Harmonization of emergency response plans			X					X				
	CO.WP5-12: Standardization of information sharing in emergency response		X	X			X			X			

Table 9 - WP5 opportunities in Use Cases and Tools

		UC				Tools							
		UC1	UC2	UC3	UC4	iSafety	SIGRUN	Tasica Cards	Global COP	Application for digitalizing triage	TapOS Aratos	BlockChain Log	HTL
WP 6	CO.WP6.2: Use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data	X	X	X			X						
	CO.WP6.7: Use of Virtual Operation Support Teams (VOSTs)		X										
	CO.WP6.11: Minimum set of competencies and skills for volunteers and integration in the field operational procedures.			X									
	CO.WP6.10: Using common procedures and standards for training and civil-military actions			X									
	CO.WP6.5: Standardization of education and training for first aid responses (Creation of a Training kit: curriculum, methodology and training manual).			X									

Table 10 - WP6 opportunities in Use Cases and Tools

6.10. Use Cases Outputs

The selected opportunities were tested in the use cases. Each of the opportunities has a deep analysis in:

- Date and location
- Participants
- Description
- Execution
- Analysis and results
- History of corrective measures
- Lessons learned
- Quality
- End-user feedback
- Result

The full results can be seen in the use case deliverables.

The final results of the Use Cases are very extensive, so to see the detail it is necessary to refer to the deliverables below:

- D7.5: Report of the use case: Spain-Portugal
- D7.6: Report of the use case: Slovakia-Italy
- D7.7: Report of the use case: Bulgaria-Greece
- D7.8: Report of the use case: Norway-Netherlands

Moreover, the project has produced lessons learned and recommendations for the reference integration that can be seen in deliverable D7.4 Reference Integration and Lessons Learned report.

7. Conclusions

The project has obtained conclusive results. The results of each of the gaps, opportunities and opportunity tests are of great value in themselves.

The harmonization report of this deliverable represents a clear landscape of the methodology followed to bring the project to the most enriching conclusions.

For more details on any of the points, please refer to previous versions of this deliverable or to the specifics of the technical area.

8. Annex A – References and bibliography

8.1. Internal references

1. VALKYRIES - D2.2 Terminology and semantics
2. VALKYRIES - D2.12 Harmonization framework
3. VALKYRIES – D3.10 Report on sustainable certification conformity and evaluation
4. VALKYRIES - D4.6 Harmonisation opportunities on the technological landscape for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters
5. VALKYRIES - D4.3 Roadmap for enhancing the pan-European technological capabilities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters
6. VALKYRIES - D4.4 Harmonisations on first aid response technologies and equipment
7. VALKYRIES - D5.6 Harmonization opportunities on the operational and procedural landscape for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters
8. VALKYRIES - D5.3 Roadmap for enhancing the pan-European operational and procedural capabilities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters
9. VALKYRIES - D5.4 Harmonisations on first aid response common practices and procedures
10. VALKYRIES - D6.6 Harmonization opportunities on the preparedness and cross-sectorial collaboration for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters
11. VALKYRIES - D6.3 Roadmap for enhancing the pan-European preparedness and cross-sectorial collaboration for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters
12. VALKYRIES – D6.4 Harmonisations on first aid preparedness and cross-sectorial collaboration
13. VALKYRIES – D7.4 Reference Integration and Lessons Learned report
14. VALKYRIES – D7.5: Report of the use case: Spain-Portugal
15. VALKYRIES – D7.6: Report of the use case: Slovakia-Italy
16. VALKYRIES – D7.7: Report of the use case: Bulgaria-Greece
17. VALKYRIES – D7.8: Report of the use case: Norway-Netherlands

9. Annex B - Glossary

Acronym	Description
WP	Work Package
UC	Use Case
SOPs	Standard Operational Procedures
C&C	Command and Control
EAB	External Advisory Board
EU	European Union
FAV	First Aid Vehicles
GA	Grant Agreement
FRS	Fire and Rescue Service
GIS	Geographic Information System
EMS	Emergency Medical Services
ISO	International Organisation for Standardisation
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
MCD	Minimum Common Data
MCI	Multi Casualty Incident

Table 11 – Glossary

10. Annex C – Gaps

This annex is a selection of the Gaps described in D4.6, D5.6, D6.6 and D3.10

First aid vehicles and supportive autonomous units			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G4.1-1a	Accurate and live weather data	Open-source data	Weather information is important in all SAR operations. Temperature, precipitation, wind speed and direction are common for all cases. Other data such as humidity, barometric data, wave high and so is important in some cases.
G4.1-1b	Up to date information about terrain and infrastructure	Map information as well as pictures	In a large-scale disaster situation like earthquakes, floodings or fires, the terrain affected will change. Roads may have disappeared, or rivers have new courses. To give as effective disaster relief as possible, it is essential for the first responders to have an updated and accurate map. This has traditionally been done with aircrafts and satellites. If the first responder teams have access to drones, they can scan the area based on their own needs and can get an accurate picture of the situation for their tasks: if it is firefighting, evacuation, or logistical support.
G4.1-2	Safety for first responders		One of the first principles is own (responder) safety. Especially in case of first-line responders who are facing unknown situation. In case of CBRN incident, the first thing to consider after the presence of hazardous materials is suspected or confirmed at the scene, is to remember to prioritise own personal safety so responder can do the job without becoming a casualty. Use caution and keep a safe distance to avoid exposure own self and by avoiding unnecessary contact with casualties, people and surfaces that may have been contaminated.
G4.1-2a	Tracking of personnel and casualties	Position	A common problem in all disaster area operations is tracking of personnel. By using a blockchain based tag system on emergency response personnel and vehicles the command centre can have live updated information of where they are physically. This information has several possible benefits, such as area monitoring for better understanding of what areas have been searched (historic track data), to provide assistance to personnel in congested areas

First aid vehicles and supportive autonomous units			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
			or inside buildings in order to find quickest and/or safest way to injured people for medical aid and evacuation or to get them to safe areas if the situation deteriorate.
G4.1-2b	Safe work environment for first responder personnel	Information on toxicity, radioactivity and similar challenges	In all disaster relief operations, especially in urban areas, the present of hazardous or toxic material is highly possible. To protect the personnel involved with the right protective gear and to decide the best approach to the task, it is vital to know what type of substances may be present or what the smoke from the fire contains the present of toxicity or hazardous gases or material.
G4.1-3a	Build ad hoc communication grids	Physical units are placed out in the disaster area to re-establish communication	In large disasters the probability that the existing communication grids may be destroyed or overloaded. To make a temporary grid is paramount to secure the transfer of data files and the ability to access different databases. Drones can provide relay nodes in a grid and UGVs and USV can be base stations and battery charges.
G4.1-3b	Distribution of equipment	Transport of needed equipment to first responders	In all disaster relief operation, the first responders will need different type of equipment. A lot of it, like bandages and medication, may be in continuous demand from the first responders. To get equipment from the storage areas and out to the first responder teams is logistically demanding under normal condition but in a disaster area with destroyed roads and inaccessible areas this will become a challenge. In recent years is it developed several unmanned vehicles with the purpose to transport goods. For the first leg, from main storage areas, UGVs can transport goods and equipment to the forward operation bases (FOB). From FOB, a UAV can take small parcels to the first responders in the field. Also, at sea, the possibility exists to use USV as transport units from shore to disaster area and use UAV to distribute the parcels to the different vessels operating in the areas.
G4.1-3c	Supply energy and charging capabilities	All electrically driven units need charging close to the operation area	Relatively small UAV's, USV's and UGV's has a short operation time, typically 30 to 60 minutes, and a limited speed. It is often crucial that charging facilities can be moved close to the operation area. These "mother"

First aid vehicles and supportive autonomous units			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
			vehicles can either be ground or water based and also act as a communication centre.
G4.1-4	Conduct search and relief missions		Unmanned systems have a potential to give first relief to casualties found by surveillance drones or by tracking of mobile phones the system can deliver lifesaving equipment to the persons in need or by someone nearby with the possibilities to assists.

Table 12 – Gaps from First aid vehicles and supportive autonomous units

Trusted communication infrastructure and end-user terminals			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G4.2-1	Communication coverage and availability	Professional experience	Current technologies used for communication present coverage limitations, especially in rural areas. This is a drawback for emergency agencies that rely in specific technologies.
G4.2-2	Network recovering in case of disaster	Professional experience and Survey	Network architecture deployed during multiple casualty emergencies may not have adequate mechanisms to recover telecommunications services.
G4.2-3	Limited coverage ranges in communications devices	Professional experience and Survey	Due to the heterogeneity of the devices, many of which are limited in performance, data transmissions are made over short distances.
G4.2-4	Bandwidth appropriate to the level of coverage	Literature	The types of use cases in a disaster response scenario—sharing high resolution GIS maps, streaming video, and large amounts of voice communication—necessitate high-bandwidth and low-latency connections.
G4.2-5	Dynamic device selection based on transmission preference	Literature	Particularly in disaster events, networks in affected areas typically receive very high volumes of incoming calls and data. A limiting factor is concurrency with large numbers of devices communicating simultaneously.
G4.2-6	Lack of secure communications	Survey	Certain emergency services do not use secure communications for sensitive data transmission.
G4.2-7	Lack of communications security monitoring	Survey	Most network architectures deployed in emergencies do not have network monitoring systems capable of detecting threats or anomalies.
G4.2-8	Most communication	Professional experience and Surveys	Technologies used nowadays in emergency scenarios work insulated from the rest.

Trusted communication infrastructure and end-user terminals			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
	technologies are not interoperable		
G4.2-9	Lack of strategies to determine the best technology based on security constraints	Professional experience	There are no regulations or guidelines for selecting the most suitable communication technology or protocols based on security requirements.
G4.2-10	There are no strict guidelines for backup plans	Surveys	There is a lack of regulations that enforce emergency institutions to implement backup plans
G4.2-11	There are no contingency plans at EU level for data restoration	Professional experience	In case of data loss, there are no clear guidelines on how to proceed.
G4.2-12	Lack of redundancy systems and services in the event of failure or catastrophe	Professional experience	In the event of an emergency affecting the proposed systems, there are no identical systems to make up for this shortcoming.
G4.2-13	Ad hoc network coverage	Literature	As multiple devices, and thus technologies, will be involved in the emergency actuations, the coverage provided by ad hoc deployment could not include all of them.
G4.2-14	Personal Data	Literature	As the data related with emergency actuations will likely be personal and sensible data, it is possible that not all the confidentiality requirements will be satisfied.
G4.2-15	Accurate service provisioning	Literature	Due to the variability of the first aid actuations, the service provisioning might be inaccurate, leading to malfunctions and security breaches.
G4.2-16	Ad hoc network scope	Professional experience	Ad hoc emergency services networks are often developed at regional, local or even agency level in EU countries (e.g., in Spain), which runs counter to the interoperability of systems and services in emergency response.
G4.2-17	Inadequate reliability of the 2G, 3G or 4G network in disasters	Literature	2G, 3G or 4G are the most widely used alternative to TETRA radio systems by the emergency services, especially in terms of data transmission. But reality shown that their capacity and availability is very limited in mass casualty incidents, where these

Trusted communication infrastructure and end-user terminals			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
			networks often have collapsed within first minutes.
G4.2-18	Negative burden of low frequency of use and legacy solutions	Professional experience	The networks used by the Emergency Services are generally adequate for their usual activity and will have involved a significant investment over time. Large new investments in infrastructure or devices with no obvious day-to-day impact, but only for infrequent incidents such as MCIs, is an unattractive prospect for their managers.
G4.2-19	Consolidated reported information	Literature	Creation of communication agreements. Development of message structures. Identification of profiles, roles and protocols.
G4.2-20	Asymmetric information flow	Professional experience	In the first moments of the disaster, the avalanche of information coming from the incident site can overwhelm the coordinating centre's ability to receive and process it.
G4.2-21	Line saturation	Professional experience	The use of shared technologies (e.g., mobile network, fixed telephone network) may be saturated not only by the personnel involved in the disaster, but also by other incidental or non-participants in the disaster. Each technology has certain limits for handling concurrent calls.
G4.2-22	Terminals that are difficult to operate in disaster situations	Professional experience	Terminals commonly used by emergency services provide a service adapted to a use that can be excessively complicated in the event of disasters, requiring many operations to initiate communication, and interruptions or disruptions that make communication difficult.
G4.2-23	Minimum acceptable technology requirements	Professional experience	Determine minimum technological characteristics to guarantee optimal service level in emergency and disaster situations.
G4.2-24	Local data collection	Professional experience	Explore new sensors data networks (e.g., Lora) devices to collect local data.
G4.2-25	FR and Victims data	Professional experience	Explore new devices to collect First responder and victims' data.
G4.2-26	TETRA coms	Literature	Coverage of TETRA data do not uniform across the users.

Trusted communication infrastructure and end-user terminals			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G4.2-27	Coms range extension	Professional experience	Use of relay nodes to extend the RF communications coverage of or to overcome Line of sight Communications limitations.
G4.2-28	Data rates	Literature	Different networks data rates impact quality of the data channelling through networks.
G4.2-29	Data latency	Literature	Different networks latency impact quality of the data channelling through networks.
G4.2-30	Data Priority	Literature	In a limited bandwidth communications context, the absence of operational data priority impacts the decision-making process and managing of critical situation.
G4.2-31	Data protocols	Literature	Federated data may not be transmitted to different network if data protocols are not supported.
G4.2-32	IP network layer	Literature	Not all communication devices or networks support IP layer as a standard.
G4.2-33	Data shared	Professional experience	Different entities codify its data communication using different data protocols
G4.2-34	Communications redundancy	Professional experience	Emergency events often face multiple communications issues, such as communication connectivity, constraints, networks unavailability, congestion, etc.
G4.2-35	Data cluster	Professional experience	As the volume of information and data increases in large scale incidents, the data loss and recover, as well as the data sharing latencies and delays may impact the overall performance of the system.
G4.2-36	APPS/Functions redundancy	Professional experience	In emergency situation, a federated solution of applications/functions may be unavailable in case of communication / connectivity loss.
G4.2-37	Blockchain redundancy	Professional experience	Operational redundancy required redundancy may not jeopardize the system security.
G4.2-38	Share health data	Literature	Use a common data protocol / standard to share health data.
G4.2-39	Querying data	Literature and professional experience	Query different data sources in a common, scalable and efficient way.
G4-2-40	System fragility due to interdependencies	Professional experience	Systems that consist of interdependent services may be face loss of functionalities even if one support service (dependency) fails.

Trusted communication infrastructure and end-user terminals			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G4.2-41	Legal and regulatory constraints	Literature and professional experience	There is a lack of protocols or legal aspects for a group of countries facing the same emergency.
G4.2-42	No institutional set-up for communications during emergencies	Professional experience	Current Government agencies and the private sector have an insufficient capacity to deal emergencies with different technical options.
G4.2-43	Constraints with cross-boundary movement of communications	Professional experience	Lack of planned management or coordination, as well as poor preparedness among international organizations.

Table 13 – Gaps from Trusted Communication infrastructure and end-user terminal

Mobile Command and Control and Operational Coordination technologies			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G4.3-1	No real-time information exchange	Professional Experience	Emergency services coordination require near real-time inputs in order to avoid delays. <i>Cross-border</i>
G4.3-2	Lack of sensory & communications integrations	Survey	Data-intensive operative environment is poorly integrated. <i>Technological</i>
G4.3-3	Insufficient the capacity of Coalition cooperation	Literature	C2 overall design purpose should accomplish coalition fulfilment. <i>Cross-border</i>
G4.3-4	Leverage logistics databases information	Literature	The aim is to function as a cross-cutting emergency system while maintaining current tools. Tools such as the GIS have to be fed with external data. <i>Cross-border and Technological</i>
G4.3-5	Delays and disconnecting	Survey	Many times, the C2 Commander is not able to take decisions due to delays and disconnecting. <i>Technological</i>
G4.3-6	Lack of C2 communication means in rural areas	Professional Experience	Prevent any comms failure due to terrain characteristics in rural areas. <i>Technological</i>
G4.3-7	Disunities COP	Professional Experience	Currently there is not a common COP of the situation. Each agency has their own events and deploy their resources in function their overview. <i>Cross-border and Technological</i>

Mobile Command and Control and Operational Coordination technologies			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G4.3-8	Situational awareness uncompleted set of information	Professional Experience	Missing set of essential information. To take advantage of the situation such as n° of tracking, n° of victims, responders, NO-GO zones and type of responders are required. <i>Cross-border</i>
G4.3-9	Non harmonisation of graphics symbols, views, and representations	Professional Experience	No global symbols. Add difficulties if the information is shared by third parties. <i>Procedural</i>
G4.3-10	Short accuracy for network transmitter	Professional Experience	Extend the range of network coverage to communicate with the 112-emergency coordination centre. <i>Technological</i>
G4.3-11	Enhance time response signal between Emergency Vehicles – Emergency Operator in GIS	Survey	The geolocation signal of emergency vehicles deployed in GIS is too slow. Real-time communications prevent issues related to navigated rescuers by operator. <i>Technological</i>
G4.3-12	Video display (CCTV) no integrated functionalities	Professional Experience	CCTV Integration with external cameras. Integrations with third party SW. <i>Technological</i>
G4.3-13	Meeting points	Survey	Map out the meeting points. <i>Cross-border</i>
G4.3-14	Type of dangerous substance	Survey	Specify the types of hazardous substances to tailor deployment and mitigate negative effects. <i>Procedural</i>
G4.3-15	Endangered areas	Survey	Overprotecting sensitive natural areas. It can cause irreparable damage to the ecosystem. <i>Procedural and Cross-border</i>
G4.3-16	Contact to incident commander or command post chief	Professional Experience	Communications improvements with Command Post Chief. <i>Procedural</i>
G4.3-17	Information area coverage by drones	Professional experience	Improve the situational awareness of large areas events, to overcome the lack of aerial information and multiple sensors capacity.
G4.3-18	Improved imagery ground resolution	Professional experience	Have a high Ground imagery sensors data resolution is critical resource to manage the situation, in particular detection of hot spots.

Mobile Command and Control and Operational Coordination technologies			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G4.3-19	Drones' data protocols	Professional experience	Imagery quality for high quality real-time data transmission requires high bandwidth and proper metadata to enable ground applications exploitation from multiple drones' providers.
G4.3-20	Nigh data gathering	Professional experience + legislation	Aviation, including drones, have limited flying condition in night condition, from sunset to sunrise, in fire events, due to safety issues. Improved aerial coordination capability is required to plan night operations.
G4.3-21	Airspace management tools	Professional experience + Regulation	With an increased number of flying drones over the operational theatre, there is a need to improve the air traffic management capability, deconflicting flight areas, establish aerial fences, and comply with safety, privacy, and air flying rules.
G4.3-22	Drones RF management tools	Professional experience	The increased number of RF communication used in MCI, including many drones operating in the same frequencies, may generated communication collision and/or loss of communication with some assets.
G4.3-23	Development of a standardised electronic triage system for the facilitation and improvement of logistics management and accomplishment of situational awareness	Literature	There is a need for a standardised system that allows for quick triage procedures to limit response times and increase situation awareness.
G4.3-24	Standardisation of systems for an automated management of resources e.g., for the assignment of resources to tasks and missions	Literature	There is a need for standardised system to be used for the management of resources e.g., geolocation of personnel and vehicles, tasks assigned to the different resources.
G4.3-25	Standardisation regarding the processing of victims' personal data	Literature	Standardisation for the compliance of sensitive data with legislations for the protection of personal data is required.

Mobile Command and Control and Operational Coordination technologies			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G4.3-26	Triage procedures	Professional experience	As no standard exists on who provides first phase triage (medical personnel only or and others), the initial identification of a victim, in most cases containing non-medical or other personal sensitive data, photos included, must be allowed using multi-colour bracelets supporting one form pf electronic tagging available (RF, 3DCode, NFT etc.). Initiation and first entry of available data has to be recorded in a secured way (strongly recommended in blockchain). Other important information related with the victim, such as location, time of triage/initiation, first-responder id etc. is captured from first responder's smart phone or tablet recording the victim.
G4.3-27	Clocks synchronization	Professional experience	Different manual or computerized systems use different clock setting methods to synchronize. As the VALKYRIES system must link different federated systems all logging transactions or metadata in a common structure (blockchain logging), clocks synchronizations should be adapted through this function
G4.3-28	The legacy of solutions for C2	Professional experience	C2 solutions have been developed largely at the agency level, highly focused on their own needs and heavily conditioned by their own development or procurement capabilities, which detracts from their effectiveness and works against accessibility and interoperability between first responders in different agencies or territories.
G4.3-29	The weight of habit	Professional experience	Unified C2 solutions developed at regional or national level are sometimes less used than would be possible because they involve incident commanders moving away from their own agency tools with which they are familiar, and in situations where stress and demands are higher.
G4.3-30	Confidentiality versus information sharing	Professional experience	The need to ensure the security of information transmission and the confidentiality of the transmitted data itself, especially in relation to emergency medical services, has sometimes worked against the development of interoperable C2 and decision support solutions, as well as

Mobile Command and Control and Operational Coordination technologies			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
			facilitating the exchange of information. Information sharing.
G4.3-31	Need for specific functionalities to meet specific needs	Professional experience	The critical information and decision criteria are indeed different in day-to-day situations managed by an Emergency Medical Service compared to a multi-casualty incident. This means that the solutions developed for day-to-day EMS C2, and decision making are often not suitable for disaster medical management, requiring specific new functionalities.
G4.3-32	Lack of social media analysis on emergency scenarios	Professional experience	There is an absence of guidelines and regulations offering recommendations for crawling social media data for analysing emergency situations.
G4.3-33	Lack of clear guidelines for selecting data crawling tools	Professional experience	There is a need at EU level for providing clear guidelines indicating which tools are more suitable for crawling social media for emergency scenarios.
G4.3-34	Cross border trace of data sharing authorization	Professional experience	Data shared among countries are subjected do international agreements and authorization which, and the identification of which data is allowed to be shared at each moment is required.
G4.3-35	Victim's advance information	Professional experience	The number of victims, its status and health conditions must be matched with the hospital medical capability and reported to the specific destination medical facility. There is no point if sharing all the data of victims to medical facilities that are will not receive the victims. It will only generate noise.
G4.3-36	Victims' health / historical data	Professional experience	Absence of the medical historical data of victims can limit the medical procedures. The victim's historical data can be directly assessed by the medical facility, but the information of the victim identification and authorization prior to its arrival to thaw medical facility may delays the medical response.
G4.3-37	Victims' data traceability	Professional experience	Improve the Victims traceability and tracking while in the response process to avoid victim loss in the transportation process, or loss of victim's awareness.
G4.3-38	FR Follow-up	Professional Experience	Last know position of FR and trace its position provides a valuable resource management capability.

Mobile Command and Control and Operational Coordination technologies			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G4.3-39	External data sources	Professional Experience	There are many potential external sources of information that can be integrated in the system, providing additional valuable data.
G4.3-40	Social media	Professional Experience	Social media data and information usability in C2 systems requires a careful filtering and validation to avoid misinformation and data noise.
G4.3-41	Wide use of sensors	Professional Experience	There is a wide range of new sensors and protocol, easy to deploy that can provide valuable field data, and are not currently exploited.
G4.3-42	Traceability of victims	Personal experience	In MCIs, victims, especially unconscious ones, maybe transferred to a medical facility without their families being notified, rendering their tracking extremely difficult both for the families and the relevant authorities as well.
G4.3-43	Identification of dangerous zones	Professional experience	The identification of dangerous zones varies across countries and organisations.
G4.3-44	Identification of relevant locations	Professional experience	Organisations use different technological solutions to identify relevant locations.
G4.3-45	No widespread use of decision support applications	Professional experience	The use of decision support applications is not widespread in the emergency services.
G4.3-46	Standardization of operating procedures	Professional experience	The need to update current operating procedures with new standards, equipment and devices is detected.
G4.3-47	New command and control standards	Professional experience	Necessary review of command-and-control standards.

Table 14 – Gaps from Mobile Command and Control and Operational Coordination technologies

The digitalization on first aid actuations			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G4.4-1	Lack of iconographic standard	Professional experience	It is required to standardize the iconographic representation used by the organizations during the first aid actuations.
G4.4-2	Iconographic discrepancies	Professional experience	It is common than the signalling employed during emergency actuations will present usage discrepancies between nations/organizations.
G4.4-3	Language barrier	Literature	Currently, every nation uses its language in emergency communications, hindering the information sharing.

The digitalization on first aid actuations			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G4.4-4	Data Normalization	Professional experience	As multiple digitalization instances should be interconnected, such as DTAs and Static models, the data should be normalized or standardized in a common language.
G4.4-5	Graphical capabilities	Professional experience	Although the digital modelling does not require too much computing nor graphical capabilities, not all the systems currently involved during first aid actuations might be able to support its representation.
G4.4-6	Continuous communication	Literature	As the digital representation should be a faithful representation of the emergency actuations, the information should be constantly updated.
G4.4-7	Ad-hoc network coverage	Literature	The digitalization of first aid actuation poses as a challenge itself, and the integration with suboptimal networks might be a hard challenge that should be addressed during ad-hoc deployments during emergency actuations.
G4.4-8	Neglecting to facilitate the work of the first responder leads to the failure of proposals.	Professional experience	Digitalization solutions for EMS intervention in multiple casualty situations do not always identify the main objective of making the work of first responders easier in these situations, which are even more demanding and stressful than usual. This reduces the chances of success.
G4.4-9	Reliability and usability in extreme conditions, a necessity in disaster response.	Professional experience	The reliability and usability of electronic devices in extreme conditions is very high nowadays, but there are specific conditions in disaster intervention that still need to be improved: behaviour in rain or blood, usability with stained gloves, use in low visibility conditions, excessive brightness or radical contrasts, etc.
G4.4-10	Generational digital divide in healthcare	Literature	Despite technological advances and growth of social demand to incorporate them into daily clinical practice, the level of implementation of digital innovation in the healthcare sector is still limited and slow, partly due to the generational digital divide.
G4.4-11	Excessive use of non-digital communications	Professional experience	Most emergency services in Europe use voice as their primary means of communication. Moreover, this use is sometimes not very brief and not very protocolled.

The digitalization on first aid actuations			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G4.4-12	Digitization increases the workload of first responders.	Professional experience	Related to G4.4-8. Many digital technologies currently used in emergency services are not useful for multiple casualty care because they require a lot of work, rather than freeing up first responders to deal with casualty care.
G4.4-13	Lack of uses of AI-based systems	Survey	Currently there are no artificial intelligence-based systems for support in emergency situations.
G4.4-14	Lack of training systems	Survey	Currently, no gamification-based techniques are used for RF training.

Table 15 – Gaps from the digitalization on first aid actuations

Instrumentation and health support wearables devices			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G4.5-1	Lack of user tracking	Professional experience - Survey	Currently, emergency incident management systems do not have methods for automatic tracking of both users and FRs in emergency incidents.
G4.5-2	Dependence of coverage on user tracking	Professional experience - Survey	Currently systems are not adapted to different needs depending on the coverage available.
G4.5-3	Lack of user identification	Professional experience - Survey	There are currently no devices that allow for the identification of users in emergency scenarios.
G4.5-4	Current commercial devices do not have the necessary technologies.	Personal experience	Current commercial devices are severely limited in terms of the communication technologies available to them.
G4.5-5	Inaccessibility to the firmware of the devices.	Literature review	Modification of the firmware that is built into commercial devices is either very costly or impossible, so it cannot be adapted to the requested needs.
G4.5-6	Reduced device battery life	Literature review	The battery life of devices can be greatly reduced when, depending on the technology they incorporate and how they are used.
G4.5-7	Lack of use of wearable devices for first triage	Professional experience	Wearable devices are not currently used to assign a first triage to patients in an emergency.
G4.5-8	Lack of devices to measure health status continuously in patients.	Professional experience	Currently no systems are used to monitor the different bio-signals of a patient and define the severity of the patient automatically.

Instrumentation and health support wearables devices			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G4.5-9	Different communication systems between First Responders	Professional experience	At present different agencies use different communication systems (VHF, mobile phone, TETRA) which may have signal problems, and which often do not "talk" to each other.
G4.5-10	No common communication standard between different countries	Professional experience	Even when, within the same country, there is a single strategy for communication between agencies in emergencies this standard is hardly ever extended beyond national borders
G4.5-11	Difficult to report a personal threat	Professional experience	The diffusion of solutions that make it possible to transmit requests for help or autonomously report dangerous situations of the FRs (e.g., panic buttons on radio equipment or position sensor) is still not widespread. In addition to this, the information is almost always transmitted to the system by voice over local networks
G4.5-12	Not immediate detection and reporting hazards during crisis response	Professional experience	The use of personal sensors is often limited to CO and low O2 detection. Sensors sensitive to different substances and explosimeters are often hand-held devices. Wearables that allow a personal hazard warning to be sent are still uncommon.
G4.5-13	Dissemination of safety and security information to FRs	Professional experience	Transmission of safety- and security-related information is almost always via voice over local radio networks
G4.5-14	Inaccurate Disaster Fatality Identification	Professional experience	Only in some realities are images of the find scene captured, usually by camera, without the ability to transmit and store them quickly and safely. In addition, much other information is not detected (e.g., GPS location).
G4.5-15	Problems related to mortuary laws	Professional experience - literature	There are no shared DVI procedures between different countries. There is no clear guidance on how to make a presumptive identification already at an MCI site. The use of technological aids in the field is minimized
G4.5-16	Lack of validated protocols for e-triage	Literature	Triage protocols for MCI based on the parameters that can be monitored by the sensors currently integrated in wearables, which are still limited, have not yet been validated.

Instrumentation and health support wearables devices			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G4.5-17	Logistical constraints	Professional experience	To be effective in an MCI, wearable devices for instrumentation and healthcare support need to be in place at the scene in the first moments of the accident. The logistics of ensuring this are complex, especially in widely dispersed emergency medical services. Conventional EMS vehicles, primarily ambulances, often have significant space constraints that leave little room for additional equipment.
G4.5-18	Relevance of investment in wearable technology in MCI	Professional experience	The investment in the development or acquisition of wearables and communication solutions for the location, traceability, or e-triage of victims in an MCI is considerable in large emergency medical services, being resources with a relatively low frequency of use compared to other resources destined for daily activity. Together with the fact that it does not lead to direct cost savings, it is often unattractive to the healthcare manager.
G4.5-19	Investing in acquisition may not be the best option.	Professional experience	Due to the accelerated rate of innovation in these devices, an eventual investment in procurement may quickly make these devices technologically outdated.
G4.5-20	Unified User roles	Professional experience	Each application and entity have its organizational structure, roles and accesses/permissions for their users. Sharing data in a non-coherent federation role structure can generate loss of trust and accountability.
G4.5-21	D2D communications integration	Professional experience	There is no global standard to easily integrate D2D communications assets and its data into a federated network.
G4.5-22	Victims monitor data	Professional experience	Critical data on the health status of victims are not available for medical services to prepare their response.
G4.5-23	Telemedicine	Professional experience	In fast development and large events nonskilled personnel may provide minimal assistance to victims in life threatening situation, where a remote guidance on how to provide minimal life support actions could save life. A Telemedicine service is required to provide this support.
G4.5-24	Cost of modern technology equipment	Professional experience	Modern technological equipment, especially devices aimed for victims, may be too costly to purchase in adequate quantities, even for MCIs with relatively low numbers of victims,

Instrumentation and health support wearables devices			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
			leading FR agencies to have limited resources for when a crisis strikes.
G4.5-25	Wearables for most critically ill patients.	Professional experience	They may not be suitable for the most critically ill patients in whom injuries may make it difficult or impossible to place and take vital signs.
G4.5-26	Lack of standardization of the functionalities of wearables	Literature	Wearable devices have functionalities such as heart rate, blood oxygen level, but we do not know how reliable they are.
G4.5-27	Lack of functionalities according to medical regulations	Literature	The information provided by the wearables should be medical regulations, so that it can be interpreted by any doctor.
G4.5-28	First responders not available for wearables	Literature	In order to protect first responders through wearables, it is necessary to provide them with these devices.
G4.5-29	Lack of a global regulation regarding the working conditions of first responders.	Literature	Wearable devices have functionalities such as stress level, sleep hours which can help to control your physical and mental state.

Table 16 – Gaps from Instrumentation and health support wearables devices

Crisis response planning			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G5.1.1-1	Lack of standardisation of terms and symbols for a common interpretation of data and a common operational picture	LITERATURE	There is no standardised glossary of terms, semantic representations or symbols sufficiently comprehensive to serve at EU level as a reference for planning, development, communications or operational actions in relation to MCIs and disasters.
G5.1.1-2	Following of Guidelines of EU Civil Protection	SURVEY	Harmonization towards acceptance, preparation and activation of EU's Civil Protection Guidelines is not achievable due to G1 and G1 above
G5.1.1-3	Lack of regulatory harmonisation between countries in	SURVEY	Lack of harmonization between the law of different territories in relation to MCI and disaster planning or response.

Crisis response planning			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
	disaster planning and response		
G5.1.1-4	Inconsistency of crisis response plans	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	In Mass Casualty Incidents are all crisis response plans inconsistent between all involved emergency agencies. Most of the emergency plans were created but have not been updated many years. Plans are outdated and do not reflect nowadays situation.
G5.1.1-5	Lack of dissemination of emergency plans	SURVEY	Lack of implementation of civil protection plans: lack of dissemination, education of the population, education and training of those involved and development of operational procedures for action groups.
G5.1.1-6	Rescue Plans Activation Gap	LITERATURE	As cross-border incidents might influence the involved countries unproportionally to their criteria, the activation of Crisis Management Rescue Plans as per their criteria might not signal the need for C2 handling from both countries' emergency operations centres
G5.1.1-7	Roles definition Gaps	LITERATURE	Different "role definitions" and privileges accessing data are in place between different federated systems. Such systems are tuned to support operations, workflows and procedure from such roles accordingly. Their gaps might create huge problems in data exchange between federated systems if a centralized approach is in force, resulting to non-operational systems

Table 17 – Gaps from crisis response planning

Reconnaissance and triage			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G5.1.2-1	Different EMS structure and composition	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	The structure and composition of the Emergency Services varies considerably from country to country or region to region, which is a factor favouring a great diversity in chains of command and operational procedures.

Reconnaissance and triage			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G5.1.2-2	Ununified procedures	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	In each country, different types of actors as first responders, military and civilians, are involved with completely different approach as per their logistics and/or their C2, following operational procedures completely different between countries. Thus, their harmonization on common procedures is difficult to impossible.
G5.1.2-3	Different professional competencies among first responders	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	The capacity to administer specific medical care at the scene of a disaster varies according to the professional profiles deployed at the scene of the emergency and the professional competencies established by law in each country, e.g., presence or absence of physicians.
G5.1.2-4	Lack of first responders' knowledge and preparation	LITERATURE	The lack of preparedness of responders sometimes results in inadequate knowledge of procedures, access, use of PPE and safety measures, etc., which compromises the disaster response.
G5.1.2-5	Lack of common training and certification	SURVEY	There is no common training and certification at first responder level (EMS & Fire Service) in first aid. In some European countries for example the fire brigade can give first aid interventions/manoeuvres etc while in others not.
G5.1.2-6	Non-standardised zoning	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	Zoning is essential for organising the response to the accident on the scene. However, the definition of working zones differs between different agencies, in each case generally according to the specific needs of the institutions: security, firefighting and rescue, health care.
G5.1.2-7	Ambulances tracking and recording	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	The vehicles arrive from different areas, not all ambulances have a GPS system that speaks to each other.
G5.1.2-8	Non-standardised victim registration and affiliation information	LITERATURE	Victim registration and affiliation: information and the procedure of registering and exchanging victim's information is not unified, and traceability is not guaranteed in cross-border incidents or where different agencies work together.

Reconnaissance and triage			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G5.1.2-9	Different triage standards and practices in use within countries between different first responders	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	Not harmonized procedures in first triage and evacuation. First responders are unclear who is responsible for this task. In many EU countries these procedures vary. Detailed triage and first medical support to victims or short triage and fast evacuation - this is also challenging issue. In some countries, trained firefighters, coast guards or volunteers provide first stage triage, prior to the handling of the victim to EMS, in others not. The harmonization in cross-border incidents is difficult to impossible, mainly for victims with ethnics or citizenship that differs to the country's agent that rescued.
G5.1.2-10	Non-standardised victim priority tagging	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	Victim tagging: tapes, triage cards, wearables... The alphanumeric or colour codes that make the priority of victims visible are not completely unified.
G5.1.2-11	Victim's clinical information	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	Lack of clinical information based on patient conditions
G5.1.2-12	Non-consensual criteria for determining means and destination of transfer	LITERATURE	Evacuation and transfer: There are no agreed recommendations for deciding the means of evacuation in MCI, which must be timely and appropriate to ensure quality care, but taking into account the real availability of resources in each case.
G5.1.2-13	Limited involvement of many hospital facilities in MCI and disaster response planning	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	Evacuation and transfer: in many cases the involvement of hospitals in the response to external MCIs is somewhat passive, limited to updating their capabilities at the request of the command centre in charge of the incident.
G5.1.2-14	Unified standards for debriefing and evaluation	SURVEY	Standards and procedures between emergency agencies for debriefing and evaluation are not unified and connected

Table 18 – Gaps from reconnaissance and triage

Communications maintenance, logistics and deployment			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G5.2.1 -1	Communication needs	SURVEY	Experiencing communication difficulties between the other various technical actors
G5.2.1 -2	Outdated technology and system	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	In common - most emergency agencies (Firefighters, EMS,...) face the problem that technology and systems are outdated
G5.2.1 -3	Lack of portability	LITERATURE	The lack of portability force users of one service to learn the other service's application, or for the application and hardware system to integrate with the larger system
G5.2.1 -4	Excessive use of radio communication	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	Radio networks with voice information transmission are widely used, but have limited data transmission capacity, which is insufficient to build a common operational picture for disaster assessment and decision-making. In general the first responder are provided with radio communication, which means that they become saturated and errors can be made in the transmission of message
G5.2.1 -5	Use of non-optimal alternative communication channels in MCI	LITERATURE	Given the limitations of radio networks, the alternative use of mobile and fixed telephone networks for strategic and operational communications makes it difficult to exchange information with other responders in MCI or disasters.
G5.2.1 -6	Usage of different software within emergency services	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	Not all emergency services use the same software - therefore the communication between operators within the system could lead to losing some important information about the whole incident or particular part of it.
G5.2.1 -7	Limited use of e-health options in MCI and disasters	LITERATURE	Limited use of e-health technologies, which are currently revolutionising standard healthcare, in MCI and disaster response.
G5.2.1 -8	Operating procedures conditioned by obsolete ICTs	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	The obsolete communication systems available to some emergency services condition their own operational procedures, forcing them to devote excessive efforts and resources to these purposes, to the detriment of the effectiveness of victim care.

Communications maintenance, logistics and deployment			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G5.2.1-9	Recording information sometimes make it difficult for first responders to do their job.	LITERATURE	The need to enter information into the C2 system by voice or by manual typing of data places a significant burden on first responders and limits the fluidity and even accuracy of the data.

Table 19 – Gaps from communication maintenance, logistics and deployment

Others maintenance, logistics and deployment			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G5.2.2-1	Lack of standardisation of logistical procedures	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	Logistics and health deployment procedures are not standardised in MCI or disasters.
G5.2.2-2	Lack of inter-agency logistics procedures	SURVEY	There are no unified inter-agency crisis procedures for logistics, maintenance and deployment.
G5.2.2-3	Insufficient logistics management tools at the national level	LITERATURE	There is a good interlocking of logistics managed by the EU and the UN, but there are deficiencies in the tools to support pre-disaster logistics planning in the different countries.
G5.2.2-4	Variability in logistics resources for disaster response.	SURVEY	The availability of certain deployment support elements such as communications and logistics vehicles, signalling elements, triage tags, PPE or facilities to set up an advanced medical post is inconsistent.
G5.2.2-5	Insufficient and non-standardised training in logistics applied to MCI and disasters	SURVEY	Despite EU recommendations for standardised formal education in humanitarian logistics, specialised training needs to be coordinated for each country.

Table 20 – Gaps from others maintenance, logistics and deployment

Command and control and support to operational decision-making			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G5.3.1-1	Not a unique C2 emergency operations centre operating in all countries	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	In most cases, different C2 non-compatible emergency operations centres operate even within the same country to support/manage police, health or firefighters/first responders. As so, different "operational view" is available to each C2, resulting to mismanagement or not proper execution of the rescue plan. The same stands for cross-border incidents

Command and control and support to operational decision-making			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G5.3.1-2	Different crisis emergency operation's centre locations	SURVEY	For Medical and non-medical organizations, the crisis emergency operations centres (EOC) are located in different places. It could be an issue because currently there are limited resources in terms of communication and may difficult decision-making management task by Command Post Leaders.
G5.3.1-3	Lack of integration of certain emergency services in the emergency operations centre.	SURVEY	In some countries, emergency operations centres do not integrate all emergency services, which can delay the provision of incident information and make coordination between services difficult.
G5.3.1-4	Municipality supportive agents excluded from C2	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	During disasters, municipalities or cities are engaged in first respond agents, mainly as logistics or supporting agents. In some countries they are included with such roles in emergency plans, in others not. There is a gap that need to be faced as municipality's local C2s usually are not included or communicate properly with C2
G5.3.1-5	Heterogeneous emergency systems in different territories	LITERATURE	EU countries have a similar crisis management system but the structure and composition of their EMSs are different, with command or operational coordination roles differing more or less substantially from each other. This hampers the homogeneity of procedures, inter-agency dialogue and the effective exchange of information.
G5.3.1-6	Different criteria for assigning roles in different territories	LITERATURE	Civil Protection recommendations on planning establish in a more or less homogeneous way the tasks to be attended to and the roles to be established to ensure an adequate response to the disaster. But these roles are not always assigned to the same services in the different plans.
G5.3.1-7	Linear plans and positive control not thriving in complex situations	LITERATURE	Current C2 Systems are not flexible in multidisciplinary environments and highly susceptible to changes due to complex situations.
G5.3.1-8	Difference in overall incident command in the emergency	SURVEY	There are differences regarding overall incident command at the emergency operations centre in the response to an MCI

Command and control and support to operational decision-making			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
	operations centre.		or disaster: it may be firefighters or civil protection.
G5.3.1-9	Difference in overall incident command at the scene.	SURVEY	There is a lot of variability in relation to which agency has overall on-scene command in the response to an MCI or disaster.
G5.3.1-10	Difference in hazard control and zoning command	SURVEY	The agency responsible for hazard control and zoning may be firefighters, civil protection or even police, depending on different plans and territories.
G5.3.1-11	Difference in rescue command	SURVEY	There is variability in who has overall on-scene rescue command in response to an MCI or disaster: it can be firefighters, EMS, or even some police units (e.g. mountain group of the Guardia Civil in Spain).
G5.3.1-12	Complexity of C2 information flows	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	The flow of both operational and command and control information with the current systems that support it is often too complex, leading to slowdowns and increased likelihood of errors.
G5.3.1-13	Legacy C2 applications	SURVEY	In common - outdated technology and systems
G5.3.1-14	Interoperability C2	SURVEY	Interoperability issues. Integrated informational and GIS systems that will interact with all stakeholders are not configured and deployed.
G5.3.1-15	Communication delays among the interveners.	LITERATURE	There are delays among the interveners in the process of information acquisition, communication and decision-making.
G5.3.1-16	Lost Communications and their logs	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	As there is not any existing common logging system of communications, messages or transactions between operators of the same C2, it is likely that crucial data can be lost, especially in cases where auditing is required to support victim cases in courts.
G5.3.1-17	Time synchronization gap	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	Logging of events or transactions with no time synchronization might create problems in auditing procedures

Command and control and support to operational decision-making			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G5.3.1-18	Lack of C2 education and training	PROFESSION AL EXPERIENCE	Joint workflows between C2 systems are not standardised and often require the support of training programmes, which are often insufficient.
G5.3.1-19	Very limited capacity for ex-post analysis in C2	LITERATURE	The information that is currently recorded in relation to command-and-control decisions or operational actions is very limited, and that which is recorded in real time does not generally associate data that would make it possible to determine the justification, origin, timing, etc. This makes it practically impossible to carry out a complete objective analysis of the incidents in order to obtain useful and contrasted information.

Table 21 – Gaps from command and control and support to operational decision-making

Common Operational Picture			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G5.4.1-1	Legal constraints to interoperability	PROFESSION AL EXPERIENCE	There are legal barriers that substantially constrain interoperability between technologies and information exchange platforms in C2.
G5.4.1-2	Insufficient awareness of information exchange between agencies and territories	SURVEY	Lack of collaboration between agencies of different administrative dependencies, due to political factors or those associated with the organisational culture.
G5.4.1-3	Need to better understand the needs of other emergency services	PROFESSION AL EXPERIENCE	There is a need to develop a common knowledge base of the different expertise of emergency personnel, from which to understand how the different responders interpret each other's needs and coordination requirements and interact with each other.
G5.4.1-4	Differing information needs for decision making	LITERATURE	The EMS first responders shares less information with other responders in MCI and disaster response. Security and firefighters have common information needs.
G5.4.1-5	No consensus on the basic information to be exchanged between agencies or territories.	LITERATURE	There are no common criteria for identifying relevant information, for information exchange or for data analysis in C2. There is no consensus on the basic information that needs to be shared among emergency commanders for decision-making.

Common Operational Picture			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G5.4.1-6	No standardised information exchange processes between agencies or territories	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	In general terms, there are no standardised specific information-sharing procedures between the commanders of different agencies or different countries in disaster response.
G5.4.1-7	Limited situational awareness	LITERATURE	Limited knowledge of the situation and its scope sometimes leads to delays in sending the necessary emergency teams. Inadequate systems for recording, storing and interpreting data of relevance to C2, leading to delays in decision-making.
G5.4.1-8	Provide a shared data base of situational information/awareness is needed.	LITERATURE	An adequate COP should provide the relevant information shared by all stakeholders, without exceeding the amount of information presented, as for some users it may be irrelevant or lead to over-information.
G5.4.1-9	Unselective information overload	LITERATURE	Information overload complicates decision-making in MCI and disaster response and creates simplified mental models.
G5.4.1-10	Different weather prediction systems between countries	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	Weather prediction, influencing both the C2 decisions and the deployment of help to non-victims, are applicable between countries, following in some cases completely different models and algorithms. So critical information (as for example ground humidity, ground temperature, burning material, sea currents etc.) is not available from all weather services, problems might be created in operational decision making. As so, in cross border incidents such incompatibility has to be resolved.
G5.4.1-11	Mission assessments by technological deployments	LITERATURE	C2 Commanders decision-making relies on briefing suggestions by rest of the participants. There are no technological capabilities in order to increase procedures decision-making according to entire joint schemes of manoeuvre.
G5.4.1-12	Advanced visualization techniques required	LITERATURE	Currently, tools that allow for a common visualisation of the emergency are scarce and those that do exist offer information through

Common Operational Picture			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
			techniques that can be greatly improved.
G5.4.1-13	On-the-fly generated data representations when requested by users required.	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	To achieve an adequate COP, the different actors and disciplines must have at their disposal tools that update the information live and do so in a visually simple and understandable way.
G5.4.1-14	High risk exposure of first responders	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	Inadequate situational awareness often exposes first responders deployed to the scene of an incident or disaster to a higher than acceptable level of risk, sometimes resulting in serious injury or death.
G5.4.1-15	On scene volunteers rescuers command and COP	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	Volunteers supporting emergency incidents cannot communicate and exchange information and data with the information system of the authorities. Thus, the incident command and the emergency operations centre, cannot have information about the status of the volunteers being involved in the incident.

Table 22 – Gaps from Common Operational Picture

Alert and warning			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G5.4.2-1	Lack of a common approach in public early warning of disasters	LITERATURE	The vast majority of the society resides in areas that are prone to different types of natural hazards e.g., earthquakes, floods, tsunamis. There is not a common approach in alerting the citizens of disaster-susceptible areas before disasters occur.
G5.4.2-2	No standardized alerting procedure in National level	SURVEY	According to the answers from the questionnaire, there is no a standardized procedure at the National level for some countries of the alerting. Thus, can be easily identified a gap in the standardization across EU.
G5.4.2-3	Technical and procedural issues in alert and warning	LITERATURE	There is no homogeneity in relation to procedures, techniques and content related to warnings and early warning systems. Technical standards play an important role in communication systems. Common form to communicate disaster is important in all

Alert and warning			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
			different countries, and even so more in cross border incident. Alert and warnings must be standardized for all stakeholders.
G5.4.2-4	No definition of "High priority public warnings"	LITERATURE	"High priority public warnings" refers to alerts for situations in which people need to act immediately or within the next hour, in response to an extraordinary or significant threat that is already observed or is likely to occur. The identification of these messages is crucial to give those affected better options to preserve life and protect property, and this practice is not widespread.
G5.4.2-5	Different command competencies in alerts	SURVEY	There is no homogeneity in terms of the agencies responsible for warning and alerting the population (Civil Protection, fire brigade).
G5.4.2-6	Outdated warning systems	LITERATURE	In many cases, the technological resources to promote early warning and the appropriate issuing and dissemination of warnings are not up to date.
G5.4.2-7	Cross Border Alarms and Warnings gap	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	Issued Alarms or Warnings in cross-border incidents are not available. This could create problems in their handling.
G5.4.2-8	Fight against misinformation and rumours or fake news	LITERATURE	Communication management in crisis situations is key in an interconnected society. Rumours and misinformation have been identified as a significant threat to the utility of social media and other online tools during disaster events.
G5.4.2-9	No follow-up of alarms and warnings issued	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	There is no mechanism available to monitor citizen's reactions after accepting Alarms or Warnings. As so, plans "assuming" their reaction might result to not desirable conditions

Table 23 – Gaps from Alert and warning

Resource federation and trusted information sharing			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G6.1-1	Non-technological initialisation of an emergency.	Professional experience	Communication between EU countries in cross-border incidents do not employ technological solutions for data exchange between countries. They typically communicate via phone.
G6.1-2	Cross-border data exchange in person.	Professional experience	Once the emergency is communicated, effectives from the affected countries move to the incident area and exchange

Resource federation and trusted information sharing			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
			information from the intervening agencies in person, without using technological solutions between countries.
G6.1-3	Lack of data federation between countries	Professional experience	EU countries do not implement data federation techniques to share information automatically and in real time with affected members of an emergency.
G6.1-4	Legal barriers between countries regarding resource federation	Literature	EU countries have different regulations in terms of data sharing between member countries and difficult the implantation of resource federation strategies.
G6.1-5	Dynamic management of data federation	Professional experience	There is a lack of dynamic data federation strategies in emergency scenarios.
G6.1-6	Use of pre-shared keys in symmetric cryptography	Professional experience	Symmetric cryptography uses pre-shared keys that, if stolen, could allow attackers to get access to the entire communication flow.
G6.1-7	Asymmetric cryptography requires a complex infrastructure	Literature	Asymmetric cryptography requires a complex hierarchy of certification authorities and trust relationships.
G6.1-8	Asymmetric cryptography is slow	Literature	Asymmetric cryptography operations are slower than those performed by symmetric cryptography.
G6.1-9	Data redundancy requires a considerable increase in disk space	Professional experience	The use of data redundancy techniques, such as RAID, substantially increase the disk space required to store the information.
G6.1-10	Data redundancy need to keep data up to date	Professional experience	Data coherence between data storage nodes increases the complexity to keep data up to date
G6.1-11	Inconsistencies in data redundancy	Professional experience	Distributed data in different nodes augments the likelihood of having inconsistent data.
G6.1-12	Emergency entities do not use dynamic network management techniques	Professional experience, Survey	Emergency environments use static networks for providing services, not considering dynamic network approaches such as SDN.

Resource federation and trusted information sharing			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G6.1-13	On-demand security capabilities	Professional experience	Emergency organisations do not implement capabilities to offer security actuations on demand.
G6.1-14	Lack of standardised frameworks for data federation	Professional experience and literature	Although there are several frameworks available for data federation, none is widely used by emergency organisations at EU level.
G6.1-15	Existing frameworks are specific	Professional experience and literature	Current frameworks available are not general enough to be used in multidisciplinary emergency scenarios.
G6.1-16	Federation incompatibilities	Professional experience	The coexistence of multiple data federation techniques might present incompatibilities, such as OAuth 2.0 and its incompatibility with OAuth 1.0.
G6.1-17	OAuth2 - Complex management	Literature	The management of OAuth2 becomes complex when a substantial number of institutions intervene.
G6.1-18	OAuth2 - Centralised authorisation server	Professional experience	The authorisation server could be a single point of failure in case of attacks.
G6.1-19	Shibboleth - Lack of generalised logout capabilities	Literature	Shibboleth is not able to perform a logout action over all services federated at the same time.
G6.1-20	Shibboleth - High implementation complexity	Literature	The configuration of proxy servers is a complex task that difficult the implantation of a Shibboleth infrastructure.
G6.1-21	Quantum Menace	Literature	The threat that of the quantum computing against the current cryptosystems and the harvest-now-decrypt-later attacks.
G6.1-22	Computational cost	Literature	The computational cost required during cryptographic processes during emergency actuations might pose as an obstacle.
G6.1-23	Key distribution	Literature	An inappropriate or insecure key distribution can venerate the whole cryptosystem.
G6.1-24	Distributed technologies	Literature	Distributed integrity mechanisms, such as Blockchain, might not be suitable for all the devices involved.
G6.1-25	PKI availability	Literature	The unavailability of PKI would disable the use of asymmetric schemes.
G6.1-26	Common data language	Professional experience	Define a common reference language for different entities and countries to support data integrity.

Resource federation and trusted information sharing			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G6.1-27	Common data taxonomy	Professional experience	Define a common reference taxonomy for different entities and countries to classify data.
G6.1-28	Tampered data	Professional experience and literature	Use of Blockchain to detect tampered data and data auditing.
G6.1-29	Dynamic reference schema	Professional experience	Schema database to support different data integrity models.
G6.1-30	COP marking data source	Professional experience and Literature	COP marks the data displayed according to the data source (own or external).
G6.1-31	Backup data	Professional experience	Backup and restore data to mitigate data loss.
G6.1-32	Country specific requirements on exchange of personal / sensitive data	Professional experience, country specific GDPR law requirements	No possibility to legally exchange personal / sensitive data except via recognised international organisations. Access to personal / sensitive data should be arranged only via local GDPR law requirements.
G6.1-33	Lack of interoperability between frameworks offering data federation	Professional experience and literature	The different frameworks do not offer interoperability between them. This makes it difficult to share information between organisations.
G6.1-34	Trusted minimum requirements	Professional experience and literature	Lack of collaboration on data sharing due to lack of trusted minimum requirements
G6.1-35	Unhelpful information provided by the frameworks	Professional experience and literature	Lack of collaboration in data exchange due to unhelpful information provided by the frameworks

Table 24 – Gaps from Resource federation and trusted information sharing

Education and training for first aid responses			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G6.2-1	European curricula for Basic First Aid	Literature	Cross-border co-operation in MCI requires comparable knowledge bases to provide equivalent services between countries.
G6.2-2	Lack of standard for cross-border recognition of first aid courses	Literature	It is not a universally valid European First Aid Certificate that guarantees a minimum knowledge base in first aid at within Europe.
G6.2-3	The specialty of emergency medicine	Literature	The specialty of emergency medicine is not recognised in all EU countries. It would be appropriate for the specialty to

Education and training for first aid responses			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
			be recognised at European level in order to comply with the EU Doctors Directive and to ensure the free exchange of doctors between EU countries.
G6.2-4	Lack of homogeneity in the provision of health resources for emergency and urgent care.	Literature	In most European countries, emergency care teams consist of a doctor, nurse and ambulance driver. Doctors are not part of the non-emergency ambulance staff.
G6.2-5	Variable training of paramedics in European countries.	Literature	Cross-border cooperation in ICM requires paramedics to have comparable knowledge bases and be able to provide equivalent services between countries.
G6.2-6	Lack of homogeneity in the response to multi-victim incidents.	Literature	In some countries there is no national standard operating procedure for dealing with multi-victim incidents.
G6.2-7	Ownership of emergency services.	Literature	The different ownership of emergency services (public, private...) hinders multi-agency training and education, as well as research and development. This hampers inter-sectoral cooperation.
G6.2-8	Lack of cooperation and mutual assistance between first aid providers	Literature	Each institution, organisation and team have the necessary skills and has the knowledge of the reaction but does not have the right communication and coordination system to achieve the best possible results.
G6.2-9	No standardised reporting after ICM and debriefing	Literature	There is no standardised reporting or debriefing after the management of an ICM, which would allow for a comparison of responses and lessons learned that could improve the response.
G6.2-10	Lack of common methodology for the organisation of training exercises for first responders and no joint trainings for first responders	Literature / Professional experience	Currently there is not a common way for the organisation of first responders' training exercises. Many first responders' organisations have developed guidelines for the planning, conduct and evaluation of training exercises but no universal approach exists. Joint trainings for first responders (EMS, FRS, Police, etc.) would bring more efficiency into MCI management.
G6.2-11	Lack of first responders' training in new technological solutions.	Literature	New technological innovations emerge, which can greatly facilitate first responders in their operations. On the other hand, if first responders are not

Education and training for first aid responses			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
			sufficiently trained to these technologies beforehand, may result in reluctance and attachment in older and less effective solutions.
G6.2-12	No centralised “lessons learned database” for FAR at European level	Literature	The dissemination of lessons learned after drills and real emergencies within Europe is limited
G6.2-13	Knowledge, skills and competency spread between various groups of healthcare professionals who are tasked to participate in the management of MCI	Literature	The pathway to acquiring MCI and disaster management competencies is to obtain appropriate knowledge and skills that are reinforced through consistent drills and evaluations
G6.2-14	Didactical level of trainings	Literature	Many trainings or courses aim to deliver a didactical level of knowledge. Participants/professionals participate in educational initiatives without having any knowledge of disaster management principles, i.e., command, control, communication, coordination and collaboration
G6.2-15	Lack of rescuers with full medical education	Professional experience	Emergency medical care provided to victims by rescuers with very little medical education
G6.2-16	Lack of common organizational structure and rules regarding collaboration between first aid responders	Literature	More of the documents concerning protocols, standards and etc. are connected with a different level of administrative structures.
G6.2-17	Lack of uniform national standards for FARs	Literature	Most of the documents imply common information regarding the organization for first aid process.
G6.2-18	Lack of capabilities for medical evacuating (MEDEVAC) by air	Literature	There are shortages regarding not having helicopters, system and pilots for medical evacuation by air. This prevents the execution of actions with a specialized helicopter. The military helicopters which are used in emergency situations are not suitable for these purposes.
G6.2-19	Insufficiency of modern field beds and other first aid gears	Literature	There are not enough first aid gears, including field beds, inside the FARs vehicles, because they were not thought to be used for mass casualty events. Some

Education and training for first aid responses			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
	inside the FARs vehicles		of the gear is also technically old and need replacement.
G.6.2-20	Lack of first aid courses by the BRC concerning the arriving time of the rescuing teams	Literature	There is a lack of courses for first aid provided by the BRC with the citizenry. Discounting the mandatory ones, which are taught to the candidates who are acquiring driving licence, there is a huge need for such courses to be taught in schools. Because not every citizen knows how to help someone in a disastrous situation before the arriving of the rescue team or medical doctor's help.
G.6.2-21	Lack of accessible locations of hospitals and other medical facilities in different regions of the country	Literature	There is significant displacement between the numbers of hospitals and other medical facilities in the country. There are even regions where no such facilities can be found. Excluding the bigger cities/administrative centres of the regions.
G.6.2-22	Lack of a common, national picture of vehicles/ambulances	Literature review and professional experience	In Greece, there is no available common information system that provides the available vehicle resources. Only 2 different systems are available in different regions.
G.6.2-23	Differences in the level of E&T (Medical doctors, nurses/equivalent, paramedics, etc.)	Literature review and professional experience	At the EU level there is no standardization of procedures and there are two main concepts: European and Anglo-American.
G.6.2-24	Lack of national standards and criteria for certification of FARs in Greece	Professional experience	There is a lack of certification in the training of medical first responders.

Table 25 – Gaps from Education and training for first aid responses

Raising practitioner and social awareness			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G6.3-1	Lack of interoperability in communication tools	Professional experience	First responders communicate via various systems and channels. This leads to losing or interrupting information flow
G6.3-2	Hoaxes	Professional experience	Hoaxes are nowadays very popular and social media users often share/post unclear, changed or fake news

Raising practitioner and social awareness			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G6.3-3	Lack of understanding between agencies	Literature	The major misunderstanding is in terms of current roles and responsibility, including the understanding of each agency's capability and resource
G6.3-4	Alternative communication system	Literature	Destruction of infrastructure such a communication system is critical as well as the lack of coverage. During disaster such as MCI it is necessary to improve agency response, especially in terms of communication and reporting lines.
G6.3-5	Lack of public awareness	Literature	Low level of public awareness of the dangers, the possible consequences and readiness for adequate response in early warning and disaster disclosure. The development and implementation of Strategy for public awareness is needed.
G6.3-6	Communication language	Professional experience	Definition of the language in which the authority in charge must notify and inform the population when the MCI takes place in a cross-border region where two or more languages are spoken.
G6.3-7	Intentional misleading of first responders and civil protection service	Professional experience	Purposeful misleading and diverging of the servicemen – firefighters, rescue teams, civil protection and others.
G6.3-8	Lack of citizen engagement in Disasters and in risk reduction	Professional experience	Citizen engagement in Disasters and in risk reduction in a local-municipal level is not available

Table 26 – Gaps from Raising practitioner and social awareness

Civil-Military cooperation			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G6.4-1	Different scope of civil-military cooperation in EU countries.	Literature	In some countries, armed forces are only involved in major disasters and do not include the concept of civil-military cooperation in their security strategies.
G6.4-2	Lack of joint training, coaching and exercises	Literature	In some countries, the armed forces are not involved in disaster response planning and preparedness. There is no sharing of training activities or exercises to facilitate the integration of the institutions.

Civil-Military cooperation			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G6.4-3	No official exchange of information between civil and military first responders based on "confidentiality"	Professional experience	"Confidentiality" restrictions based on different legal basis the civil and military units operate.
G6.4-4	Lack of protocols for coordination between military and civil actors	Literature	In some countries there are no accepted protocols for joint actions of military and civil teams in cases of disasters
G6.4-5	Lack of programs and standards for first responders Joint Education and Training	Literature	In most countries there are no adopted programs for joint training on uniform scenarios, common standards and procedures for joint actions of military and civilian teams in cases of natural disasters
G6.4-6	Lack of clarity on preparing for and conducting disaster and emergency operations and response planning	Literature	In most countries there are no clear and relevant to modern conditions procedures and action plans
G6.4-7	Lack of social awareness of the military's involvement and usefulness in the civilian sphere.	Literature	A large part of society is not aware of how useful the military instrument can be in contributing to and assisting the civilian sphere. Not only in dealing with military conflicts of a more violent nature.
G6.4-8	Lack of political effort to include and develop the military as an instrument of assistance in emergency and civil protection situations	Literature	Normalizing the use of the military arm in politics to combat catastrophes, pandemics and natural disasters can be an important step towards the civilian sphere understanding its participation and normalizing processes.

Table 27 – Gaps from Civil-Military cooperation

Civil Protection and Aid Volunteerism			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G6.5-1	Variability in the mode and degree of cooperation between authorities and civil protection.	Literature	The variability between the mode and degree of cooperation is due to different normative bases, forms of organisation and levels of competence.
G6.5-2	No common approach in the post-disaster social and psychosocial support of victims as	Literature	Multi-casualty incidents may leave a mark both to the affected populations and first responders, who operate on the field and face stressful situations. Many volunteering organisations provide

Civil Protection and Aid Volunteerism			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
	well as first responders.		psychological support to both groups. There is a need for a standardised approach or a widely adopted guideline to this direction.
G6.5-3	No clear UCPM cooperation	Literature	Need to better understand the scenarios in which the UCPM could be activated and what level of response should be expected from the mechanism, as well as the need to develop adequate host country support structures and procedures to receive assistance from UCPM.
G6.5-4	Lack of training on intercultural competences and foreign language skills in organisations active in civil protection	Literature	First responders are increasingly confronted with situations that require intercultural competencies and foreign language skills, requiring multicultural teams to act jointly or in a complementary manner in relation to these requirements in disaster situations
G6.5-5	Insufficient coordination and coherence between national and EU policies	Literature	While the European disaster management framework is advanced at regional level, significant legislative preparation remains to be done at national level.
G6.5-6	Integration of volunteers within the response SOP	Literature	Volunteers play a vital role throughout the emergency cycle so it is necessary to create an appropriate and recognised organisational and operational framework for volunteering.
G6.5-7	Joint exercises between volunteers and national authorities	Literature	Emergency preparedness capacity needs to be strengthened with qualified staff and volunteers. To this end, it is important that exercises at national and European level include the participation of these volunteers.
G6.5-8	Insufficient legislation for volunteers	Literature	Volunteer based organisations must be protected legally and integrated in government actions.
G6.5-9	Protection of volunteers	Literature	Organisations might need to ensure volunteers privately, i.e., by procuring an all-in insurance
G6.5-10	No centralised "lessons learned database" for Civil Protection at European level	Literature	The dissemination of lessons learned after field exercises and real situations within Europe is limited.

Civil Protection and Aid Volunteerism			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G6.5-11	Different approach to professional, volunteer first responder teams and spontaneous volunteers	Professional experience	Extremely wide gaps in management, attitude to, ensuring of different types of first responders on the field and in the training and preparation.
G6.5-12	Volunteers are not regulated by the law	Professional experience and literature	In some EU countries the status of Volunteer first responders is not legally regulated
G6.5-13	Volunteers and unified training at National level	Professional experience	In Greece, volunteer training is carried out by the organization in which each volunteer is a member.
G6.5-14	International disaster management coordinating organizations must develop a unified/aligned structure for their members' training, processes, and operational procedures	Professional experience and literature review	Harmonically operating forces and mechanisms from various nations are missing from international disaster management coordinating organisations. As a result, a unified/ aligned structure of their members' training, processes, and operational procedures is required.

Table 28 – Gaps from Civil Protection and Aid Volunteerism

Sustainable International/European Certification and evaluation facilities - Equipment			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G3.5-1	Lack of information about dedicated standard and certification of the equipment/system for the FRs	Professional experience	Even in case of the existing equipment/system for the FRs, it is not easy to identify which laws, standards and certification this equipment/system are in compliance with
G3.5-2	Lack of laws, standards and certification for novel technology	Professional experience	Advanced technologies for the FRs have been actively developed. In case of novel technology (e.g., Unmanned Surface Vehicle, Unmanned Ground Vehicle, wearable, etc.), there is a lack of relevant laws and standards. Accordingly, certification is also lacking.
G3.5-3	Lack of information on relevant certification for the first response enablers	Professional experience	It is not clear whether specific certification is needed or not for the first response enablers

Sustainable International/European Certification and evaluation facilities - Equipment			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G3.5-4	Lack of harmonized certification scheme for the first response enablers	Professional experience	The UCPM provides the assessment tool for the certification, but it may not sufficiently cover the novel technologies
G3.5-5	Difficult to introduce the common certification scheme the first response enablers	Professional experience	The equipment/system for the FRs are quite diverse in technology, concept of operation, application area and performance, so it is difficult to identify common technical/functional requirements for the common certification scheme
G3.5-6	Challenges from complex systems for the first responders	Professional experience	The certification scheme needs to cover not only the product itself but also software, data protection and cybersecurity certification
G3.5-7	Necessity of new evaluation procedure and modifications on the evaluation facilities	Professional experience	As novel technologies have been introduced in the emergency response, new evaluation procedure and modifications on the evaluation facilities are necessary
G3.5-8	The accreditation for new evaluation facilities needs to be considered	Professional experience	If new evaluation facilities are introduced in the certification process, it needs to be accredited by the accreditation body
G3.5-9	Need to establish the technical and functional requirement for first response enablers	Professional experience	In the certification process, to define the requirements to be satisfied is important. Especially, to define necessary requirements should take precedence for novel technologies
G3.5-10	Lack of communication channel between stakeholders in certification process	Professional experience	There are several information sharing programs in UCPM, but there is not much information about the certification
G3.5-11	Difficulties to implement the data protection certification mechanism under article 42 GDPR	Professional experience	GDPR entered into application on May 25th 2018 but the concrete application of article 42 is still missing
G3.5-12	Complex technology training	Professional experience	Acquiring the necessary skills to mitigate new risks requires the use of advanced technology
G3.5-13	Cybersecurity recertification system may slow down upgrades	Literature	software providers may be reluctant to produce regular updates for their products/systems because of the time/cost of the recertification process

Sustainable International/European Certification and evaluation facilities - Equipment			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G3.5-14	The proposed Act on AI is focussed for high risk AI only	Literature	Medium and lower risk AI systems have only limited mandatory information duties.
G3.5-15	SAR not prepared to keep information registered	Professional experience	It necessary to recover all information from SAR after some malfunction or something similar
G3.5-16	Little cooperation and joint usage of test facilities	Professional experience	Test labs have their own facilities and operate as businesses, so there might be a lack of interest for joint usage and cooperation
G3.5-17	Lack of standardized cybersecurity criteria and best practices for certification		This may lead to inconsistencies in evaluating the security of emerging technologies, making it difficult to ensure a uniform level of cybersecurity
G3.5-18	Interoperability and integration security		Certification schemes should account for the security aspects of integrating emerging technologies with existing systems, ensuring that the integration doesn't introduce new vulnerabilities or compromise the security of connected systems
G3.5-19	Need a more thorough risk assessment		Traditional certification processes often focus on static assessments. In the context of cybersecurity, there's a gap in incorporating dynamic risk assessment to evaluate the technology's resilience to evolving threats.
G3.5-20	Responding to rapid Technological Advancements		The certification process needs to address the challenge of keeping up with the rapid advancements in technology, ensuring that new equipment and systems are evaluated against the latest standards

Table 29 – Gaps related to certification of technologies and equipment for emergency response

Sustainable International/European Certification and evaluation facilities - Operation			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G3.5-21	EU Drone regulations leaves it up to the national state to specify regulations for using drones in disaster response	EU legislation	Could create a problem in cross border situations if there are different national requirements

Sustainable International/European Certification and evaluation facilities - Operation			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G3.5-22	Required specific experience and expertise to operate unmanned system	Professional experience	A certification scheme that verifies the ability to operate complex unmanned systems is needed
G3.5-23	There is no certification for operating UAVs in UCPM	literature	UAVs have started to be actively used in the disaster situation, but a certification scheme has not been established yet
G3.5-24	Identification of new competencies	Professional experience	Development of new skills needed to respond to new risks
G3.5-25	Standardization operation procedures	Professional experience	SOPs Development to unify procedures
G3.5-26	Lack of common European certification for pre-hospital emergency medical personnel	Literature	Efficient cross-border cooperation requires medical staff with comparable knowledge and comparable services provided between countries, but their education varies drastically within European countries
G3.5-27	Training and Qualification		There's need for certification schemes and standards to ensure that FRs are adequately trained and qualified to operate capabilities effectively, especially in high-stress situations
G3.5-28	Budget Constraints		Each organization and agency involved in first aid response may have budget limitations, and may be in a different economic situation. This may cause potential gaps in compliance.
G3.5-29	Evolving Threats		As new threats and emergency situations emerge, there may be a challenge in adapting the certification criteria to address these evolving scenarios
G3.5-30	Cross-disciplinary Knowledge		Effective certification scheme of emerging technologies requires expertise from various disciplines, including technology, disaster management, ethics, and public safety. A gap may exist in bringing together these diverse knowledge area.

Sustainable International/European Certification and evaluation facilities - Operation			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G3.5-31	Long-term viability		Some emerging technologies may become obsolete quickly, while others could have long-term value. The certification scheme should address the balance between encouraging innovation and ensuring that certified technologies remain relevant over time
G3.5-32	Global consistency		Given that disasters can have international implications, achieving global consistency in certification/standard for emerging disaster management technologies can be challenging due to varying regulatory environments and cultural considerations.
G3.5-33	Human factors in cybersecurity		Some certification schemes might overlook the human factors in cybersecurity, including user training, secure development practices, and incident response readiness, all of which are crucial for a comprehensive security posture.
G3.5-34	Training and skill updates		The certification scheme should facilitate ongoing training and skill updates for first responders. Ensuring that certified responders stay current with best practices and the latest techniques is crucial for effective emergency response.
G3.5-35	Legal and liability considerations for certified FRs		Establishing clear guidelines on legal responsibilities, liabilities, and insurance aspects for certified first responders during emergency operations is essential to prevent legal hurdles in cross-border operations

Table 30 – Gaps related to certification of operation in emergency response

11. Annex D – Opportunities

This annex is a selection of the opportunities described in D4.6, D5.6, D6.6 and D3.10.

First responder vehicles and supportive autonomous units			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP-4.1-1a	G4.1-1a	Accurate and live weather data	There are developed UAV systems using quadro-copter technology with the necessary sensors to measure all possible weather data. They are robust enough to withstand freezing temperatures and high winds.
OP4.1-1b	G4.1-1b	Up to date information about terrain and infrastructure in the disaster areas	Aerial drones can be equipped with a variety of cameras from still photos to live video stream, both traditionally, low light and thermal images can be chosen. The drones come in a spectre of prices based on the quality of the technology from Go-pro technology with 1080 pixels up to 4k with 5000p. This gives an opportunity to make very detailed photos of the disaster area, with the possibility to zoom in on areas of interest.
OP4.1-2a	G4.1-2a	Tracking of personnel, equipment, and casualties	A common problem in all disaster area operations is tracking of personnel. By using a blockchain based tag system on emergency response personnel and vehicles the command centre can have live updated information of where they are physically.
OP4.1-2b	G4.1-2b	Safe work environment for first responder personnel	In all disaster relief operations, especially in urban areas, the present of hazardous or toxic material is highly possible. To protect the personnel involved with the right protective gear and to decide the best approach to the task, it is vital to know what type of substances may be present or what the smoke from the fire contains the present of toxicity or hazardous gases or material.
OP4.1-3a	G4.1-3a	Build ad hoc communication grids	In large disasters the probability that the existing communication grids may be destroyed or overloaded. To make a temporary grid is paramount to secure the transfer of datafiles and the ability to access different databases. Drones can provide relay nodes in a grid and UGVs and USV can be base stations and battery charges.
OP4.1-3b	G4.1-3b	Distribution of equipment.	In all disaster relief operation, the first responders will need different type of equipment. A lot of it, like bandages and medication, may be in continuous demand from the first responders. To get equipment

First responder vehicles and supportive autonomous units			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
			from the storage areas and out to the first responder teams is logistically demanding.
OP4.1-3c	G4.1-3c	Supply energy and charging capabilities	Relatively small UAV's, USV's and UGV's has a short operation time, typically 30 to 60 minutes, and a limited speed. It is often crucial that charging facilities can be moved close to the operation area. These "mother" vehicles can either be ground or water based and also act as a communication centre.
OP4.1-4	G4.1-4	Conduct search and relief missions	Unmanned systems have a potential to give first relief to casualties found by surveillance drones or by tracking of mobile phones the system can deliver lifesaving equipment to the persons in need or by someone nearby with the possibilities to assists.

Table 31 – Opportunities from First responder vehicles and supportive autonomous units

Trusted communication infrastructure and end-user terminals			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP-4.2-1	G4.2-2 G4.2-8 G4.2-34	Use of alternative communication systems	First responder agencies could use alternative communication systems in case of a system or network failure.
OP4.2-2	G4.2-1 G4.2-27	Extend network coverage	The different countries could improve the network coverage of the most used communication technologies to improve current coverage limitations.
OP4.2-3	G4.2-2	Use of technologies that allow the adaptability of the network architecture	The VALKYRIES project identifies the adaptability of network technologies in the face of environmental adversities, with communications being fundamental to the transmission of critical data.
OP4.2-4	G4.2-3	Use of technologies that favour the extension of coverage to devices with fewer resources	The use of technologies that create wide coverage ranges favours the connection and, therefore, the transmissions of constrained devices.
OP4.2-5	G4.2-3	Use of mobile technologies to facilitate service delivery	Due to environmental adversities, the use of miniaturized cell phone technology, commonly known as decode-and-forward relays, can extend the coverage of mobile services to include hard-to-reach areas. This approach enables transmissions to large crowds, such as in relief camp settings, hard-to-reach urban areas, or rural locations where ground transportation has been disrupted.

Trusted communication infrastructure and end-user terminals			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP4.2-6	G4.2-3	Use of UAVs for coverage extension in areas of difficult access or poor coverage	Emergency areas may be in poor coverage or difficult to access locations, the use of devices that can extend existing coverage is critical to the interoperability of VALKYRIES.
OP4.2-7	G4.2-3	Use of balloons to create communication routes in rural or poor coverage areas	Sometimes emergencies occur in remote locations or where a robust communications architecture does not exist, therefore, deploying devices that meet the needs of a fixed network architecture is necessary.
OP4.2-8	G4.2-4	Selection of technologies based on the type of data to be transmitted	The selection of technologies must be made depending on the type of data to be transmitted, being critical the relevant and indispensable information for the emergency.
OP4.2-9	G4.2-5	Creation of communication preference mechanisms in the networks available during the emergency	It is necessary to ensure that data transmissions over the communications networks are preferential to favour the exchange of data to devices operated by first responders and not by other entities (e.g., curious citizens, nearby personal vehicles, commercial radio stations, etc.).
OP4.2-10	G4.2-6	Unified regulations for data protection in emergency scenarios	There is an opportunity for a homogenised regulation regarding securitization of communications in emergency scenarios at EU level.
OP4.2-11	G4.2-7	Use of monitoring technologies or services capable of detecting threats that may affect the network	There is an opportunity for substantial improvement in network security by using active and passive monitoring systems capable of detecting threats to assets in real time.
OP4.2-12	G4.2-8	Improve intercommunication between technologies	There is room for standardisation work regarding interconnection of different technologies to allow changing easily between technologies.
OP4.2-13	G4.2-9	Use of technologies based on security constraints	EU regulations could focus on providing clear guidelines regarding which technologies or protocols are more suitable according to data security constraints in each scenario.
OP4.2-14	G4.2-10	Definition of backup guidelines at EU level	There is an opportunity for defining and implanting strict backup regulations enforcing emergency institutions to store sensitive data with redundancy to avoid information loss.

Trusted communication infrastructure and end-user terminals			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP4.2-15	G4.2-11	Creation of data restoration contingency plans	The EU could design and implement recommendations or guidelines on how to proceed for data restoration in case of incidents.
OP4.2-16	G4.2-12	Deployment of redundant services to provide back-up support in case of failure	The EU could provide recommendations for the deployment of auxiliary systems in multiple casualty scenarios.
OP4.2-17	G4.2-13 G4.2-16	Developing national ad hoc emergency networks	The creation of ad hoc national networks for emergency services (e.g., in Portugal, Ireland or Denmark) would help to ensure interoperability between the different emergency services.
OP4.2-18	G4.2-17	Leveraging 5G networks	The 5G network could provide an affordable, stable, and low-latency communications solution for autonomous and teleoperated vehicles and human intervention teams. In addition, functionalities such as Network Slicing could guarantee quality of service in crowded environments and ensure the confidentiality of a particularly critical network.
OP4.2-19	G4.2-24	Extend IOT data range	Long range local data gathering using Lora Network.
OP4.2-20	G4.2-25	Victims and FR data gathering	Wearable's sensors can collect victims and FR health data via Bluetooth and transmit them the network.
OP4.2-21	G4.2-26	Bridge between networks	To enable a wider network coverage, and overcome networks differences between entities, a gateway/bridge approach can be used to interconnect different networks and jointly cover a wider area.
OP4.2-22	G4.2-27	Increase RF area coverage	Use of drones with communications relay payload to increase the coverage of the FR communications.
OP4.2-23	G4.2-28 G4.2-29 G4.2-31	GATEWAY	To establish the connectivity bridge between different networks and translate from one network protocol to another network.
OP4.2-24	G4.2-32	IP LAYER	Establish IP layer as the reference network protocol for all the entities and communication that want to share data, within SIGRUN, to communication at IP level.
OP4.2-25	G4.2-30	Data Priority	Use gateways functions to implement the data priority established by the Command

Trusted communication infrastructure and end-user terminals			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
			Centre, by using SLA and QoS, to ensure data transfer end-to-end based on the data prioritization.
OP4.2-26	G4.2-33	Data Conversion	APIs used by the SIGRUN, and the GATEWAYS provide the function to convert data formats, taxonomy, language, etc., between the application to the SIGRUN reference established or other agreed by the entities.
OP4.2-27	G4.2-34	Communications redundancy	Establish a redundant communications solution by integrating different networks and communication solutions into a common communications framework and architecture that enables bridging and multiple paths between different networks.
OP4.2-28	G4.2-34	GATEWAYS networks	By having gateways between different networks increases the redundancy by adding alternative so the communications.
OP4.2-29	G4.2-35	Data cluster	Data servers aggregated in clusters enables a higher redundancy, increase SLA and QoS performance and higher services availability.
OP4.2-30	G4.2-35	Data cluster	To improve the data redundancy, it should be data backup capability.
OP4.2-31	G4.2-36	APPS/Functions redundancy	An application agnostic federated system with the data status distributed enables a system function redundancy, in case of a function unavailable, other application can be deployed.
OP4.2-32	G4.2-37	Block Chain redundancy	Use the Blockchain networks to store shared metadata and transactional data.
OP4.2-33	G4.2-35	Data backup	Use of backup servers for the non-transaction and streaming data to add additional non-real time redundancy capability.
OP.4.2-34	G4.2-38	Shared Health data	Explore the potential use of EHR to exchange data between medial services.
OP4.2-35	G4.2-39	Querying data	Use of MQTT protocol to integrate data sources and data gathering within the SIGRUN sources.
OP4.2-36	G4.2-14 G4.2-15	Light cryptographic protocols	The use of light cryptographic protocols reduces the computing time and computing requirements.
OP4.2-37	G4.2-14 G4.2-15	RBAC/ABAC	The use or RBAC will atomize the data access which will allow to optimal control.
OP4.2-38	G4.2-20	Sectorisation	Division or sectorisation of incoming information.

Trusted communication infrastructure and end-user terminals			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP4.2-39	G4.2-21	Access limitation	Limit network access and type of communication to a certain group of subscribers.
OP4.2-40	G4.2-22	Specific terminals for disasters	Either purchase or program existing terminals for unattended and simple use.
OP4.2-41	G4.2-19	Standard training in device use	Implementation of training standards and use of devices.
OP4.2-42	G4.2-23	Standard capabilities of emergency devices	Implementation of device technical requirements standards.

Table 32 – Opportunities from Trusted communication infrastructure and end-user terminals

Mobile command and control and operational coordination technologies			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP-4.3-1	G4.3-1 G4.3-2 G4.3-28	VR debriefing systems	Backing to Virtual Reality systems for FRs may be implemented to C2. Items likely training performance or training outputs might be improved the results. <i>Technological</i>
OP-4.3-2	G4.3-3	Multiplatform. Run different OS	Interlinking applications. Note is a basic characteristic to standardise. <i>Technological</i>
OP-4.3-3	G4.3-11 G4.3-24	Location of near/nearest vehicles	Not enough traceability of vehicles location from other organizations. Which technology could fulfil this opportunity? <i>Technological</i>
OP-4.3-4	G4.3-11	Georeferenced recording of events on the ground	Know-how disaster events. Monitor the location of the events and display by C2 application. Chance to track events in terms of geo-referencing. <i>Technological</i>
OP-4.3-5	G4.3-7	COP standardization	Provide a global and real-time overview of the environmental situation and resources in the field.
OP-4.3-6	G4.3-11 G4.3-35 G4.3-36	HUMS (Health and Usage Monitoring Systems) or simulators for boosting forces	Opportunity to have a constantly metrics of your vehicle, device or system. <i>Cross-border and Technological</i>
OP-4.3-7	G4.3-3 G4.3-45	Asset's responsiveness and being able to adapt to fast-changing environments, mission needs and scenarios	Deploying emergency items in VUCA environments (volatility, uncertainty, complexity, and ambiguity). <i>Cross-border, Technological and Procedural</i>

Mobile command and control and operational coordination technologies			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP-4.3-8	G4.3-2	Detecting trends and achieving maximum operative readiness	AI capable of performing tasks commonly associated with human intelligence.
OP-4.3-9	G4.3-32	Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms	Predicting trends from previous exercises. Collecting and processing data to improve decision support.
OP-4.3-10	G4.3-32 G4.3-40	Social Network data visualization C2	Recap data from social network such as pictures, videos or current states in order to increase decision-making and have a better understanding of the global situation. <i>Technological</i>
OP-4.3-11	G4.3-28	Open Source C2 App	Providing technologies to the most vulnerable and under-resourced societies. <i>Technological</i>
OP-4.3-12	G4.3-31	Satellite weather data recorded in Hybrid Digital Twins as a layer	As weather prediction services use different standards and methodologies, this could be a critical gap in cross-border incidents effecting many parameters in decision making or logistics deployment. Recording such data, through available APIs, from ESA and/or NASA and/or ARATOS satellite systems, can resolve the gap through COP exchange between agents and countries by sharing the Hybrid Digital Twins recorded data.
OP-4.3-13	G4.3-7	Common Operational Picture exchange	As different agents within a country usually operate their own C2 systems, COP within a country using the VALKYRIES system and standards can be defined as ai recording in the Hybrid Digital Twins of the VALKYRIES Core System. Then the COP exchange between countries (parametrized on permissions/restrictions as per bilateral agreements) can be easily performed.
OP-4.3-14	G4.3-32	Guidelines for social media crawling	EU members could elaborate recommendations for implementing social media crawling strategies.
OP-4.3-15	G4.3-32 G4.3-33 G4.3-40	Guidelines for selecting social media crawling tools	EU members could develop guidelines indicating the best tools and technologies used for social media data acquisition according to the type of platform consulted.
OP-4.3-16	G4.3-19	Drones' imagery data	Explore of multiple deployed drones in the field theatre to collect aerial view data (from EO/IR/ Lidar sensors) and increase the covered area, in particular for wide areas events.

Mobile command and control and operational coordination technologies			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP-4.3-17	G4.3-18 G4.3-19 G4.3-22	Obtain high ground resolution data	Combine multiple data to improve the coverage and details of the in-field situation: 1) Drones imagery high resolution sensors and its flight level; 2) ground data sensors, from IOT deployable sensors of external IOT services; 3) In field imagery from FR and victims Smartphones.
OP-4.3-18	G4.3-21 G4.3-22	Airspace coordination with drones	New capability is required to manage the increasing number of flying elements in cases of Emergency / Disaster event, this can be used by new solution or integration with external services.
OPx.3-19	G4.3-21 G4.3-38	RF space management	Add new capabilities to manage the RF spectrum as the number of communication infrastructures and radios is used with deployable sensors (Ground/ Air / Mobile /etc.).
OP-4.3-20	G4.3-34	Cross border data trace	Data shared between countries could be traced by establishing a countries agreement reference, as a sharing authorization schema, for which the data is validated prior to be shared, and enables trace of the that data.
OP-4.3-21	G4.3-35	Victims advance information	Only the data from victims assigned to a response medical facility is shared, from the moment it is assigned and including during transportation.
OP-4.3-22	G4.3-36	Victims' historical data	The historical data collected during the event should be shared to the medical facility assigned to provide the medical service, including the information enabling its access to the victim EDR.
OP-4.3-22	G4.3-41 G4.3-42	Traceability of victims and FR	Use of wearables and other portable sensors combined with communication capabilities to enable the C2 and medical services to locate and trace the FR and victims. Each data to the specific needs.
OP-4.3-22	G4.3-39	External data	Specify API protocols and standard to enables external services to interface/share data with the SIGRUN
OP-4.3-23	G4.3-43	Guidelines for identifying dangerous zones	EU members could elaborate regulations and guidelines to harmonise the procedures of identifying dangerous zones.
OP-4.3-24	G4.3-44	Identification of relevant locations	EU members could define recommended technologies for the identification of relevant locations in emergency scenarios.
OP-4.3-25	G4.3-45	Use of decision-making applications	Implementation of decision support applications in emergency services.

Mobile command and control and operational coordination technologies			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP-4.3-26	G4.3-46	Creation of operating procedures	Create operating procedures that collect the requirements of the standards used in equipment and devices.
OP-4.3-27	G4.3-46 G4.3-47	Incorporation of new standards	Create procedures to adapt equipment, devices, and infrastructures to the appearance of new standards.

Table 33 – Opportunities from Mobile command and control and operational coordination technologies

The digitalization on first aid actuations			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP4.4-1	G4.4-10	Digital Skills Improvement	To improve the digital skills of the first responder.
OP4.4-2	G4.4-2	Wearable's implementation	As it is expected to track information using smart instrumentation and wearables, it poses as a great opportunity to include their information in the digital environment.
OP4.4-3	G4.4-1 G4.4-2	European Iconographic Standardization	There is an opportunity to create an iconographic standard that accomplish with the desired requirements and avoid discrepancies.
OP4.4-4	G4.4-3 G4.4-4	European data standardization	To define a common standard for communications would ease the information sharing during emergencies and the connection with digitalization instances.
OP4.4-5	G4.4-5	Device's upgrade	To assure that the devices involved during first aid actuations accomplish with the required computational and graphical requirements, they should be evaluated and upgraded.
OP4.4-13	G4.4-13	Use of AI-based systems	It is possible to use AI-based systems for decision making or other considerations.
OP4.4-14	G4.4-11	Reduce voice communication	Digitization of first responders' actions will reduce reliance on voice communications.
OP4.4-15	G4.4-12	Reduce digital workload	Automating as many information flows as possible.
OP4.4-16	G4.4-8 G4.4-9	Placing FR as an important focus on the design of solutions	Taking first responders into consideration in the design of solutions for operational and C2 support in MCI and disasters is necessary to ensure that it provides them with the support they need with adequate usability, facilitating their tasks and not hindering them, and with reliability in real working conditions.

Table 34 – Opportunities from The digitalization on first aid actuations

Instrumentation and health support wearable devices			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP4.5-1	G4.5-1	Use of wearables for tracking	It is possible to employ wearables that incorporate technologies such as RFID or NFC to track the stage of the incident each user is in.
OP4.5-2	G4.5-1	Use of wearables for tracking	Use of wearables incorporating GPS technology to track the location of each user in an emergency scenario.
OP4.5-3	G4.5-1	Use of wireless technologies in wearables	It is possible to use wearables that incorporate GPS technology for real-time location of the users' position and thus associate them to a certain position/phase.
OP4.5-4	G4.5-2	Use of RFID-based wearables for identification	Through the use of RFID devices, it is possible to assign a unique identifier that allows users to be uniquely identified within an emergency scenario.
OP4.5-5	G4.5-2	NFC printing on traditional cards for identification	It is possible to print NFC tags on top of traditional cards to avoid a collapse due to lack of coverage.
OP4.5-6	G4.5-3	Prototyping with own technologies	It is possible to create a prototype of wearable devices that incorporates those modules to enable the necessary technologies to meet the needs raised.
OP4.5-7	G4.5-3	Firmware prototyping	It is possible to design firmware that incorporates a prototype to meet the needs that are required in such scenarios.
OP4.5-8	G4.5-4	Adaptive data delivery	To save battery power, data sending can be adapted depending on the patient's situation, sending data more continuously or in a reduced form.
OP4.5-9	G4.5-5	RFID to avoid batteries	RFID-based devices avoid the use of batteries in these devices and therefore the limitation of the lifetime.
OP4.5-10	G4.5-11 G4.5-13	Communicate by voice	It would be possible to implement the functionality of wearables that do not have them with a microphone and a speaker to allow local communication between FRs.
OP4.5-11	G4.5-17	Communication by text	Wearables that have screens could transmit and receive text messages to and from C2.
OP4.5-12	G4.5-11	Warning of a danger for FRs	There are integrations in some wearables that allow you to report a personal physical threat via an easy action (panic button) or detection of lying position and lack of movement. This information is correlated by the GPS coordinates of the RF and also the opening of an ambient microphone. The use of these solutions should be more widespread.

Instrumentation and health support wearable devices			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
			In addition to this it could be interesting to be able to report via the wearable the localization of different dangers (fire, smoke, collapse) that identify NO-GO zones to report them to FRs approaching that zone.
OP4.5-13	G4.5-1 G4.5-25 G4.5-26	Automatic transmission of vital signs of FRs	It would be possible to transmit to C2 automatically (continuously, at defined intervals, on request) vital signals of the FRs detected by the wearables. For example, heart rate, oxygen saturation, but also lack of movement could be detected.
OP4.5-14	G4.5-14	Integration of sensors for hazardous substances	The possibility of integrating sensors for various hazardous substances within wearables (e.g., helmets) would allow continuous monitoring of dangers. The possibility of transmitting this information, correlated for example by the GPS coordinates, to C2 would make it immediately available to all FRs in the area, triggering an alarm when they approach danger.
OP4.5-15	G4.5-13	Broadcasting of safety and security information	Ability to transmit information on the safety and security of FRs through wearables. Preceded by a pre-established warning signal, they can be short text or audio messages or, in the case of devices with larger screens, contain images relating to the location of the danger.
OP4.5-16	G4.5-15	Create common procedures for disaster fatality identification between different countries	Sharing certain information about deceased victims obtained through wearables can provide a common basis for the harmonization of DVI procedures among different countries. The more accurate and verified the identification, the easier it will be to agree on a shared regulation. This solution may be difficult to implement due to political problems.
OP4.5-17	G4.5-14	Freezing the scene of a deceased victim discovery	The ability to capture via a wearable device (body cam, smart glasses) images and the exact location of a scene before recovering a deceased victim would provide authorities responsible for identifying the victim with valuable information. This data could be securely transmitted and stored.

Instrumentation and health support wearable devices			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP4.5-18	G4.5-18	Acquire unique IDs of implanted wearables	The ability to “read” an implantable wearable and correlate its ID with a person’s medical record would allow a person to be identified with certainty and quickly.
OP4.5-19	G4.5-14	Record victim’s data in blockchain	The ability to log data in blockchain will be provided by the VALKYRIES’ system for all crucial transactions and metadata. This can also cover the recording of all medical data gathered in different stages of triage or handling of the victim between different agents, up to the entry of the victim to the final hospital to take care.
OP4.5-20	G4.5-10 G4.5-20	Use of first responder’s telecom devices to record victim’s data as per its wearable unique id	In case we use the combination of NFT wearables and blockchain, then the communication to the appropriate C2 or supporting federated software can be performed using the communication capabilities of the smart phone/tablet of the first responder initiating/updating or retrieving information on a trusted “need to know” basis.
OP4.5-21	G4.5-25 G4.5-26	Collect victim’s vital signs	Use of smart wearables, devices, and smartphones to collect in near real-time victim’s vital signs, possibly including, but not limited to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Heart rate ○ Body Temperature ○ Oxygen levels and saturation ○ Abrupt movements ○ Blood pressure
OP4.5-22	G4.5-26	Monitor patient vital signs	The vital signs collected can be transmitted to the medical centre that records the vital signs history and generated a victim’s dashboard, monitoring the key values of the patient signals and raise alerts.
OP4.5-23	G4.5-22	Mask victims ID from victim’s signs	For purpose of privacy protection, the identification data of the victims and the victims’ vital signs could be masked with alias. Only the identification service would be able to cross this information by authorization of the victims.
OP4.5-24	G4.5-20	Patient vital signs available to medical service	The victim current and historic vital signs data are shared with the assigned medical service for treatment.
OP4.5-25	G4.5-17 G4.5-22	Victim’s vital signs on route	While on route, the ambulances carrying the victims are equipped with the means to, either directly collect the victim’s vital signs

Instrumentation and health support wearable devices			
ID	GAP ID	Opportunity name	Justification
			or to recover that data from the victim's sensors artifacts (wearables, smart devices, etc.), and send them to the medical service of destination.
OP4.5-26	G4.5-18	Victim ID	Use of pre-tagged RF, WR code, and marked colour to mark a victim. Registration of the victim with personal data can be done by FR. Victim's signals are mask with the TAG, not with the victim's name or ID.
OP4.5-27	G4.5-23	Telemedicine service	A telemedicine service can be set-up to provide assistance to responders aiding a victim.
OP4.5-28	G4.5-23	Telemedicine guidance	Telemedicine can provide audio assistance to responders to 1) guide them in applying lifesaving procedures and, 2) help performing assessment of the victim's health condition and basic diagnostics.
OP4.5-29	G4.5-23	Telemedicine data collection	The telemedicine service can receive imagery from the victims and use of remote experts to confirm/help achieve a diagnostic.
OP4.5-30	G4.5-22	European Health Data Space	EU Proposal to expand the use of electronic health data to deliver health care to the individual from whom those data were collected ("primary use") and to improve research, innovation, policy making, patient safety, personalised medicine, official statistics or regulatory activities ("secondary use").
OP4.5-31	G4.5-25	Use of wearables on critically ill patients	The use of wearables in critically ill patients should be analysed in more detail.
OP4.5-32	G4.5-26 G4.5-27	Establish an international standard for wearable functionalities	To ensure the reliability of the measurements provided by wearables. All wearable manufacturers should manufacture according to an international standard.
OP4.5-33	G4.5-27 G4.5-29	Manufacturing wearables according to medical regulations	Implementing medical regulations in wearables, these devices would be more useful for first responders.
OP4.5-34	G4.5-18 G4.5-25 G4.5-28	Providing first responders with wearables	It would allow the physical and mental condition of first responders to be monitored and taking decisions
OP4.5-35	G4.5-7 G4.5-18 G4.5-25	Implementing the use of wearables among FR	Ensure that the physical and mental conditions of first responders are correct.

Table 35 – Opportunities from Instrumentation and health support wearable devices

Crisis response planning		
ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP5.1.1-1	Regulatory harmonisation	In order to promote the establishment of unified cross-border response plans and procedures, EU countries should seek to develop legislation to harmonise them.
OP5.1.1-2	Standardisation of terms and symbols for a common understanding of the situation	In multi casualty incidents, in which the coordination and collaboration of different first responders' agencies are required, it is crucial that data and information exchanged through the various systems should be interpreted in the same way by first responders. Apart from semantics that are used in systems, it is essential for FRs among the EU Member States to adopt a common terminology and symbology. This could lead to better collaborations and to the accomplishment of a common operational picture and situational awareness. Moreover, common signals and symbols could be used in social media for early warning.
OP5.1.1-3	Adequate revision and updating of emergency plans.	Developing, updating, revising and publishing crisis management plans on regular basis. This should be stated in the specific law.
OP5.1.1-4	Adequate dissemination and training in relation to emergency plans.	Good emergency planning is not effective if it is not accompanied by an adequate dissemination plan that includes the potentially affected population and training for all those involved in the response.
OP5.1.1-5	Facilitating EU's Civil Protection Guidelines through a common federated system	A federated system could facilitate harmonization towards acceptance, preparation and activation of EU's Civil Protection Guidelines.
OP5.1.1-6	Facilitating harmonisation through a common federated system	Leave the operational procedures and the supported role definitions "as it is" and tuned in different federated systems linked into SIGRUN and allow their evolution/adaptation towards an optimum harmonization from "lesson learning" following their practice in cross-border incidents as the core of such change management. Common role definitions and workflows will be included only for the support of the Core of SIGRUN system.
OP5.1.1-7	C2 activation through a common federated system / COP	Signalling of the need to activate C2 through the COP exchange/sharing of the Valkyries / SIGRUN system

Table 36 – Opportunities from Crisis response planning

Reconnaissance and triage		
ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP5.1.2-1	Harmonisation of emergency services structure	Greater homogeneity in the structure and composition of the emergency services would favour greater homogeneity in the organisation of the chain of command and operational procedures. Given that this goal is almost impossible, harmonisation between the commanders of the emergency services working together would be the priority.
OP5.1.2-2	Homogenisation of professional competencies in emergencies	It would be desirable to move towards homogenisation of training and competencies for emergency services professionals at EU level.
OP5.1.2-3	Integrated pre-hospital and hospital MCI plans and operational procedures.	Legislation to encourage the development and integration of joint EMS-hospital MCI response plans, with EMS and hospitals taking a more proactive role to maximise the effectiveness of the response.
OP5.1.2-4	Standardisation of terminology and criteria.	Standardisation of terminology and harmonisation of criteria for zoning in MCI response would make it easier for different agencies or regions to work together.
OP5.1.2-5	Standardisation of the information to be exchanged between disaster managers in the EU.	Standardisation of the basic information to be collected in relation to each victim is fundamental to guarantee traceability and continuity of care for those affected in a disaster, even more so in cross-border disasters. Of great interest is the use of reliable mobile applications that, while guiding the first responder in their work, allow for easy recording and sharing of relevant victim information.
OP5.1.2-6	Standardisation of means of triage tagging in MCI.	Use "clever" coloured wristbands (equipped with electronic readable id) in first triage/victim identification, log the data in secured blockchain structure and allow other rescuers handling the victim to record more data, prior to the handling of the victim in a hospital.
OP5.1.2-7	Standardisation of triage procedures in MCI.	Standardisation in the triage, coding and tagging of disaster victims is essential to ensure traceability and continuity of care for those affected, especially in disasters where different agencies or countries have to work together. In the simplest or most difficult conditions, standardising the triage priority codes, the tagging and the victim information recording (e.g., via a standardised triage tag, via a mobile application or via a wearable) has proven to be a simple way to support the interoperability of first responders.

Reconnaissance and triage		
ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP5.1.2-8	Establishment of consensus and recommendations	Professional and scientific societies competent in emergency medicine in the EU should issue consensus and recommendations on triage, on-scene care and evacuation of victims in an MCI or disaster situation, thereby promoting quality standards in line with current scientific evidence.
OP5.1.2-9	Facilitating harmonisation through a common federated system	Leave the operational procedures "as it is" and tuned in different federated systems linked into SIGRUN and allow their evolution/adaptation towards an optimum harmonization from "lesson learning" following their practice in cross-border incidents as the core of such change management.
OP5.1.2-10	Improving real-time victims' clinical information	Accessing to different parameters could help in choosing the patient's destination
OP5.1.2-11	Improving vehicles tracking	Acquire the arrival and set which is the entry point, the person who detects it, transmitting information to SIGRUN to facilitate its management and use
OP5.1.2-12	Improving the first responders training	Approach studies of first responders by integrating lessons learned from past disasters.
OP5.1.2-13	Standardization of first responders training and certification in Europe	First responders (EMS, FRS) should have standardised common training and knowledge in order to have a quality level of rescue.
OP5.1.2-14	Debriefing and evaluation standardization in MCI and disasters	Debriefings after each incident, drill, operation are essential. Debriefings shall be well structured and should describe each operation which was made during intervention, because many issues raise only after the operation. Step-by-step approach and clear identification of the roles of first responders. IRS and First responders (EMS, FRS, Police...) should use a common debriefing and evaluation after the intervention. Common trainings for First responders - practice cooperation and make procedures more efficient. It is necessary to set processes, responsibilities of each First responder and uniform evaluation.

Table 37 – Opportunities from Reconnaissance and triage

Communications maintenance, logistics and deployment		
ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP5.2.1-1	Improving communications	Real-time sharing of acquired information necessary
OP5.2.1-2	Technological updating of emergency services	Updating the ICT resources used by the emergency services would greatly simplify current operational procedures, make them more efficient, and improve interoperability between agencies and territories.
OP5.2.1-3	Technological updating of emergency services	Upgrading the ICT resources used by emergency services transferring information by digital data or another communication system would simplify communication procedures, make them more efficient by fostering the development of a common situational awareness, and improve interoperability between agencies and territories.
OP5.2.1-4	ICT technological updating of emergency services	Upgrading the ICT assets used by the emergency services would reduce the use of alternative communications resources outside common channels, thus promoting the development of appropriate common situational awareness.
OP5.2.1-5	Improving portability	Interoperability could be achieved if systems could interface using formatted messages, e-mail, or import/export functions
OP5.2.1-6	Technological e-health updating of emergency services	Upgrading the ICT resources used by the emergency services would increase the diagnostic and therapeutic capabilities of the first medical responders on the scene.
OP5.2.1-7	Simple and usable solutions that make the first responder's job easier.	Digitalisation solutions for EMS intervention in MCI and disasters must also address as an important objective the recording of automatic or sensor-based data and in general the simplification of the work of first responders in these situations, which are even more demanding and stressful than usual.

Table 38 – Opportunities from Communications maintenance, logistics and deployment

Others maintenance, logistics and deployment		
ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP5.2.2-1	Establish cross-border operational plans and procedures.	In addition to the development of cross-border collaborative plans, EU countries should seek the development of unified procedures among the services involved regarding the planning and logistical response to an MCI or disaster affecting several countries.

Others maintenance, logistics and deployment		
ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP5.2.2-2	Homogenisation of logistical resources in disaster response.	Standardisation in deployment support elements, such as communications and logistics vehicles, signalling elements, triage tags, PPE or facilities to establish an advanced medical post, would favour logistical interoperability between agencies and territories in MCI or disaster response.
OP5.2.2-3	Establishment of consensus and recommendations	Professional societies competent in emergency response in the EU should issue consensus and recommendations regarding the planning and logistical response of emergency services to an MCI or disaster.
OP5.2.2-4	Improve national disaster planning and response logistics tools.	Progress needs to be made in the use of technological tools and national information systems to ensure that logistical preparedness and response to national and cross-border incidents is effective.
OP5.2.2-5	Strengthen logistics expertise	It is advisable to develop specialised formal education, homogenised across EU countries, to provide logistics training for emergency services professionals involved in these aspects of disaster response.

Table 39 – Opportunities from *Others maintenance, logistics and deployment*

Command and control and support to operational decision-making		
ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP5.3-1	Harmonisation of emergency services command competencies among the different EU countries.	It would be desirable to move towards homogenisation in the distribution of competencies between emergency services within the EU. In the meantime, it is necessary to favour the highest degree of harmonisation to facilitate interoperability between disaster management mechanisms in different countries.
OP5.3-2	C2 self-adaptive network environment	Resilient and self-adaptive network environment due to high complexity response of the task.
OP5.3-3	Integration of all emergency services into a single emergency operations centre.	In order to ensure unity of action in the C2 of the emergency, it is necessary that all services involved in the response can be integrated into a single emergency operations centre.
OP5.3-4	Municipality supportive agents' engagement	Use the same track and trace technologies and devise to municipalities' assets in order to track their availability and status in COP

Command and control and support to operational decision-making		
ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP5.3-5	Define criteria for C2 facilities location	Establish criteria for the location of CEOC, Incident Command Post ICP and the Advanced Medical Post AMP, based on the communications coverage and scope of the incident.
OP5.3-6	Harmonization of procedures	Harmonisation of operational competencies and procedures, determination of the minimum dataset and establishment of basic interoperability standards.
OP5.3-7	Harmonisation of the emergency command and control system between EU countries.	Definition of an EU harmonised Control and Command System (C2S) framework adapted to the breadth of the territory and the severity of the new challenges.
OP5.3-8	Simplify information flow	Simplify the information exchange process. Fewer steps, fewer errors.
OP5.3-9	Standardisation of the information to be exchanged between disaster managers in the EU.	Standardisation of the information to be exchanged between disaster managers in the EU could facilitate the definition of joint workflows between C2 systems and the design of specific training programmes.
OP5.3-10	Technological updating of emergency services	Identify systems that do not allow for the integration of needs for emergency services. Propose an action plan for the purchase of new equipment.
OP5.3-11	Facilitating C2 interoperability through a common federated system	To be able to share information between systems in a supranational environment.
OP5.3-12	Improving communications	Communications improvements in terms of data sharing. Real-time is a must for MCI.
OP5.3-13	Blockchain "logbooks"	Log all messages metadata and transactions from federated systems in blockchain "logbooks"
OP5.3-14	Facilitating synchronisation through a common federated system	Log all messages metadata and transactions from federated systems in blockchain "logbooks" synchronizing the clocks of the federated systems with a central one provided by SIGRUN

Command and control and support to operational decision-making		
ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP5.3-15	Facilitating research through a common federated system	The recording of data, in addition to assisting in the real-time management of the emergency, provides a posteriori data that describe in detail the sequence of events in a real incident, allowing an objective analysis and thus the evaluation of procedures, the identification of areas for improvement, greater knowledge of the behaviour of these disasters, etc.
OP5.3-16	Hybrid Digital Twins as a C2 tool	Map all digitized data into Hybrid Digital Twins of SIGRUN system and transfer a copy to all involved C2s (within a country or between countries) following permission criteria

Table 40 – Opportunities from Command and control and support to operational decision-making

Common Operational Picture		
ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP5.4.1-1	Regulatory harmonisation	To encourage interoperability between cross-border C2. Information exchange technologies and platforms, EU countries should seek to develop legislation to encourage harmonisation.
OP5.4.1-2	Fostering a culture of information exchange	It is necessary to work on the individual, organisational and political culture to foster an attitude committed to the need to share all relevant information that allows for maintaining adequate situational awareness in disaster response. A culture of information sharing between institutions would facilitate the exchange of research results, organisational learning, and adaptation and improvisation.
OP5.4.1-3	Taking volunteers into account	COP of the available data from the volunteers in a common system for the effective utilization of the volunteer human resources.
OP5.4.1-4	Standardisation of information to be exchanged between disaster managers in the EU.	Standardisation of the basic information to be exchanged between disaster managers is essential for the interoperability of emergency services and decision support systems. There is a need to improve C2 communication at inter-agency, cross-sectoral and cross-border levels. Harmonisation of standards at EU level would be desirable to create a unified basis that can be applied in each country. Deciding what information is relevant is a critical task for developers of information exchange systems between institutions.

Common Operational Picture		
ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP5.4.1-5	C2 applications	Integrate information from other agencies into command-and-control applications for each cross-border emergency service
OP5.4.1-6	Improving Mission assessments by technological deployments	VR goggles and see a visual fly out of entire joint schemes of manoeuvre, war-gaming COAs real time while discussing them with the distributed planning staff who used the same environment to build the plans
OP5.4.1-7	Improving visualization techniques in MCI and disasters	Study and learn from every advanced visualisation technique used in other sectors of society and try to apply their usefulness to an emergency situation.
OP5.4.1-8	On-the-fly generated data representations using advanced, cognitive loop enhancing techniques (dendrograms, stream graphs, hive plots...)	In order for the image and information to be updated live, it is necessary that a person intervening in the emergency has the function of interacting with the system that provides the COP and constantly updates it with the data it receives. Some elements could be updated with the use of well positioned sensors, cameras and so on.
OP5.4.1-9	Facilitating a COP through a common federated system	Use available satellite services monitoring weather and their results (such as Copernicus or Aratos Satellite), map the weather conditions as layers in COP/Hybrid Digital Twins and exchange through a common federated system / COP
OP5.4.1-10	Creating a unified COP for MCI and disasters	Creating a COP that provides realistic, situationally aware information, tailored so that its visualisation can be understood by agencies of different types, is essential. But it will also be necessary for the user to have options within the COP to access more specific information in their field.
OP5.4.1-11	Pay special attention to the safety of first responders.	It is difficult to fully ensure the safety of first responders during a disaster, but in addition to providing adequate means and fostering an adequate safety culture in the emergency services, it is essential to maintain adequate situational awareness at all times.

Table 41 – Opportunities from Common Operational Picture

Alert and warning		
ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP5.4.2-1	Defining a common approach to disaster early warning	There is an opportunity for a common approach in alerting the citizens of disaster-susceptible areas before disasters occur.

Alert and warning		
ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP5.4.2-2	Identifying "high priority public warnings"	Documents and guides have been published in order to describe the technique for identifying "high priority public warnings". This refers to alerts for situations in which people need to act immediately or within the next hour, in response to an extraordinary or significant threat that is already observed or is likely to occur. Although these are less than one percent of the alert messages typically accessible to the public, such high priority messages are crucial to enabling people to preserve life and protect property.
OP5.4.2-3	Standardization of alerts procedures and responsibilities in Europe	The alert of MCI incidents should be comprehended and common at European level and subsequently at national and local level. The notification must be common, as, in the case of an MCI incident that occurs at a cross-border point, the alert and notification responsibilities and procedures must be standardized for all stakeholders.
OP5.4.2-4	Standardization of alerts information and systems in Europe	A single emergency alert message standard is needed to communicate alerts over a variety of communications infrastructure (e.g., broadcast TV and radio, cellular, and wired media), thereby reaching the end user over variety of last-mile technologies (e.g., cellular, cable, DSL, Wi-Fi, Bluetooth). Common Alerting Protocol (CAP) attempts to serve this purpose. CAP, which is used by U.S IPAWS, provides a standardized data profile that defines a consistent way for alert and warning messages to be distributed among the involved entities. The EU supports its Member States in the assessment of hazards by complementing their national early warning and information systems in real-time. These tools contribute to early analysis and actions through early warnings. Alerts allow the Emergency Response Coordination Centre to provide a comprehensive early assessment. It also enables early action within the framework of EU civil protection inside the EU and worldwide.
OP5.4.2-5	Technological upgrading of warning systems	Adequate upgrading of the technological resources of emergency services and emergency operations centres would help promote early warning and the appropriate issuance and dissemination of alerts.

Alert and warning		
ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP5.4.2-6	Hybrid Digital Twins as an alert and warning harmonization tool	Map all digitized data, including alarms and warnings issued, into Hybrid Digital Twins of SIGRUN system and transfer a copy to all involved C2s (within a country or between countries) following permission criteria
OP5.4.2-7	Creating and supporting initiatives that fight against misinformation in disasters	Currently, the main route of communication of emergencies are social networks, representing both an opportunity thanks to the rapid dissemination of information and a challenge due to the great presence of hoaxes and false/fake news.
OP5.4.2-8	Social media analysis of citizens behaviour	Social media and apps analysis of citizen's behaviour. Out of the scope of the Valkyries project.

Table 42 – Opportunities from Alert and warning

Resource Federation and trusted information sharing		
ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP6.1-1	Use of resource federation techniques	The Valkyries project identifies an opportunity for implementing data federation and data sharing strategies between EU members in emergency situations.
OP6.1-2	Create a common regulation for resource federation at the EU level	Creating a new EU-level federation regulation could allow countries to effectively share sensitive data between affected members following GDPR guidelines.
OP6.1-3	Dynamic management of data federation	The EU could define guidelines indicating the best principles to implement dynamic data federation strategies, as well as creating regulations for their implantation for all EU members.
OP6.1-4	Use of temporal session keys	Since using pre-shared keys for protecting communications is not recommended, we encourage as an opportunity for improvement the use of temporal keys derived from an initial key, reducing the impact of attacks on confidentiality.
OP6.1-5	Generate a certification authority at EU level for emergencies	The creation of a certification authority at EU level for its use in emergency situations could considerably simplify the complexity of the public key infrastructure required in these scenarios.
OP6.1-6	Use of hybrid cryptographic solutions	In practise, applications commonly use a hybrid approach between symmetric and asymmetric cryptography. The first one is used for encrypting the data transmitted, while the latter is employed for key distribution. There is an opportunity for standardisation in this regard at EU level, particularly in medical scenarios, and for the use of Decentralized identifiers and verifiable credentials.
OP6.1-7	Optimisation of data redundancy techniques	There is an opportunity for improving the efficiency of protocols and techniques used for data redundancy, optimising storage resources.

Resource Federation and trusted information sharing		
ID	Opportunity name	Justification
	regarding data storage	
OP6.1-8	Optimisation of data redundancy techniques regarding data coherence	There is an opportunity for improving current protocols and techniques used for data redundancy, taking into consideration data coherence between nodes.
OP6.1-9	EU regulations regarding data redundancy	The EU could put efforts in creating guidelines or regulations offering recommendations about the most suitable technologies to avoid these situations.
OP6.1-10	Dynamic network management	Emergency services could benefit from using dynamic network management principles such as SDN to reconfigure the network to offer more adaptability and better services, reducing the cost.
OP6.1-11	On-demand security capabilities	There is room for regulations indicating how to manage emergency networks in a dynamic way to offer security capabilities on demand.
OP6.1-12	EU Regulations regarding data federation framework	It would be desirable that all EU members adopt a common framework offering data federation. Therefore, it is necessary to establish regulations, with respect to data federation and frameworks.
OP6.1-13	Definition of general data federation frameworks	There is an opportunity for designing and creating a general enough framework to include all particularities of the different emergency services operating in the EU.
OP6.1-14	Federation incompatibilities	EU regulations could offer a list of federation technologies that should be implemented by all federation platforms and technologies to comply with the EU regulation.
OP6.1-15	OAuth 2.0 - Optimised designs for data federations	There is an opportunity for system administrators to design federated systems keeping a low structural complexity.
OP6.1-16	OAuth 2.0 - Redundant authorisation server	There is an opportunity for system administrators to design federated systems based on OAuth using load balancing techniques over multiple authorisation servers.
OP6.1-17	Shibboleth - Single Sign Out	Valkyries identifies an opportunity to improve the Shibboleth standard by incorporating single sign out capabilities.
OP6.1-18	Shibboleth - Reduce implementation complexity	There is an opportunity for improving the Shibboleth standard to ease the complexity of proxy servers.
OP6.1-19	PQC KEM hybrid schemas	As PQC standardization enables to implement efficient cypher cryptosystems, there is an opportunity to implement these schemas and avoid future transitions.
OP6.1-20	PQC DSA hybrid schemas	As PQC standardization enables to implement efficient signature cryptosystems, there is an opportunity to implement these schemas and avoid future transitions.

Resource Federation and trusted information sharing		
ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP6.1-21	Quantum Key Distribution	The implementation of QKD systems would provide information-theoretically secure keys to the cryptosystem.
OP6.1-22	Light cryptographic methods	The use of lighter algorithms will ease the implementation using less powerful devices.
OP6.1-23	Distributed PKI	The use of distributed PKI would avoid the problems of availability related to network failures during emergency actuations.
OP6.1-24	Common data language, taxonomy and reference schema	Use of a scheme Library supported on a database, where the library holds different cooperation reference schemas allows each event to negotiate establish and store the schema used by the event, or reuse in future events. It enables a federated system to define a common reference frame for data sharing
OP6.1-25	Tampered data	Use of Blockchain to detect tampered data and data auditing
OP6.1-26	COP marking data source	Establish a COP definition to mark differently external and own data sources displayed
OP6.1-27	Backup data	Define a backup service to collect all the data: Block-chain for transactional data, and for all the exchanged metadata. Local data backup capability to provide resilience and adaptability in case of connectivity lost. Establish an automatic restore capability in case of temporary data lost
OP6.1-28	High level framework	Without changes in the current framework. Define a high-level framework that translates de data and make this interoperable- (SIGRUN) ₂

Table 43 – Opportunities from Resource Federation and trusted information sharing

Education and training for first aid responses		
ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP6.2-1	Common core curriculum for the speciality of emergency medicine	The WHO provides a classification and minimum standards for emergency medical teams that could serve as a basis for a European classification.
OP6.2-2	European Paramedic Curriculum (EPaCur)	This curriculum could increase the number of countries offering this type of training at the undergraduate level, which would raise the level of competence of paramedical professionals in general.
OP6.2-3	Cooperation and coordination between institutions	Facilitate the exchange of information necessary for decision-making by the different services involved in the emergency response.

Education and training for first aid responses		
ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP6.2-4	Standardisation of reports and debriefing	Implementation of a system based on the EU Civil Protection Knowledge Network and Lessons Learned Programme or WHO Guidance for After Action Review. Standardised data collection could facilitate the compilation of the information in a global database.
OP6.2-5	Creation of a lessons learned database for FARs at European level	A global database of lessons learned would connect outcomes that could be transformed into recommendations for future improvement.
OP6.2-6	Creation of a universally valid European First Aid Certificates	These certificates should be issued by a National accredited institution after a specific training recognised via EQF and be conducted by the EU-OSHA, based on the guidelines of the ERC.
OP6.2-7	Creation of a Register of European First Aid members.	A European First Aid Certificate opens the opportunity to create a European register of qualified personnel for the intervention in Mass Casualty Incident (MCI). These types of registries help the development of international and cross-border protocols.
OP6.2-8	Conduct of simulation exercises	Development of educational software for simulations of disasters, accidents and catastrophes for educational purposes. The software, in this sense, will contribute to the quality and effect of the overall training process in the direction of forming and upgrading the practical skills of employees for risk assessment, timely management decision-making, ensuring appropriate coordination, and emergency control and response systems situations. The purpose of its development is for every employee of the FARs to be registered in the specified platform and to have access to training materials for various courses and trained
OP6.2-9	Creating or supplementing the legislative framework in the field of natural disasters and environmental catastrophes.	This initiative is imperative from the point of view of refining the conceptual apparatus, because the declaration of a state of emergency requires the existence of a law defining extraordinary events.
OP6.2-10	Transformation of General Directorate of Fire Safety and Protection of the Population	Transformation of the structure on the basis of the relief and climatic features of the territory of the Republic of Bulgaria. This will lead to optimization not only of the capabilities that these structures will have, but also lead to an appropriate use of resources

Education and training for first aid responses		
ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP6.2-11	Acquisition of new vehicles and equipment from neighbouring countries, NATO and EU partners	A consistent and efficient policy for acquisition is required on the government level. On regional and international levels, cooperation between the neighbours which are part of same organizations is considered to be a good practice. Therefore, a trade of new vehicles and equipment between them is also in consideration. The old ones can be sold, used for last time by the partners in hazardous regions or be sliced into pieces.
OP6.2-12	Creation of first aid and paramedic help for school and university programs	Enhancement of the presence in the citizens' life from the earliest moments with a volunteer program curriculum. This way the level of saved lives until first aid arrives will increase. By making this program voluntary will test the efficiency of the program. If extremely needed and after a test period the program can become obligatory curriculum.
OP6.2-13	Establishment and rebuilding of some of the former first aid institutions	The whole process is a prolonging one which requires finance from the government as well as additional funding from the EU cohesive fund. Also, the political site of the issue must be addressed here, with the passing of amendments to the existing law for health care. If needed an additional supporting law must be accepted by the Parliament.

Table 44 – Opportunities from Education and training for first aid responses

Raising practitioner and social awareness		
ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP6.3-1	SIGRUN application	Providing advanced communications, information sharing and tactical C&C services for the first (first-aid) responders
OP6.3-2	VOSTs	Virtual Operation Support Teams (VOSTs) have been established in many countries to help authorities manage information in high-pressure information environments. These teams monitor social media, support situational awareness, counter rumours and disseminate official communication. Establishing this kind of teams within all EU countries.
OP6.3-3	Debriefing sessions after each incident or disaster	This is an issue that also arise in D5.2. Debriefing sessions after the intervention are missing or unappreciated parts of the incident or disaster
OP6.3-4	Alternative communication system	Provide the back-up plan in the case of failure of ordinary used systems
OP6.3-5	Strategy for public awareness	Development of Strategy for public awareness
OP6.3-6	Unified communication language	Design of a catalogue of visual warning signs (indicative signs, colour codes) or auditory signs (alarms) to alert and inform the population.

Table 45 – Opportunities from Raising practitioner and social awareness

Civil-Military cooperation		
ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP6.4-1	Implementation of European civil-military doctrine.	At the European level, the Joint Allied Doctrine for the Military Contribution to Humanitarian Assistance has been developed to provide basic guidelines and standards for planning and executing operations in support of civilian structures. There is also a training centre
OP6.4-2	Shared understanding brought about by working together, connecting, education	Through creation and adoption of unified guidance, procedures and TTPs for applying the capabilities of CIMIC specialists and experts in disaster settings will provide greater clarity on the contribution and future actions of civil and military actors in such operations.
OP6.4-3	Development of national requirements and capabilities for the implementation of joint civil-military procedures for disasters, accidents and catastrophes	By developing national requirements and a program to build capabilities to implement joint civil-military procedures in disasters, accidents and catastrophes, better coordination and cooperation between military and civilian teams will be achieved
OP6.4-4	Programs and scenarios for joint training of civil-military teams developing	If programs and scenarios are developed for the joint training of civil-military teams, then in cases of natural disasters, they will immediately begin the implementation of the developed and mastered practical procedures for providing assistance to the population
OP6.4-5	Amendment of the current Law for defence of classified information	The current application and use of the law is not perfect, it needs amends, which would help speed up the process by which the medical staff will gain access to classified information. Such amendments can be in the period in which the access is granted and the waiting is shortened for example by two-three weeks.
OP6.4-6	Insertion of new technology and checkpoints for communication with neighbouring country	Enhancing the level of communication between neighbouring countries is an important matter in potential and enduring cooperation between the neighbours on civil and on military level.

Table 46 – Opportunities from Civil-Military cooperation

Civil Protection and Aid Volunteerism		
ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP6.5-1	Encourage the intercultural competencies and foreign language skills in the training for first responders to cross-border MCI	To ensure compatibility and complementarity between intervention teams, the UCPM provides a training programme. The training helps experts improve their coordination and assessment skills in disaster response, but it should be complemented with the intercultural competencies and foreign language skills.

Civil Protection and Aid Volunteerism		
ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP6.5-2	Integration of volunteers into the emergency operational procedures	Define the roles, "chain of command", liability and the way to operate within the emergency cycle for volunteers.
OP6.5-3	Guarantee the involvement of volunteers in field exercises	Field exercises test the specific response capabilities, self-sufficiency, interoperability, coordination and procedures of the different actors and their response material. The UCPM should ensure that volunteers participate in its field exercises, as they are one of the actors involved.
OP6.5-4	Ensure protection of volunteers during their operation exploring insurance field.	Follow a strategic approach by defining a limited area of assistance as well as risk-free activities for those volunteers who are not protected by insurance.
OP6.5-5	Creation of a lessons learned database in Civil Protection	A global database of lessons learned would make easier to connect outcomes from past that could be transformed into recommendations for future improvement.
OP6.5-6	Introduction of first aid spontaneous volunteers management course/ programme	In the large-scale disasters usually a large number of medical and non-medical staff volunteers to support field operations. So far there is no unified training programme how to manage those people.

Table 47 – Opportunities from Civil Protection and Aid Volunteerism

Sustainable International/European Certification and evaluation facilities - Equipment				
ID	Related gaps	Opportunity name	Type of input	Justification
OP3.5-1	G3.5-1	Collect, organize and present certification requirements for SAR equipment	Professional experience, rules and regulations	Technology providers need easy access to certification requirements for SAR equipment and efficient certification procedures to innovate and get equipment to market quicker
OP3.5-2	G3.5-1	Gathering the laws and standards information related to first aid response enablers in database	Professional experience	The laws and standards are essential to the certification, so finding the relevant laws and standards is a fundamental and important task in the certification process
OP3.5-3	G3.5-1	Demonstrate that the application of the existing regulation/certification scheme to novel technologies is adequate	Professional experience	Until the regulations and standards are established, manufacturers may apply relevant existing laws/standards/certification to their new product. So, it is

Sustainable International/European Certification and evaluation facilities - Equipment				
ID	Related gaps	Opportunity name	Type of input	Justification
				necessary to evaluate that existing ones are enough
OP3.5-4	G3.5-10	Arrange communication channel between stakeholders in the certification process	Professional experience	In order to increase efficiency, the stakeholders in the certification process need to communicate each other from the beginning of the development
OP3.5-5	G3.5-10	Establish online information sharing site	Professional experience	A positive effect can be expected if all stakeholders can easily access to the information about the certification
OP3.5-6	G3.5-9	Identify that requirements of the first aid response enabler and organize the data for further reference	Professional experience	The evaluation procedures and criteria vary according to the enablers. It would be useful if there is well organized requirements according to the enablers
OP3.5-7	G3.5-7	Suggest customized conformity assessment methodology for SAR equipment/system in order to save time and cost	Professional experience	From the economic aspects, the utilization of customized conformity assessment methodologies (e.g., simulation, virtual reality) could save expenditure in the certification process
OP3.5-8	G3.5-6, G3.5-7	Suggest measures for that conformity assessment can be carried out along with development process	Professional experience	To enhance the efficiency of the certification process, the conformity assessment needs to be carried out from the early stage of development
OP3.5-9	G3.5-2, G3.5-3	Build a database of useful information from the initiative projects for novel technologies	Professional experience	Well organized information will be useful for further reference
OP3.5-10	G3.5-12	New tested technology	Professional experience	Use of technology with experience in the field under the same context of operation
OP3.5-11	G3.5-13	Lighten the resources in cybersecurity recertification	Literature	The use of automatic tests could reduce the resources required in the cybersecurity recertification process

Sustainable International/European Certification and evaluation facilities - Equipment				
ID	Related gaps	Opportunity name	Type of input	Justification
OP3.5-12	G3.5-14	Include medium and low risk AI certification schemes in the proposed Act on AI	Literature	The working groups for Act on AI should promote the AI certification schemes for medium and low risk AI systems, expanding the certification market
OP3.5-13	G3.5-15	Security for novel technological devices	Professional experience	Protect and recover information after some incident
OP3.5-14	G3.5-16	Possible joint usage of facilities for certification.	Professional experience	Propose mechanisms for collaboration between test facilities to get increased capacity and quicker certification process
OP3.5-15	G3.5-17	Collaboration between stakeholders related to cybersecurity		Through collaboration between cybersecurity experts, technology developers, regulatory bodies, and certification organizations, robust, up-to-date, and universally recognized cybersecurity criteria for certification can be established
OP3.5-16	G3.5-18	Data flow and interfaces		Certification scheme can consider the security of data flows and interfaces between the new technology and existing systems
OP3.5-17	G3.5-18 and 19	A thorough Risk assessment		A comprehensive risk assessment could identify potential security risks when new technologies interface with legacy systems

Table 48 – Opportunities related to certification of technologies and equipment for emergency response

Sustainable International/European Certification and evaluation facilities - Operations				
ID	Related gaps	Opportunity name	Type of input	Justification
OP3.5-18	G3.5-22	Harmonize certification requirements for DRONE operation in disaster response between national states	Professional experience, rules and regulations	Clarity is needed for drone operators in cross-border situations
OP3.5-19	G3.5-25, G3.5-23	Improve staff skill	Professional experience	Use correctly equipment and improve teamwork
OP3.5-20	G3.5-24	Harmonization of procedures and operations	Professional experience	Better effectiveness related with international border scenario
OP3.5-21	-	Perform international test with the use cases and technology solutions built on Valkyries	Professional experience	It will improve the overall performance of the results with the fine-tuning of ideas and technological proposals through the test
OP3.5-22	G3.5-25	European certification for pre-hospital emergency medical personnel	Literature	The creation of a common European certificate for pre-hospital emergency medical personnel would make cross-border cooperation more efficient
OP3.5-23	-	New certification schemes are business opportunity for CABs	Professional experience	As new certification schemes emerge, the portfolio of services and tools that CABs can offer is expanding
OP3.5-24	G3.5-27	Customized Training programs that can be used in certification procedure		Develop training programs tailored to the specific technologies that FRs will be using.
OP3.5-25	G3.5-27	Utilize new capabilities		Incorporate new capabilities that mimic the high-stress environments FRs may face. It allows FRs to practice using the technology under pressure,

Sustainable International/European Certification and evaluation facilities - Operations				
ID	Related gaps	Opportunity name	Type of input	Justification
				improving their effectiveness and decision-making skills
OP3.5-26	G3.5-27	Include Hands-on Training in the certification procedure for FRs		Practical experiences build confidence and helps FRs become familiar with the new technologies
OP3.5-27	G3.5-27	Incorporating continuous learning into the certification scheme for FRs		“continuous learning” is an essential aspect of ensuring that FRs remain proficient in using new technologies and are prepared to handle evolving challenges in emergency situations
OP3.5-28	G3.5-27	Establishing consistent training and qualification requirements for FRs across different regions		Standardization ensures that all FRs meet a uniform level of expertise, regardless of their deployment location
OP3.5-29	G3.5-28	Cost-effective certification		Find cost-effective strategies that provide significant value in terms of skills, knowledge, and improved capabilities while aligning with limited budgets
OP3.5-30	G3.5-29	Post-certification monitoring		Ongoing monitoring may ensure that certified enablers remain reliable and safe for use in emergency situations.
OP3.5-31	G3.5-30	Interdisciplinary training programs		Develop interdisciplinary training programs and educational courses that bring together experts from technology, disaster management, ethics, public safety, and other relevant fields.
OP3.5-32	G3.5-30	Interdisciplinary advisory committees		Establish advisory committees composed of experts from different fields to provide

Sustainable International/European Certification and evaluation facilities - Operations				
ID	Related gaps	Opportunity name	Type of input	Justification
				guidance to certification bodies.
OP3.5-33	G3.5-30	Ethical and social impact assessments		Integrate ethical and social impact assessments into the certification process. This involves evaluating not only the technical aspects of a technology but also its potential ethical, legal, and societal consequences.
OP3.5-34	G3.5-31	Flexible certification criteria		Develop certification criteria that are adaptable and can be updated as technologies evolve.
OP3.5-35	G3.5-32	International cooperation and harmonization		Dedicated forums and working groups can be established to foster international partnerships and collaborations among governments, regulatory bodies, and relevant international organization, with the aim of aligning disaster management technology standards.
OP3.5-36	G3.5-33	Integrate Human-centric training and awareness		Develop and implement regular cybersecurity training and awareness programs for end-users. Focus on educating them about recognizing and mitigating security threats, including phishing, social engineering, and safe online behavior.
OP3.5-37	G3.5-34	Implementing lifelong learning, ongoing assessment, and a supportive organizational culture in certification scheme		Implement mandatory continuing education requirements for first responders to ensure that they stay up-to-date with the latest techniques, technologies, and best practices in emergency response.

Sustainable International/European Certification and evaluation facilities - Operations				
ID	Related gaps	Opportunity name	Type of input	Justification
OP3.5-38	G3.5-35	Creating effective harmonized guidelines for certified FRs during cross-border emergency operations		Effective harmonized guidelines are essential for promoting seamless and legally compliant cross-border emergency response. It facilitates cooperation, reduce legal uncertainties, and enhance the overall effectiveness of emergency operations, ensuring the safety and well-being of both FRs and affected communities.

Table 49 – Opportunities related to certification of operation in emergency response

12. Annex E – Mapping and Harmonization needs to improve standards, including voluntary Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) and ISO or EN standards

VALKYRIES

Task 3.4 Mapping and Harmonisation needs to improve standards, including voluntary Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) and ISO or EN standards

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1. Executive Summary

This report includes the work activity developed under T3.4 and constitutes an Annex of the D3.10 as a premise to the final analysis developed under T3.5. The document describes the different works carried out with the international standardization norms that can be used in any type of organization to achieve the standardization and homogenization of cross-border emergency management activities. The possible ISO or EN standards that are related to emergency management have been identified and analyzed, and an analysis of them has been carried out to identify gaps and opportunities for the comprehensive management of cross-border emergencies. In the same way, the different standard operating procedures that are used by end users and emergency teams have been identified and analyzed.

The activities carried out for the development of the different objectives have been based on the study and analysis of international standards such as ISO and EN based on the following technical committees:

- ISO/TC 262 Risk management
- ISO/TC 292 Security and resilience
- ISO/TC 46/SC 10
- ISO/TC 215 Health informatics
- ISO/TC 176/SC 2 Quality systems
- ISO/TC 21/SC 3 Fire detection
- ISO/TC 211 Geographic information

The reference standards with a national scope of all the participants of the Valkyries project have also been compiled, for the different use cases that are derived from transpositions of international standards.

Other international standards compiled, shown below, originate from the IEC-CEN-CENELEC organizations:

- CEN/TC 239 – Rescue systems
- CEN/TC 192 – Fire and rescue service equipment
- TC 65/SC 65A – Systems aspects

The standard operating procedures have been compiled and analyzed by the different organizations that make up the Valkyries group.

The identified gaps and opportunities have been coded for traceability.

In the next chapters, some maps of international standards and standard operating procedures is presented, together with the identification of associated gaps and opportunities. Once analysed as conclusions, some recommendations are generated for a regulatory reference framework and a template of operating procedures.

2. Identification

Deliverable Title: Mapping and Harmonisation needs to improve standards, including voluntary Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) and ISO or EN standards

Deliverable Id: T3.4

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3. Introduction

3.1. Objectives

The main objective of the document is to respond to Task 3.4 of Harmonization and pre-standardization of equipment, training and coordinated tactical procedures for the deployment of resources in European catastrophes with multiple victims.

Investigate and analyze pre-standardization opportunities related to first aid response facilitators, which give rise to recommendations, common requirements, guidelines and application tools to constitute a new and sustainable reference model, which is applied in new standardization actions. .

Identify opportunities and improvements related to international standards (ISO/EN) applicable to cross-border emergency management. Compile the SOPs currently developed within the scope of cross-border emergency management and the identification of gaps and opportunities for the different identified use cases.

From the analysis of the gaps associated with the SOPs, taking into account the different processes in the use cases, establishing the criteria for action and the minimum common information necessary to obtain a unified SOP to be used in the framework of cross-border emergency management.

4. Methodology

ISO standards are a set of regulations and provisions of universal application, which are intended to guarantee minimum quality conditions, minimum technological requirements, and service levels in all types of organizations and services.

Organizations that comply with the requisites of the ISO standards will have an objective recognition that endorses them in front of their clients, which in case of being certified, will be granted by the entities that manage the normalization or standardization of processes worldwide. In any case, the application of the standards guarantees an objective recognition of a standard methodology.

Having the ISO certificate is synonymous with a minimum operational excellence for international standards in the area in which the organization is dedicated. On the other hand, ISO standards seek to create a minimum framework of requirements and organizational endorsement through the creation of an ISO method that is internationally valid.

The objective pursued by ISO standards is to ensure that products and/or services achieve the desired quality. For organizations, they are instruments that allow minimizing costs, since they make it possible to reduce errors and, above all, they favor the increase in productivity and efficiency.

For society, ISO standards are also important. There are more than 19,500 standards that help almost all aspects of a person's day-to-day life, such as those aimed at guaranteeing road safety or the safety of toys or emergency management. If a product and/or service complies with any of these regulations, society can be sure that they are reliable and that they have the quality required worldwide.

During the elaboration of any of these standards, ISO considers that it is of great importance that the users or consumers of these services and/or final products form part of the expert

committees responsible for said elaboration, as well as professionals of the sector/service in question.

The VALKYRIES project has created a methodology based on taking ISO/EN reference information and SOPs. The identification of the standards, together with the compilation of the operational operating procedures, and the identification of gaps and opportunities of each of them individually and as a whole, allows the projection of a standardized regulatory framework for the management of cross-border emergencies and the creation of operating procedures to be used during the event by any organization.

The analysis of the different standards in the context of cross-border emergency management, taking into account expert opinion, differences between countries and usability capabilities in a uniform way in an international environment allows a first approach to creating a unified international standard framework.

Standard operating procedures are developed as a tool for the operation of the uniform framework for cross-border management. Operational procedures in cross-border management require the participation of at least the neighbouring countries, the various organisations involved and take into account the cultural differences of their societies. The analysis of the diversity of information included in the collection of the SOPs consulted makes it possible to present a possible unified operating procedure solution.

4.1. Review of ISO/SOPs

A compilation and research study of all the possible regulations/standards applicable or related to regulations and safety and emergency management has been carried out, preparing a list where each one of them has been analyzed, identifying all the opportunities applicable to the integral management of actions in case of cross-border emergency.

A shared work file has been created with Valkyries group, which constitutes a normative reference map, where all the norms are compiled and the possible opportunities to apply the common or unified procedure have been analyzed for each of them.

Each ISO technical committee generates, based on certain needs, issued by the interested parties, various families of standards. During the project, a large part of the regulations in force have been investigated to identify, in the first instance, which are the most appropriate for the VALKYRIES project. These standards have been analyzed under certain criteria to assess the suitability of the selection within the consortium.

Application use cases and their relationship with the different work groups have been assigned for each of them. For this, we have worked with a unified support where to trace the various relationships and trace all the information.

The study was carried out on all norms/standards related to Emergencies, Safety and Quality, according to the following categories:

- Emergency management: set of reference standards intended to create a common framework for cross-border emergency management and "improve the security and resilience of society"
- Emergency management support: standards associated with emergency management that serve to specify activities and sub-processes of emergency management
- Technology: set of international standards related to technological aspects

- Vehicle requirements: Its purpose is to analyze the requirements to be met by the means of medical transport
- IT Security: It tries to harmonize aspects related to data security and information management with a computer component.
- Management system: bases of a general management system on which to settle for the rest of the processes
- Vocabulary: reference standards that serve as a glossary for the rest of the standards analyzed

For each ISO standard, the impact on the consortium has been analyzed, identifying the proprietary availability of the reference standards, the identification of certifications and knowledge of the standard. ISO standards, having a general treatment and not focused on a specific sector, together with the voluntary use of the standards, cause their own factor of lack of standardization in the implementation and reference in the development of activities. This prior knowledge taking highlights the necessary analysis of gaps and opportunities starting from a previous state, in terms of the identification and ownership of the rules, and secondly, those related to the development of the rules within a common framework, comprehensive management of cross-border emergencies.

Document Definition	Introduction/Scope
ISO 22320:2018 Security and resilience - Emergency management - Guidelines for incident management	ISO 22320:2018. This document gives guidelines for incident management, including <ul style="list-style-type: none"> — principles that communicate the value and explain the purpose of incident management, — basic components of incident management including process and structure, which focus on roles and responsibilities, tasks and management of resources, and — working together through joint direction and cooperation.
ISO 22322:2015 Security and resilience - Emergency management - Guidelines for public warnings	ISO 22322:2015 provides guidelines for developing, managing, and implementing public warning before, during, and after incidents.
ISO 22324:2015 Security and resilience - Emergency management - Guidelines for colour-coded alerts	ISO 22324:2015 provides guidelines for the use of colour codes to inform people at risk as well as first response personnel about danger and to express the severity of a situation. It is applicable to all types of hazard in any location.
ISO/TR 22351:2015 Societal Security - Emergency Management - Message structure for exchange of information (EMSI - Emergency Management Shared Information)	ISO/TR 22351:2015 describes a message structure for the exchange of information between organizations involved in emergency management. An organization can ingest the received information, based on the message structure, in its own operational picture.
ISO 22398:2013 Societal security — Guidelines for exercises	ISO 22398:2013 recommends good practice and guidelines for an organization to plan, conduct, and improve its exercise projects which may be organized within an exercise programme.
ISO 22300:2021 Security and resilience — Vocabulary	This document defines terms used in security and resilience standards.
UNE 179002:2018 Health services. Quality management system (QMS) for health care transport organization.	This rule is mandatory for those entities that carry out medical transport by road, whether public or private.
UNE-EN 13718-1:2015+A1:2020 Medical vehicles and their equipment - Air ambulances - Part 1: Requirements for medical devices used in air ambulances Medical vehicles and their equipment - Air ambulances - Part 2: Operational and technical requirements for air ambulances	Part 1- This European Standard specifies the general requirements for medical devices carried by and used in air ambulances and in external hospitals and clinics in situations where environmental conditions may differ from normal indoor conditions. Part 2- This part of EN 13718 specifies the requirements for the performance and equipment of air ambulances, including the requirements for interfaces with medical devices, used for the transport and treatment of sick or injured persons. This part of EN 13718 is

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	applicable to air ambulances capable of transporting at least one person on a stretcher.
ISO/IEC 27001:2013. Information Technology - Security Techniques - Information security management systems (ISMS) - Requeriments	ISO/IEC 27001:2022 This document specifies the requirements for establishing, implementing, maintaining and continually improving an information security management system within the context of the organization. This document also includes requirements for the assessment and treatment of information security risks tailored to the needs of the organization. The requirements set out in this document are generic and are intended to be applicable to all organizations, regardless of type, size or nature. Excluding any of the requirements specified in Clauses 4 to 10 is not acceptable when an organization claims conformity to this document.
ISO 22328:2020-1 Securty and resilience - Emergency management - Guidelines for the implementation of a community-based disaster early warnings system	ISO 22328:2020-1 This document gives guidelines for the implementation of a community-based disaster early warning system (EWS). It describes the methods and procedures to be implemented and provides examples.
ISO 22315:2014 Societal security - Mass evacuation - Guidelines for planning	ISO 22315:2014 provides guidelines for mass evacuation planning in terms of establishing, implementing, monitoring, evaluating, reviewing, and improving preparedness. It establishes a framework for each activity in mass evacuation planning for all identified hazards. It will help organizations to develop plans that are evidence-based and that can be evaluated for effectiveness.
ISO 22396:2020 Security and resilience — Community resilience — Guidelines for information exchange between organizations	ISO 22396:2020 This document gives guidelines for information exchange. It includes principles, a framework and a process for information exchange. It identifies mechanisms for information exchange that allow a participating organization to learn from others' experiences, mistakes and successes. It can be used to guide the maintenance of the information exchange arrangement in order to increase commitment and engagement. It provides measures that enhance the ability of participating organizations to cope with disruption risk.
ISO 22319:2017 Security and resilience - Community resilience - Guidelines for planning the involvement of spontaneous volunteers	ISO 22319:2017 provides guidelines for planning the involvement of spontaneous volunteers (SVs) in incident response and recovery. It is intended to help organizations to establish a plan to consider whether, how and when SVs can provide relief to a coordinated response and recovery for all identified hazards. It helps identify issues to ensure the plan is risk-based and can be shown to prioritize the safety of SVs, the public they seek to assist and incident response staff.
ISO 9001:2015 Quality management systems — Requirements	ISO 9001:2015 The adoption of a quality management system is a strategic decision for an organization that can help to improve its overall performance and provide a sound basis for sustainable development initiatives.
ISO 19136:2007 / ISO 19136-1:2020 Geographic information — Geography Markup Language (GML) — Part 1: Fundamentals	Geography Markup Language (GML) is an XML grammar written in XML Schema for the description of application schemas as well as the transport and storage of geographic information.
ISO 19128:2005 Geographic information — Web map server interface (WMS)	ISO 19128:2005 specifies the behaviour of a service that produces spatially referenced maps dynamically from geographic information. It specifies operations to retrieve a description of the maps offered by a

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	server, to retrieve a map, and to query a server about features displayed on a map
ISO 19142:2010 Geographic information — Web Feature Service (WFS)	ISO 19142:2010 specifies the behaviour of a web feature service that provides transactions on and access to geographic features in a manner independent of the underlying data store. It specifies discovery operations, query operations, locking operations, transaction operations and operations to manage stored parameterized query expressions.
CEN ISO/TS 19139:2009 / ISO/TS 19139-1:2019 Geographic information — XML schema implementation — Part 1: Encoding rules	This document defines XML based encoding rules for conceptual schemas specifying types that describe geographic resources. The encoding rules support the UML profile as used in the UML models commonly used in the standards developed by ISO/TC 211. The encoding rules use XML schema for the output data structure schema.
EN 1789:2020 Medical vehicles and their equipment - Road ambulances	This European Standard specifies requirements for the design, testing, performance and equipping of road ambulances used for the transport, monitoring, treatment and care of patients. It contains requirements for the patient's compartment in terms of the working environment, ergonomic design and the safety of the crew and patients.
EN 1846-1:2011 Firefighting and rescue service vehicles - Part 1: Nomenclature and designation	This European Standard establishes classes and defines categories which are functions of the use and mass of the firefighting and rescue service vehicles and provides a designation system that gives the various criteria used for characterizing the vehicles.
EN 1846-2:2009+A1:2013 Firefighting and rescue service vehicles - Part 2: Common requirements - Safety and performance	This European Standard specifies the common requirements for safety and the (minimum) common performance requirements of firefighting and rescue service vehicles as designated in EN 1846-1
EN 1846-3:2013 Firefighting and rescue service vehicles - Part 3: Permanently installed equipment - Safety and performance	This part of this European Standard specifies the minimum requirements for safety and performance of some optional specific permanently installed equipment on firefighting and rescue service vehicles, operated by trained persons, as designated in EN 1846-1 and specified in EN 1846-2
EN 13976-2:2018 Rescue systems - Transportation of incubators - Part 2: System requirements	This European Standard specifies the requirements for a transport incubator system needed for care and treatment of infants, used in emergency or planned transport. It specifies the particular requirements needed to ensure the proper function of equipment during transportation (e.g. monitors, respirators, infusion pumps, extra corporeal lung support- (ECLS-) systems, gas supply) and to provide safe transportation for infants and operators. This European Standard also specifies that the equipment or systems shall not interfere with the functions of the road and air ambulance providing transportation.
EN 1865-1:2010+A1:2015 Patient handling equipment used in road ambulances - Part 1: General stretcher systems and patient handling equipment	This European Standard defines minimum requirements for the design and performance of stretchers and other patient handling equipment used in road ambulances for the handling and carrying of patients. It aims to ensure patient safety and minimize the physical effort required by staff operating the equipment.
EN 1865-2:2010+A1:2015 Patient handling equipment used in road ambulances - Part 2: Power assisted stretcher	This European Standard defines minimum requirements for the design and performance of power assisted stretchers used in road ambulances for the treatment and transportation of patients. It aims to ensure patient safety and minimize the physical effort required by staff operating the equipment.

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EN 1865-3:2012+A1:2015 Patient handling equipment used in road ambulances - Part 3: Heavy duty stretcher	This European Standard specifies minimum requirements for the design and performance of heavy duty stretchers used in road ambulances for the treatment and transportation of patients. It aims to ensure patient safety and minimize the physical effort required by staff operating the equipment.
EN 1865-4:2012 Patient handling equipment used in road ambulances - Part 4: Foldable patient transfer chair	This European Standard defines the minimum requirements for the design and performance of foldable patient transfer chairs, which are used for the conveyance of patients to and/or from road ambulances. It aims to ensure patient safety and to minimize the physical effort required by staff operating the equipment.
EN 1865-5:2012 Patient handling equipment used in road ambulances - Part 5: Stretcher support	This European Standard specifies the minimum requirements for the design and performance of stretcher supports that are installed in road ambulances to hold the main stretcher or incubator systems in accordance with EN 1865-1, EN 1865-2 and EN 13976-2 to ensure patient and operators safety and to minimise the physical effort required by staff operating the equipment. In this European Standard reference is made to EN 1789.
ISO 13606-1:2019 Health informatics — Electronic health record communication — Part 1: Reference model	This document specifies a means for communicating part or all of the electronic health record (EHR) of one or more identified subjects of care between EHR systems, or between EHR systems and a centralised EHR data repository.
ISO 31073:2022(en) Risk management — Vocabulary. 2022	This document defines generic terms related to the management of risks faced by organizations.
BS EN 17173:2020 European CBRNE glossary	This document contains terms and definitions for CBRNE (chemical, biological, radiological, nuclear, explosive) applications.
ISO 22327:2018 Security and resilience — Emergency management — Guidelines for implementation of a community-based landslide early warning system	This document gives guidelines for a landslide early warning system. It provides a definition, aims to improve understanding, describes methods and procedures to be implemented, and gives examples of types of activities.
ISO/DIS 22328-2 Security and resilience — Emergency management — Part 2: Guidelines for the implementation of a community-based landslide early warning system (UNDER DEVELOPMENT)	This document gives guidelines for a landslide early warning system. It provides a definition, aims to improve understanding, describes methods and procedures to be implemented, and gives examples of types of activities.
ISO/FDIS 22328-3 Security and resilience — Emergency management — Part 3: Guidelines for the implementation of a community-based tsunami early warning system (UNDER DEVELOPMENT)	This document gives guidelines for a landslide early warning system. It provides a definition, aims to improve understanding, describes methods and procedures to be implemented, and gives examples of types of activities.
ISO 22329:2021 Security and resilience — Emergency management — Guidelines for the use of social media in emergencies	This document gives guidance on the use of social media in emergency management. It gives guidance on how organizations and the public can use, and interact through, social media before, during and after an incident as well as how social media can support the work of emergency services.
ISO/IEC 27000:2018 Information Technology - Security techniques - Information security management systems - Overview and vocabulary	ISO/IEC 27000:2018 provides the overview of information security management systems (ISMS). It also provides terms and definitions commonly used in the ISMS family of standards

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ISO/IEC/IEEE 15939:2017 Systems and software engineering — Measurement process	ISO/IEC/IEEE 15939:2017 provides an elaboration of the measurement process from ISO/IEC 15288 and ISO/IEC 12207. The measurement process is applicable to system and software engineering and management disciplines. The process is described through a model that defines the activities of the measurement process that are required to adequately specify what measurement information is required, how the measures and analysis results are to be applied, and how to determine if the analysis results are valid. The measurement process is flexible, tailorable, and adaptable to the needs of different users. ISO/IEC/IEEE 15939:2017 identifies a process that supports defining a suitable set of measures that address specific information needs. It identifies the activities and tasks that are necessary to successfully identify, define, select, apply, and improve measurement within an overall project or organizational measurement structure. It also provides definitions for commonly used measurement terms.
ISO/IEC 27002:2022 Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection — Information security controls	This document provides a reference set of generic information security controls including implementation guidance. This document is designed to be used by organizations: a) within the context of an information security management system (ISMS) based on ISO/IEC27001; b) for implementing information security controls based on internationally recognized best practices; c) for developing organization-specific information security management guidelines.
ISO/IEC 27010:2015 Information technology - security techniques - Information security management for inter-sector and inter-organizational communications	ISO/IEC 27010:2015. This International Standard provides controls and guidance specifically relating to initiating, implementing, maintaining, and improving information security in inter-organizational and inter-sector communications. It provides guidelines and general principles on how the specified requirements can be met using established messaging and other technical methods. This International Standard is applicable to all forms of exchange and sharing of sensitive information, both public and private, nationally and internationally, within the same industry or market sector or between sectors. In particular, it may be applicable to information exchanges and sharing relating to the provision, maintenance and protection of an organization's or nation state's critical infrastructure. It is designed to support the creation of trust when exchanging and sharing sensitive information, thereby encouraging the international growth of information sharing communities.
ISO/IEC 27014:2020 Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection — Governance of information security	This document provides guidance on concepts, objectives and processes for the governance of information security, by which organizations can evaluate, direct, monitor and communicate the information security-related processes within the organization.
ISO/IEC 27018:2019 Information technology - security techniques - Code of practice for protection of personally identifiable information (PII) in public clouds acting as PII processors	ISO/IEC 27018:2019. This document establishes commonly accepted control objectives, controls and guidelines for implementing measures to protect Personally Identifiable Information (PII) in line with the privacy principles in ISO/IEC 29100 for the public cloud computing environment.
ISO 27799:2016 Health informatics — Information security management in health using ISO/IEC 27002	ISO 27799:2016 gives guidelines for organizational information security standards and information security management practices including the selection, implementation and management of controls taking into consideration the organization's information security risk environment(s) By implementing ISO 27799:2016, healthcare organizations and other custodians of health information will be able to ensure a minimum requisite level of security that is appropriate to their organization's circumstances and that will maintain the confidentiality, integrity and availability of personal health information in their care.

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ISO 22325:2016 Security and resilience - Emergency management - Guidelines for capability assessment	ISO 22325:2016 provides guidelines for an organization in assessing its emergency management capability. It includes · an assessment model with a hierarchy of four levels;; · eight indicators;· an assessment process, explaining how to plan, collect, analyse and report.
ISO 22326:2018 Security and resilience - Emergency management - Guidelines for monitoring facilities with identified hazards	ISO 22326:2018. This document gives guidelines for monitoring hazards within a facility as a part of an overall emergency management and continuity programme by establishing the process for hazard monitoring at facilities with identified hazards.
ISO 19941:2017 Information Technology - Cloud Computing - Interoperability and portability	ISO/IEC 19941:2017 specifies cloud computing interoperability and portability types, the relationship and interactions between these two cross-cutting aspects of cloud computing and common terminology and concepts used to discuss interoperability and portability, particularly relating to cloud services.
ISO 21110:2019 Information and documentation - Emergency preparedness and response	ISO 21110:2019 provides a context for emergency planning, response and recovery for all types of an archive, library or museum collections in light of other existing plans. It provides responders and other stakeholders with an outline for planning, responding and recovering. This document does not address the causes of a critical event, but the consequences and wider impacts. This document outlines a cycle for developing, exercising and reviewing a plan, and how to present a plan. It aims to encourage responders to develop their capabilities in emergency preparedness and touches on some elements of response and recovery, where relevant, by highlighting indicators of good practice.
ISO 8201:2017 Alarm systems - Audible emergency evacuation signal - Requirements	ISO 8201:2017 specifies the requirements for an audible emergency evacuation signal intended to indicate without ambiguity, to all persons within the reception area of the signal, that an emergency situation (fire, gas leaks, explosion, nuclear radiation, etc.) requires immediate evacuation.
ISO 22395:2018 Security and resilience - Community resilience - Guidelines for supporting vulnerable persons in an emergency	ISO 22395:2018 This document gives guidelines for organizations to identify, involve, communicate with and support individuals who are the most vulnerable to natural and human-induced (both intentional and unintentional) emergencies. It also includes guidelines for continually improving the provision of support to vulnerable persons in an emergency.
ISO 22397:2014 Societal security — Guidelines for establishing partnering arrangements	ISO 22397:2014 provides guidelines for establishing partnering arrangements among organizations to manage multiple relationships for events impacting on societal security. It incorporates principles and describes the process for planning, developing, implementing and reviewing partnering arrangements.
ISO 22316:2017 Security and resilience — Organizational resilience — Principles and attributes	ISO 22316:2017 provides guidance to enhance organizational resilience for any size or type of organization. It is not specific to any industry or sector. ISO 22316:2017 can be applied throughout the life of an organization.
ISO 22392:2020 Security and resilience — Community resilience — Guidelines for conducting peer reviews	ISO 22392:2020 This document gives guidelines for organizations to design, organize, conduct, receive feedback from and learn from a peer review of their disaster risk reduction (DRR) policies and practices. It is also applicable to other community resilience activities. It is intended for use by organizations with the responsibility for, or involvement in, managing such activities including policy and preparedness, response and recovery operations, and designing preventative measures (e.g. for the effects of environmental changes such as those from climate change)

Document Definition	Introduction/Scope
ISO/TS 22393:2021 Security and resilience — Community resilience — Guidelines for planning recovery and renewal	ISO/TS 22393:2021 This document gives guidance on how to develop recovery plans and renewal strategies from a major emergency, disaster or crisis (such as the COVID-19 pandemic). It provides guidelines on how to identify the short-term, transactional activities needed to reflect and learn, review preparedness of parts of the system impacted by the crisis, and reinstate operations to build preparedness. It also distinguishes a longer-term perspective of recovery, called “renewal”. In describing renewal, the document provides guidelines on how to identify visionary initiatives to address the strategic impacts and opportunities that have been exposed by the crisis and need to be addressed through transformational, ambitious initiatives. Recovery plans enhance preparedness following a crisis and renewal strategies enhance resilience. The guidelines cover how, in both recovery and renewal, there is a need to identify scalable activity on people, places, processes, power and partners.
IEC 63152:2020 Smart cities-cityservice continuity against disasters - the role of the electrical supply	IEC 63152:2020 establishes concepts and gives guidelines to help sustain a variety of city services on the occasion of a disaster from the perspective of providing electricity. It outlines the basic concepts on how multiple city services can cooperate and continue by electricity continuity plan(s) and electricity continuity system(s). It also specifies methods and means to establish these
IEC/UNE EN 61508-1:2010 Functional safety of electrical/electronic/programmable electronic safety-related systems -- Part 1: General requirements	IEC 61508-1:2010 covers those aspects to be considered when electrical/electronic/programmable electronic (E/E/PE) systems are used to carry out safety functions. A major objective of this standard is to facilitate the development of product and application sector international standards by the technical committees responsible for the product or application sector. This will allow all the relevant factors, associated with the product or application, to be fully taken into account and thereby meet the specific needs of users of the product and the application sector. A second objective of this standard is to enable the development of E/E/PE safety-related systems where product or application sector international standards do not exist
IEC/UNE EN 61508-2:2010 Part 2: Requirements for electrical/electronic/programmable electronic safety-related systems	IEC 61508-2:2010 applies to any safety-related system, as defined by IEC 61508-1.
IEC/UNE EN 61508-3:2010 Part 3: Software requirements	IEC 61508-3:2010 applies to any software forming part of a safety-related system or used to develop a safety-related system within the scope of IEC 61508-1 and IEC 61508-2; provides specific requirements applicable to support tools used to develop and configure a safety-related system within the scope of IEC 61508-1 and IEC 61508-2; requires that the software safety functions and software systematic capability are specified; establishes requirements for safety lifecycle phases and activities which shall be applied during the design and development of the safety-related software.
IEC/UNE EN 61508-4:2010 Part 4: Definitions and abbreviations	IEC 61508-4:2010 contains the definitions and explanation of terms that are used in parts 1 to 7 of the IEC 61508 series of standards.
IEC/UNE EN 61508-5:2010 Part 5: Examples of methods for the determination of safety integrity levels	IEC 61508-5:2010 provides information on the underlying concepts of risk and the relationship of risk to safety integrity; a number of methods that will enable the safety integrity levels for the E/E/PE safety-related systems to be determined.

Document Definition	Introduction/Scope
IEC/UNE EN 61508- 6:2010 Part 6: Guidelines on the application of IEC 61508-2 and IEC 61508-3	International Standard IEC 61508-6 has been prepared by subcommittee 65A: System aspects, of IEC technical committee 65: Industrial-process measurement, control and automation. This part of IEC 61508 contains information and guidelines on IEC 61508-2 and IEC 61508-3.
IEC/UNE EN 61508-7:2010 Part 7: Overview of techniques and measures	IEC 61508-7:2010 contains an overview of various safety techniques and measures relevant to IEC 61508-2 and IEC 61508-3. The references should be considered as basic references to methods and tools or as examples, and may not represent the state of the art. This edition constitutes a technical revision. It has been subject to a thorough review and incorporates many comments received at the various revision stages
UNE 179002:2018. Health services. Quality management system for health care transport organization.	This rule is mandatory for those entities that carry out medical transport by road, whether public or private. One of the requirements to obtain authorization is the obligation to be certified in quality standards such as ISO 9001 and UNE 179002.

Table 1 - International Standards

In the next list, for the same analysis, all the Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) that it has been possible to compile have been included, to later evaluate them for the 4 use cases (end users) and produce a map of the operational processes for each one of them.

The operational procedures have been collected by the different members of the consortium and analyzed internally by their owners. The operational procedures represent the heterogeneity of procedures, legal requirements, instructions, manuals and other documents that with different denominations seek to generate standardized operations for their resources in terms of emergency management. Due to the internal authorship of the operating procedures, with the consequent overcoming of obstacles related to communication policy, use of a different language, sensitive information and liability policies, the study of gaps and opportunities has been carried out by the owners of such procedures.

Use Case	Document Definition	Introduction/Scope
UC1	PLANO NACIONAL DE EMERGÊNCIA DE PROTEÇÃO CIVIL	The National Civil Protection Emergency Plan (hereinafter referred to as PNEPC or simply the Plan) is an instrument to support civil protection operations in the event of imminence or occurrence of a serious accident or catastrophe in mainland Portugal, with a view to enabling the direction of the actions to be developed, the technical and operational coordination of the means to be committed and the adequacy of the exceptional measures to be adopted. In accordance with what is defined in the Civil Protection Basic Law, this National Plan, as to the geographic area of coverage.

Use Case	Document Definition	Introduction/Scope
UC1	Plan estatal general de emergencias de protección civil - PLEGEM	Contains the organisational and functional framework, the mechanisms for resource mobilisation and the and the coordination scheme of the Public Administrations involved in Public Administrations intervening in civil protection emergencies of national emergencies of national interest, in which it establishes the direction and coordination of the National Civil Protection System by its central bodies.
UC1	PROTOCOLO entre el Reino de España y la República Portuguesa sobre Cooperación Técnica y Asistencia Mutua en materia de Protección Civil, hecho en Evora el 9 de marzo de 1992.	"ARTICLE 1 Object and scope of application 1. The Contracting Parties shall prepare and execute, by mutual agreement, joint or coordinated actions within the framework of scientific and technical cooperation project programs in the field of Civil Protection.
UC4	UAS STANDARD OPERATING PROCEDURES - FLIGHT OPERATIONS	The standard operational procedures will serve as a guide for flight operations planning and execution. The operational procedures document best practices and internal processes for safe and effective flight operations. This includes roles and responsibilities, mission phases, and emergency procedures
UC2	Methodological instruction which establishes a system of mutual communication when addressing the consequences of MCI	The purpose of this document is to establish a system of mutual communication between involved organizations in solving the consequences of an incident. Mutual communication between the submitters of information is triggered in MCI in which there was a serious threat to health or immediate threat to lives of three or more persons, or in a situation of direct threat to lives and health of a larger number of persons, or in the event of a threat to public health. Information flow is described, Operation center decides about the level of incident (BRAVO to DELTA), Operation center also reports the extent of MCI to the Ministry of Health.
UC2	PRO 22 - Management, spheres of action, responsibilities, operational strategies, information and decision-making flows, use of resources, victim management and collaboration	Managing a disaster that affects a large part of the territory and population to ensure the rescue and relief of victims. Suitable and strategic procedures are outlined directly and in cooperation with other agencies.

Use Case	Document Definition	Introduction/Scope
UC2	IOP 34 - Crossborder MCI	Operational indications to meet the demand for vehicols, with team's mobilisation. Survey of availability in hospitals. Communication with Civil Protection. Activation of PMA and stock lots.
UC2	Decree of the Ministry of Health of SR, establishing details of the emergency medical service	Spatial, material, technical and personnel equipment of operating call center of the Emergency medical service and station of the Emergency medical service
UC2	Methodological and tactical procedures of intervention execution	These procedures contain methodoligical sheet with characteristics of an action, tasks and activity procedures, expected peculiarities (declaring an alarm to the fire unit, departure of the fire unit, transport to the siteof an incident, arrival to the site of an incident, rescuing people, handling over the siteof an incident, leavind the site of an incident, intervention with the presence of dangerous substances, etc.)
UC1	Additional protocol on mutual aid in case of forest fires (Spain Portugal)	The purpose of this Protocol is to establish the conditions and procedures for the provision of assistance or relief and the requirements for the provision of means in the event of an emergency due to forest fires in border areas between Spain and Portugal
UC1	Real Decreto 524/2023, de 20 de junio, por el que se aprueba la Norma Básica de Protección Civil.	The purpose of the Basic Civil Protection Standard is to provide civil protection planning with the necessary cohesion that guarantees the integrated operation of the National Civil Protection System.
UC1	PLANO NACIONAL DE DEFESA DA FLORESTA CONTRA INCÊNDIOS	The serious fires that have occurred in Portugal in recent years have led the Government to conclude that it is necessary to deal with this problem in an objective and uncomplicated way and to prepare the country, as well as its structures linked to the prevention and protection of the forest, to higher levels. of potential risk.
UC3	DISASTER PROTECTION ACT	This Act shall settle providing the protection of the life and health of the population, the conservation of the environment and the property in case of disasters. This Act shall settle providing the protection of the life and health of the population, the

Use Case	Document Definition	Introduction/Scope
		conservation of the environment and the property in case of disasters.
UC3	MINISTRY OF THE INTERIOR ACT	<p>Prom. SG. 53/27 Jun 2014. Section V. Provision of Fire Safety and Protection in Fires, Disasters and Emergencies Section V "a".</p> <p>Art. 17. (1) The activities of providing fire safety and protection in fires, disasters and emergencies shall be carried out by the authorities of fire safety and protection of the population under the conditions and procedure of this act.</p> <p>Section VI. Enabling access of citizens to the emergency services through the National Emergency Calls System with SEN 112 (new - SG 14/15)</p>
UC3	Regulations of the Ministry of Interior (Moi) for emergency reaction in case of earthquake.	This document describes the immediate activities thta the duty officers and sructures of gthe General Derectorate "Fire Safety and protection of Population" of the Moi must undertake
UC3	ACT ON THE NATIONAL EMERGENCY SYSTEM WITH A SINGLE EUROPEAN CALL NUMBER 112	Prom. SG. 102/28 Nov 2008. This Act shall regulate the structure and functions of the National Emergency System with a Single European Call Number 112 The National Emergency System with a Single European Call Number 112, the responsibilities for its setting up, maintenance and development, as well as the rights and the obligations of the citizens using the single European emergency call number 112.
UC3	COORDINATING THE STRUCTURES OF THE UNIFIED RESCUE SYSTEM (URS) IN AN EARTHQUAKE	The procedure determines the order for bringing the forces and means from the URS for action during an earthquake and was developed on the basis of Art. 29, para. 2, item 2 of The Disaster Protection Act. The procedure is applied to earthquakes above the 3rd degree on the scale of Medvedev-Sponhoer-Karnik on the territory of the Republic of Bulgaria, where destruction was caused, there are injured people and those who need help.

Use Case	Document Definition	Introduction/Scope
UC3	National Law 4662/20 (OGG27 A 4662/07.02.2020)	National Crisis Management and Risk Management Mechanism, Restructuring of the National Secretariat for Civil Protection, upgrading a system of voluntary policy protection, reorganization of the Fire and other provisions.
UC3	Action Plan Egkelados	General Action Plan for emergency response due to earthquakes
UC3	Action Plan "Dardanos"	General Action Plan for emergency response and short-term management of floods impacts
UC3	"Xenokratis (Ministerial Decision	National General Plan for Civil Protection, aiming at effective response to catastrophic phenomena for the protection of life, health and property of citizens, as well as the protection of the natural environment.
UC2	CENTRAL ALARM PLAN OF THE INTEGRATED RESCUE SYSTEM	The Integrated Rescue System is to be used in preparedness for an arisen emergency event and in case of need to conduct rescue and relief work by two or more components of the Integrated Rescue System.

Table 2 - Standard Operating Procedures

4.2. Analysis and Evaluation

After this first screening and analysis, once it has been carried out, with the selected standards, a GAP analysis has subsequently been carried out, where for each of them the following has been analyzed and related:

- Gap name
- Type of input
- Justification
- ID
- Related Gap
- Opportunity name
- Type of input
- Justification

All these standards have been studied and selected, due to their relevance and/or usefulness for the creation of the harmonized procedure that is intended to be created, due to the specificity of each of them, all of them related to some specific process of the scope of the Project.

For this, the following information have been taken into account:

- Related with other International Standards and/or Certifications (referenced inside of ISO)
- Is it of value for a unified cross-border emergency management framework?
- Is it easily accessible and consultable within the organisation?
- Used in Task/Deliverable in other Valkyries WP
- Evaluation ISO
- ISO implemented? / Certificated?
- Recognised-Used by partner / country? (ISO)
- Is this ISO/EN necessary to one or more Use Case?
- Identify GAP and OPPs

For the analysis of the SOPs, the collection of information by the Valkyries components for the initial evaluation of these documents has been carried out in the same way.

- Ability to form part of a common reference framework for the comprehensive management of cross-border emergencies
- Potential impact on emergency management
- Probability of application. Ease of transposition to current state.
- Document shared with third parties
- Document created under international standard
- Document with all information needed to build and unified SOP

4.3. Preparation of Process Maps

Disasters, whether caused by natural or human-induced causes, have always highlighted the importance of proper incident management that results in minimising loss of life, injury, impact on infrastructure and increasing the resilience of societies.

In the context of the VALKYRIES H2020 project, health, communications and infrastructure will be addressed. Incident management has been a matter of national, regional and local scope, with management generally being the responsibility of a single organisation or entity. Today, there is a need for an international and cross-sectoral approach. This translates into the need to create a framework that responds to the relationships between governments, organisations and their societies.

It is necessary to respond to the need for adequate assistance between organisations, regions and/or borders during incident management, taking into account technical, resource, cultural and other differences. It is therefore necessary to involve multiple representatives of the VALKYRIES use cases in a single approach to create a framework for cross-border incident management.

4.3.1. Incident management process

According to ISO 22320 the management of an incident involves a combination of facilities, equipment, personnel, organisational structure, procedures and communications.

It should always be borne in mind that the framework established by an international standardisation standard allows for equal comparison between the activities carried out by any type of organisation. This reference framework, by its nature, has the same concept.

The unified framework for cross-border incident management must be developed on the basis of a set of principles. These principles must be known, respected and implemented by any organisation wishing to operate within this framework.

Initially, these general principles consist of the following:

- Ethical values: Incident management must first and foremost preserve the life and dignity of people.
- Collaborative work: Recognition of the participation and responsibilities of the different organisations and their resources.
- Threat and risk management: a continuous analysis of the risks and the different nature of the threats that can generate crises with an impact on societies and environments must be contemplated.
- Preparedness: Incident management requires a prior stage of preparation. This will affect all resources and personnel involved, regardless of their nature (organisations, sectors, governments).
- Information sharing: Recognition of the need to share sensitive and necessary information for all stages of impact management.
- Safety: The safety of health and rescue resources must be preserved.
- Flexibility: The necessary capacity to adapt to the dynamic events that occur during the incident is recognised in order to be reactive and proactive in any situation.
- Cultural factors: Recognition of cultural diversity and adaptation of the response and actions according to social and cultural diversity.

The incident management process ranges from the activation of the emergency to the reception of the victims in a health care facility. The process encompasses all information reception and information sharing to assess the scenario and identify possible contingencies in order to develop the most appropriate response.

This shared information should be used for decision making among all organisations involved and these decisions should be accepted. The process is to be applied at any level of responsibility.

Figure 1 - Incident management process

At a general level, emergency plans are generated for a certain type of emergencies, within the Valkyries project different use cases are developed, which represent different scenarios or emergency plans. The emergency is managed by plans that have all the necessary information and mark which resources are associated, and how decisions are made. Within the plans, other documents can be developed, such as operational procedures for the detailed development of specific activities within the emergency management.

The development of the plan must include sufficient information to manage any risk that may arise during the course of the emergency, with the capacity to make decisions in the short and long term. To this end, it is important to know the resources, tools, procedures and technologies.

The management of plans requires, as standard, a structure composed of: decision-making, planning, operations, logistics and finance. This structure is required at all levels at which emergency management is structured. Thus, the analysis of two factors, the context of the organisation developing the plan and the nature of the emergency, will result in different structures, but always maintaining a standard pattern that would enable the coordination of activities and resources.

Some of the tasks involved in cross-border emergency management, and according to Annex C of ISO 22320: Public information, expert consultation, Operational picture.

4.3.2. Process Map for international standards in cross border emergency

Figure 2 - International Standards Diagram

SUB-PROCESS	Document Definition
GENERAL	ISO 22320:2018 Security and resilience - Emergency management - Guidelines for incident management
PRIOR / PREPARATION	ISO 22322:2015 Security and resilience - Emergency management - Guidelines for public warnings
RESOURCES	ISO 22324:2015 Security and resilience - Emergency management - Guidelines for colour-coded alerts
OPERATING	ISO/TR 22351:2015 Societal Security - Emergency Management - Message structure for exchange of information (EMSI - Emergency Management Shared Information)
PRIOR / PREPARATION	ISO 22398:2013 Societal security — Guidelines for exercises
GENERAL	ISO 22300:2021 Security and resilience — Vocabulary
RESOURCES	UNE 179002:2018 Health services. Quality management system (QMS) for health care transport organization.

SUB-PROCESS	Document Definition
RESOURCES	UNE-EN 13718-1:2015+A1:2020 Medical vehicles and their equipment - Air ambulances - Part 1: Requirements for medical devices used in air ambulances Medical vehicles and their equipment - Air ambulances - Part 2: Operational and technical requirements for air ambulances
RESOURCES	ISO/IEC 27001:2013. Information Technology - Security Techniques - Information security management systems (ISMS) - Requieriments
GENERAL	ISO 22328:2020-1 Securty and resilience - Emergency management - Guidelines for the implementation of a community-based disaster early warnings system
PRIOR / PREPARATION	UNE-EN ISO 22315:2014 Societal security - Mass evacuation - Guidelines for planning
PRIOR / PREPARATION	ISO 22396:2020 Security and resilience — Community resilience — Guidelines for information exchange between organizations
PRIOR / PREPARATION	ISO 22319:2017 Security and resilience - Community resilience - Guidelines for planning the involvement of spontaneous volunteers
GENERAL	ISO 9001:2015 Quality management systems — Requirements
RESOURCES	ISO 19136:2007 / ISO 19136-1:2020 Geographic information — Geography Markup Language (GML) — Part 1: Fundamentals
RESOURCES	ISO 19128:2005 Geographic information — Web map server interface (WMS)
RESOURCES	ISO 19142:2010 Geographic information — Web Feature Service (WFS)
RESOURCES	CEN ISO/TS 19139:2009 / ISO/TS 19139-1:2019 Geographic information — XML schema implementation — Part 1: Encoding rules
RESOURCES	EN 1789:2020 Medical vehicles and their equipment - Road ambulances
RESOURCES	EN 1846-1:2011 Firefighting and rescue service vehicles - Part 1: Nomenclature and designation
RESOURCES	EN 1846-2:2009+A1:2013 Firefighting and rescue service vehicles - Part 2: Common requirements - Safety and performance
RESOURCES	EN 1846-3:2013 Firefighting and rescue service vehicles - Part 3: Permanently installed equipment - Safety and performance
RESOURCES	EN 13976-2:2018 Rescue systems - Transportation of incubators - Part 2: System requirements
RESOURCES	EN 1865-1:2010+A1:2015 Patient handling equipment used in road ambulances - Part 1: General stretcher systems and patient handling equipment

SUB-PROCESS	Document Definition
RESOURCES	EN 1865-2:2010+A1:2015 Patient handling equipment used in road ambulances - Part 2: Power assisted stretcher
RESOURCES	EN 1865-3:2012+A1:2015 Patient handling equipment used in road ambulances - Part 3: Heavy duty stretcher
RESOURCES	EN 1865-4:2012 Patient handling equipment used in road ambulances - Part 4: Foldable patient transfer chair
RESOURCES	EN 1865-5:2012 Patient handling equipment used in road ambulances - Part 5: Stretcher support
RESOURCES	ISO 13606-1:2019 Health informatics — Electronic health record communication — Part 1: Reference model
GENERAL	ISO 31073:2022(en) Risk management — Vocabulary. 2022
GENERAL	BS EN 17173:2020 European CBRNE glossary
OPERATING	ISO 22327:2018 Security and resilience — Emergency management — Guidelines for implementation of a community-based landslide early warning system
OPERATING	ISO/DIS 22328-2 Security and resilience — Emergency management — Part 2: Guidelines for the implementation of a community-based landslide early warning system (UNDER DEVELOPMENT)
OPERATING	ISO/FDIS 22328-3 Security and resilience — Emergency management — Part 3: Guidelines for the implementation of a community-based tsunami early warning system (UNDER DEVELOPMENT)
PRIOR / PREPARATION	ISO 22329:2021 Security and resilience — Emergency management — Guidelines for the use of social media in emergencies
GENERAL	ISO/IEC 27000:2018 Information Technology - Security techniques - Information security management systems - Overview and vocabulary
RESOURCES	ISO/IEC/IEEE 15939:2017 Systems and software engineering — Measurement process
RESOURCES	ISO/IEC 27002:2022 Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection — Information security controls
RESOURCES	ISO/IEC 27010:2015 Information technology - security techniques - Information security management for inter-sector and inter-organizational communications
RESOURCES	ISO/IEC 27014:2020 Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection — Governance of information security

SUB-PROCESS	Document Definition
RESOURCES	ISO/IEC 27018:2019 Information technology - security techniques - Code of practice for protection of personally identifiable information (PII) in public clouds acting as PII processors
RESOURCES	ISO 27799:2016 Health informatics — Information security management in health using ISO/IEC 27002
OPERATING	ISO 22325:2016 Security and resilience - Emergency management - Guidelines for capability assessment
PRIOR / PREPARATION	ISO 22326:2018 Security and resilience - Emergency management - Guidelines for monitoring facilities with identified hazards
PRIOR / PREPARATION	ISO 19941:2017 Information Technology - Cloud Computing - Interoperability and portability
OPERATING	ISO 21110:2019 Information and documentation - Emergency preparedness and response
RESOURCES	ISO 8201:2017 Alarm systems - Audible emergency evacuation signal - Requirements
OPERATING	ISO 22395:2018 Security and resilience - Community resilience - Guidelines for supporting vulnerable persons in an emergency
OPERATING	ISO 22397:2014 Societal security — Guidelines for establishing partnering arrangements
OPERATING	ISO 22316:2017 Security and resilience — Organizational resilience — Principles and attributes
OPERATING	ISO 22392:2020 Security and resilience — Community resilience — Guidelines for conducting peer reviews
PRIOR / PREPARATION	ISO/TS 22393:2021 Security and resilience — Community resilience — Guidelines for planning recovery and renewal
RESOURCES	IEC 63152:2020 Smart cities-cityservice continuity against disasters - the role of the electrical supply
RESOURCES	IEC/UNE EN 61508-1:2010 Functional safety of electrical/electronic/programmable electronic safety-related systems -- Part 1: General requirements
RESOURCES	IEC/UNE EN 61508-2:2010 Part 2: Requirements for electrical/electronic/programmable electronic safety-related systems
RESOURCES	IEC/UNE EN 61508-3:2010 Part 3: Software requirements
GENERAL	IEC/UNE EN 61508-4:2010 Part 4: Definitions and abbreviations

SUB-PROCESS	Document Definition
PRIOR / PREPARATION	IEC/UNE EN 61508-5:2010 Part 5: Examples of methods for the determination of safety integrity levels
OPERATING	IEC/UNE EN 61508- 6:2010 Part 6: Guidelines on the application of IEC 61508-2 and IEC 61508-3
OPERATING	IEC/UNE EN 61508-7:2010 Part 7: Overview of techniques and measures
RESOURCES	UNE 179002:2018 . Health services. Quality management system for health care transport organization.
	Specifications for Digital Scenarios for Crisis Management Exercises

Table 3 - Process Diagram - International Standards

4.3.3. Process Map for Standard Operating Procedures in cross border emergency

Operational procedures are deployed within the Operations phase in the process map based on international standards. Operational procedures can have a multitude of origins and needs to be met depending on the nature and risk management of the organisation that generates them. The operational procedures identified are distributed as follows.

Figure 3 - Standard Operating Procedure Diagram

Legislative support / International Reference

These are reference documents whose deployment and adaptation is primarily the responsibility of the country. They correspond to applications of European regulations, international support guides such as INSARAG are also taken into consideration.

National emergency plan

Documents with national scope developed to provide emergency management by public resources and third party support at national level. Inside of this category appear other management documents with the same objective and less scope, like a regional or local scope.

Operational procedures

A document directly related to the operation that provides the necessary and sufficient information to achieve an objective.

Technical instructions

Specialised documentation on a small task. They usually provide brief and technical information.

Technical reference manuals.

Documentation associated with equipment, devices and/or process development with extensive information for deployment and knowledge of an associated public.

Use Case	SUB-PROCESS	Document Definition	Introduction / Scope
UC1	National emergency plan	PLANO NACIONAL DE EMERGÊNCIA DE PROTEÇÃO CIVIL	The National Civil Protection Emergency Plan (hereinafter referred to as PNEPC or simply the Plan) is an instrument to support civil protection operations in the event of imminence or occurrence of a serious accident or catastrophe in mainland Portugal, with a view to enabling the direction of the actions to be developed, the technical and operational coordination of the means to be committed and the adequacy of the exceptional measures to be adopted. In accordance with what is defined in the Civil Protection Basic Law, this National Plan, as to the geographic area of coverage.
UC1	National emergency plan	PLANO MUNICIPAL DE EMERGÊNCIA DE PROTEÇÃO CIVIL DE ÉVORA	Plan prepared for the Municipality of Évora in accordance with the provisions of resolution 25/2008, of 18 July, concerning the criteria and technical standards for the elaboration and operation of civil protection emergency plans.
UC1	National emergency plan	PLANO MUNICIPAL DE EMERGÊNCIA DE PROTEÇÃO CIVIL DE PORTALEGRE	The Portalegre District Civil Protection Emergency Plan (hereinafter referred to as the Portalegre PDEPC or simply Plan) is a general civil protection emergency plan, intended, under the terms of the law, to deal with most serious accident situations or catastrophe that may develop within the

Use Case	SUB-PROCESS	Document Definition	Introduction / Scope
			territorial and administrative scope of the district of Portalegre.
UC1	Legislative support / International Reference.	DECRETO 52/2010, de 5 de marzo, por el que se aprueba el Plan de Lucha contra Incendios Forestales de la Comunidad Autónoma de Extremadura (Plan INFOEX).	The Plan for the Fight against Forest Fires of the Autonomous Community of Extremadura (INFOEX Plan) aims to establish the measures for the detection and extinction of forest fires and the resolution of the situations that derive from them. To this end, the times of danger are defined, the organization and procedures for action of the means and services whose ownership corresponds to the Junta de Extremadura and those from other Public Administrations and Entities and Organizations of a public or private nature are established. . Likewise, uses and activities likely to cause forest fires and sanctions for actions contrary to the provisions regarding forest fires are regulated.
UC1	Legislative support / International Reference.	PROTOCOLO entre el Reino de España y la República Portuguesa sobre Cooperación Técnica y Asistencia Mutua en materia de Protección Civil, hecho en Evora el 9 de marzo de 1992.	The Contracting Parties shall prepare and execute, by mutual agreement, joint or coordinated actions within the framework of scientific and technical cooperation project programs in the field of Civil Protection.
UC1	Operational procedures	PR-GNR-02 PROTOCOLO DE ACTUACIÓN EN EMERGENCIAS	This standard is applicable at the Marqués de Valdecilla Research Institute (IDIVAL). (SPAIN). Organize the actions of the center staff in an emergency situation to minimize the risks and their consequences
UC4	Technical reference manuals.	UAS STANDARD OPERATING PROCEDURES - FLIGHT OPERATIONS	UAS STANDARD OPERATING PROCEDURES - FLIGHT OPERATIONS
UC1	Operational procedures	Mass Casualty Incidents and Triage	Incidents with Multiple Victims and Triage. The Incident with Multiple Victims is characterized by presenting in its beginnings a disproportion between resources and needs, and therefore requires an extraordinary response, in order to optimize existing resources, preserving a

Use Case	SUB-PROCESS	Document Definition	Introduction / Scope
			response capacity for the rest of events.
UC1	Operational procedures	Complex Incident Procedure. PIC code	Establishes a framework for action in complex accidents in the municipal sphere of the City of Madrid in which the coordinated action of at least three municipal services is necessary: MUNICIPAL POLICE, FIREFIGHTERS, SAMUR-PC and SAMUR SOCIAL.
UC2	Operational procedures	Methodological instruction which establishes a system of mutual communication when addressing the consequences of MCI	The purpose of this document is to establish a system of mutual communication between involved organizations in solving the consequences of an incident. Mutual communication between the submitters of information is triggered in MCI in which there was a serious threat to health or immediate threat to lives of three or more persons, or in a situation of direct threat to lives and health of a larger number of persons, or in the event of a threat to public health. Information flow is described, Operation center decides about the level of incident (BRAVO to DELTA), Operation center also reports the extent of MCI to the Ministry of Health.
UC2	Operational procedures	PRO 22 - Management, spheres of action, responsibilities, operational strategies, information and decision-making flows, use of resources, victim management and collaboration	Managing a disaster that affects a large part of the territory and population to ensure the rescue and relief of victims. Suitable and strategic procedures are outlined directly and in cooperation with other agencies.
UC2	Operational procedures	IOP 34 - Crossborder MCI	Operational indications to meet the demand for vehicols, with team's mobilisation. Survey of availability in hospitals. Communication with Civil Protection. Activation of PMA and stock lots.

Use Case	SUB-PROCESS	Document Definition	Introduction / Scope
UC2	Operational procedures	IOP 35 - USAR Activation	Actions in case of Urban and Source activation. Operational indications and availability of resources. Scouting activities
UC2	Legislative support / International Reference	Decree of the Ministry of Health of SR, establishing details of the emergency medical service	Spatial, material, technical and personnel equipment of operating call center of the Emergency medical service and station of the Emergency medical service
UC2	Operational procedures	Methodological and tactical procedures of intervention execution	These procedures contain methodological sheet with characteristics of an action, tasks and activity procedures, expected peculiarities (declaring an alarm to the fire unit, departure of the fire unit, transport to the site of an incident, arrival to the site of an incident, rescuing people, handling over the site of an incident, leaving the site of an incident, intervention with the presence of dangerous substances, etc.)
UC1	Legislative support / International Reference	Additional protocol on mutual aid in case of forest fires (Spain Portugal)	The purpose of this Protocol is to establish the conditions and procedures for the provision of assistance or relief and the requirements for the provision of means in the event of an emergency due to forest fires in border areas between Spain and Portugal
UC1	Operational procedures	Plan INFOEX	The purpose of the Plan for the Fight against Forest Fires of the Autonomous Community of Extremadura (INFOEX Plan) is to establish the measures for the detection and extinction of forest fires and the resolution of situations that derive from them.
UC1	Legislative support / International Reference	Plan PLATERCAEX	PLATERCAEX is the Territorial Civil Protection Plan of the Autonomous Community of Extremadura that is prepared to comply with the effective application of the Basic Civil

Use Case	SUB-PROCESS	Document Definition	Introduction / Scope
			Protection Standard approved by ROYAL DECREE 407/1992, of April 24, which constitutes the legal framework that determines the entire system of preparation and response to situations of serious collective risk, public calamity or catastrophe, whose main purpose is to prevent the loss of human lives and material goods in different emergency situations.
UC1	Legislative support / International Reference	Real Decreto 524/2023, de 20 de junio, por el que se aprueba la Norma Básica de Protección Civil.	The purpose of the Basic Civil Protection Standard is to provide civil protection planning with the necessary cohesion that guarantees the integrated operation of the National Civil Protection System.
UC1	Operational procedures	PLANO NACIONAL DE DEFESA DA FLORESTA CONTRA INCÊNDIOS	The serious fires that have occurred in Portugal in recent years have led the Government to conclude that it is necessary to deal with this problem in an objective and uncomplicated way and to prepare the country, as well as its structures linked to the prevention and protection of the forest, to higher levels of potential risk.
UC3	Legislative support / International Reference	DISASTER PROTECTION ACT	This Act shall settle providing the protection of the life and health of the population, the conservation of the environment and the property in case of disasters. This Act shall settle providing the protection of the life and health of the population, the conservation of the environment and the property in case of disasters.
UC3	Legislative support / International Reference	MINISTRY OF THE INTERIOR ACT	Prom. SG. 53/27 Jun 2014. Section V. Provision of Fire Safety and Protection in Fires, Disasters and Emergencies Section V "a". Art. 17. (1) The activities of providing fire safety and protection in fires, disasters and emergencies shall be

Use Case	SUB-PROCESS	Document Definition	Introduction / Scope
			<p>carried out by the authorities of fire safety and protection of the population under the conditions and procedure of this act.</p> <p>Section VI. Enabling access of citizens to the emergency services through the National Emergency Calls System with SEN 112 (new - SG 14/15)</p>
UC3	Legislative support / International Reference	Regulations of the Ministry of Interior (Mol) for emergency reaction in case of earthquake.	This document describes the immediate activities that the duty officers and structures of the General Directorate "Fire Safety and protection of Population" of the Mol must undertake
UC3	Legislative support / International Reference	ACT ON THE NATIONAL EMERGENCY SYSTEM WITH A SINGLE EUROPEAN CALL NUMBER 112	Prom. SG. 102/28 Nov 2008. This Act shall regulate the structure and functions of the National Emergency System with a Single European Call Number 112. The National Emergency System with a Single European Call Number 112, the responsibilities for its setting up, maintenance and development, as well as the rights and the obligations of the citizens using the single European emergency call number 112.
UC3	Legislative support / International Reference	COORDINATING THE STRUCTURES OF THE UNIFIED RESCUE SYSTEM (URS) IN AN EARTHQUAKE	<p>The procedure determines the order for bringing the forces and means from the URS for action during an earthquake and was developed on the basis of Art. 29, para. 2, item 2 of The Disaster Protection Act. The procedure is applied to earthquakes above the 3rd degree on the scale of Medvedev-Sponhoer-Karnik on the territory of the Republic of Bulgaria, where destruction was caused, there are injured people and those who need help.</p>
UC3	Legislative support / International Reference	National Law 4662/20 (OGG27 A 4662/07.02.2020)	National Crisis Management and Risk Management Mechanism, Restructuring of the National Secretariat for Civil Protection,

Use Case	SUB-PROCESS	Document Definition	Introduction / Scope
			upgrading a system of voluntary policy protection, reorganization of the Fire and other provisions.
UC3	National emergency plan	Action Plan Egkelados	General Action Plan for emergency response due to earthquakes
UC3	National emergency plan	Action Plan "Dardanos"	General Action Plan for emergency response and short-term management of floods impacts
UC3	Legislative support / International Reference	INSARAG GUIDELINES 2020	The INSARAG Guidelines provides a methodology to guide countries affected by a sudden-onset disaster causing large-scale structural collapse, as well as international USAR Teams responding in the affected country
UC3	National emergency plan	Xenokratis (Ministerial Decision 1299/2003–Government Gazette 423 B/10-04-2003)	National General Plan for Civil Protection, aiming at effective response to catastrophic phenomena for the protection of life, health and property of citizens, as well as the protection of the natural environment.
UC2	National emergency plan	CENTRAL ALARM PLAN OF THE INTEGRATED RESCUE SYSTEM	The Integrated Rescue System is to be used in preparedness for an arisen emergency event and in case of need to conduct rescue and relief work by two or more components of the Integrated Rescue System.
UC1	Operational procedures	Manual para el manejo de los incidentes de múltiples víctimas en la urgencia extrahospitalaria. Manual for the management of incidents involving multiple victims in extrahospital emergencies	This reference work tries to provide information on health care in multi-victim accidents based on the experience and training of the participants in the work.
UC1	National emergency plan	Plan estatal general de emergencias de protección civil - PLEGEM	Contains the organisational and functional framework, the mechanisms for resource mobilisation and the and the coordination scheme of the Public

Use Case	SUB-PROCESS	Document Definition	Introduction / Scope
			Administrations involved in Public Administrations intervening in civil protection emergencies of national emergencies of national interest, in which it establishes the direction and coordination of the National Civil Protection System by its central bodies.

Table 4 - Process Diagram - Standard Operating Procedure

4.4. Gap and Opportunity Analysis

A gap analysis (or needs analysis) is a process used to compare actual performance with desired performance. The “gap” is understood as the space between where your business is currently and where you would like it to be.

A gap analysis can help to:

- Brainstorm possible strategies. Strategic teams can use a gap analysis to develop potential action plans that they can implement to achieve their goals.
- Identify weak points. If the expected results have not been obtained, a gap analysis can help identify the cause of certain performance gaps.
- Measure current resources. A gap analysis can help you identify specifically how a task was performed and how resources were allocated so they can be used more efficiently in the future.

A gap analysis can be performed:

- At the strategic level: To compare the condition or level of the business with that of the industry standards.
- At the Operational level: To compare the current state or performance with what you have desired.

A GAP analysis is performed in four phases:

- Analyze the current situation.
- Define the desirable situation.
- Determine the gap.
- Fix the gap.

Phase 3 (4.4.1.) is described below, where the possible gaps found after the analysis of the standards detected have been identified and analyzed, to subsequently detect possible opportunities for their solution (phase 4: 4.4.2).

4.4.1. Gap Analysis

To carry out phase 2, GAPS have been identified for each of the standards identified above:

<p>G3.1: Non-uniform roll-out of road ambulance requirements</p> <p>UNE 179002:2018 Health services. Quality management system (QMS) for the organisation of medical transport.</p>
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The technical characteristics, medical equipment and staffing of ambulances must be regulated.

In order to establish and promote safety and clarity, as well as having the necessary equipment and personnel at the time of the emergency, road ambulances should have a uniformity to avoid confusion, both for other services and for possible patients or victims, in order to keep all equipment operational, make correct use of it and optimise time.

G3.2: Armonization of community-based disaster early warning system (EWS)

ISO 22328:2020-1 Security and resilience - Emergency management - Guidelines for the implementation of a community-based disaster early warnings system

Existence of various solutions that respond to specific countries needs generate potential discrepancies regarding the response at the border.

The existence of different solutions that respond to the specific needs of each country creates potential discrepancies in the response at the border.

Each country manages through various tools, such as risk management, its response to different emergencies. It is in the diversity of tools and their results that the differences in the response of the different organisations and entities are found.

G3.3: Misunderstandings relative to different vocabulary meanings

ISO 31073:2022(en) Risk management — Vocabulary. 2022

Use of similar concepts not usually used for all partners

It is important that all the concepts and terminology used, both when preparing documentation as well as forms of action, materials, etc., have the same meanings in all cases and for all countries in order to avoid confusion when carrying out any type of intervention.

G3.4: Heterogeneity about simulations and exercises for training skills

ISO 22398:2013 Societal security — Guidelines for exercises

Existing different criteria, procedures and path for making simulations and exercises among differents organizations.

There must be a similarity and uniformity when establishing, planning, carrying out and improving a programme of exercises or rehearsal drills, in which all the countries of the Project should participate, in order to harmonise types of actions before all types of disasters or emergencies, so that, in the event of a disaster or emergency, everyone acts in the same way or methodology. These drills should have an established frequency.

G3.5: Different classes of fire fighting vehicles and road ambulances

EN 1846-1:2011 Firefighting and rescue service vehicles - Part 1: Nomenclature and designation

UNE-EN 1789:2007 on medical transport vehicles by road

Different classes of fire fighting vehicles and road ambulances require the support of different resources.

All fire fighting vehicles (fire engines) must comply with the technical characteristics according to normative, where fire fighting vehicles are classified according to their MASS; (Light, Medium

and Heavy) CATEGORY; (1-Urban, 2-Rural and 3-All Terrain) SEATS (Driver included) and OTHER SPECIFICATIONS such as water tank capacity, pump performance and others, using the most suitable according to the type of emergency.

For ambulances, the application of the standard contributes to the improvement of the quality of the medical service, allowing to reduce the response time in the event of a medical emergency.

G3.6: Access to health information on electronic devices

ISO 13606-1:2019 Health informatics — Electronic health record communication — Part 1: Reference model

Consultation of information in multi-technological electronic devices in a cross-border environment

For victims or unconscious patients or children who are unable to communicate, it is necessary and/or beneficial to know their medical history. It would therefore be essential to establish systems for accessing and communicating medical records electronically, regardless of the area where they are located.

G3.7: Use of channels for early warning communication

ISO 22328:2020-1 Security and resilience - Emergency management - Guidelines for the implementation of a community-based disaster early warnings system

Different categorization of severity with the same event

For the communication of emergencies, they must be categorised by type or severity in order to be able to act according to the type of emergency or severity. Therefore, the communication system must be quick and clear in order to avoid errors and/or confusion for the organisation of all emergency devices and personnel.

G3.8: Non-uniform evacuation protocols

ISO 22315:2014 Societal security - Mass evacuation - Guidelines for planning

Protocols built for scope not optimized for cross-border events

Preparedness for each type of emergency must be established, implemented, monitored, evaluated, reviewed and improved in order to act in the same manner or methodology in the event of a mass evacuation for all identified hazards. It will help meet your obligation to save human life and reduce suffering.

This International Standard does not cover activities to stabilise the affected area after an evacuation, protect property and preserve the environment.

G3.9: Security control of sensitive information

ISO/IEC 27010:2015 Information technology - security techniques - Information security management for inter-sector and inter-organizational communications

Treatment of critical information with international actors and cutting-edge technology

There may be a need to share confidential information security threat information, vulnerabilities and patient/victim incidents or between different organisations in the same or different countries.

The information exchanged is very valuable and sensitive, often restricted to certain organisations. For this reason, the source of information must be protected and remain anonymous.

Information exchanges take place in stressful environments, under intense pressure, leading to the likelihood of problems with information security controls, so common rules for security need to be established.

G3.10: Cloud computing service

ISO 19941:2017 Information Technology - Cloud Computing - Interoperability and portability

Cloud computing service according to the needs and requirements of the different countries and entities.

Cloud computing is a new way of providing information processing services. A cloud computing solution allows users to optimise the allocation and cost of resources associated with their information processing needs. There is no need to invest in infrastructure, but rather to use the infrastructure made available by the service provider, ensuring that there are no situations of lack or excess of resources, and no additional costs associated with such situations.

In a cloud computing environment, information management is virtually in the hands of the customer who contracts the cloud computing services of the customer who contracts the cloud services, who processes it through the Internet by accessing database solutions, e-mail, or any type of application according to their needs their needs.

G3.11: High precision map digitizing

ISO 19128:2005 Geographic information — Web map server interface (WMS)

Layout of alternative routes updated with high precision

In order to establish precise evacuation measures and locations, it is necessary to have routes in difficult or unfamiliar environments, which is why high precision maps of all areas are immediately available, establishing a service that dynamically produces spatially referenced maps from geographic information.

G3.12: Emergency plans for localities

Law 5/2004, of June 24, on the prevention and fight against forest fires in Extremadura.

Lack of development of emergency plans in municipalities that are coordinated with national and collaborative plans in the border environment

The first responders to arrive in emergency areas are those closest to the disaster site, so they are from the nearest municipalities. Emergency plans should be developed that can be communicated or should be known to these municipalities.

G3.13: Procedures for coordination resources Spain-Portugal

Resolution of December 16, 2020, of the Undersecretariat, publishing the Agreement of the Council of Ministers of December 15, 2020, approving the General State Plan for Civil Protection Emergencies.

Bilateral procedure for international assistance not harmonized.

Bilateral relationships between different entities require a robust regulatory framework for shared management. The necessary creation of documentation for different purposes creates a risk of loss of coordination.

Establishment of a common harmonised international emergency protocol, applicable to all countries involved, so that the different types of actions are common.

G3.14: Management of cross-border emergencies do not contemplate all the requirements of the participants

ISO 22320:2018 Security and resilience - Emergency management - Guidelines for incident management

Cross-border emergency management plans do not include a combination of facilities, equipment, personnel, organizational structure, procedures and communications with any country.

Cross-border emergency management plans should provide guidelines for incident management, including principles that convey value and clarify the purpose of emergency management, as well as its basic components, including process and structure, focusing on roles and responsibilities, tasks and resource management and encouraging joint management work and cooperation.

G3.15: Shared decision making interferes with the management of resources that can coordinate joint activities

ISO 22320:2018 Security and resilience - Emergency management - Guidelines for incident management

Slow management and poor efficiency of the units dedicated to cross-border incident resolution tasks

Cross-border emergency management plans should provide guidelines for incident management, including principles that convey value and clarify the purpose of emergency management, as well as its basic components, including process and structure, focusing on roles and responsibilities, tasks and resource management and encouraging joint management work and cooperation.

G3.16: Unique interpretation of each of the participants in the coordinated intervention process for cross-border incident management

ISO 22320:2018 Security and resilience - Emergency management - Guidelines for incident management

Each public or private organization generates an independent procedure to contribute to the participation of the cross-border incident, creating coordination barriers

A multitude of operational procedures with different treatments and needs have been identified. Integrated management of operational procedures at local, regional and/or national/international level is considered interesting to optimise the response.

G3.17: Non-uniform early warning system

ISO 22322:2015 Security and resilience - Emergency management - Guidelines for public warnings

Alert system focused on national framework and their needs

Any type of emergency or incident needs an effective response to save lives, mitigate damage and harm, and there is a need to respond quickly to an ongoing emergency situation. Time to communicate is limited, and often a specific message involving practical action needs to be disseminated to a large group in a simple way. Procedures that deliver the message effectively and elicit the desired response can save lives, protect health and prevent major disruption.

G3.18: Great heterogeneity of technology and requirements to receive the actions of the international alert system

ISO 22322:2015 Security and resilience - Emergency management - Guidelines for public warnings

Difficulty in standardizing technologies and alarm systems at a European level

Protecting people at risk is an important part of emergency response. Public warning allows you to alert your staff and enables people at risk to take safety measures to reduce the impact of incidents. Effective public warning consisting of alerts and notifications can prevent panic reactions and help optimise responses and mitigate impact.

G3.19: Non-uniform treatment of risks identified within the public alarm system

ISO 22322:2015 Security and resilience - Emergency management - Guidelines for public warnings

Non-uniform risks and criteria in multinational and inter-company environments

Effective response to incidents requires structured and pre-planned public warning. Public warning is based on two functions: hazard monitoring and risk dissemination. It is also necessary to establish a mechanism for risk identification, hazard monitoring, decision making and alert dissemination, to evaluate and improve emergency response.

G3.20: Lack of uniformity in the criteria for categorizing signaling and alarm communication associated with the different risks

ISO 22324:2015 Security and resilience - Emergency management - Guidelines for colour-coded alerts

Communication of the non-uniform public alert system for the identified events and citizen response to it.

People at risk from an emergency or accident should be able to get to safety even if they do not fully understand the hazards. Public alerts, through a combination of warnings and advance notifications, allow people at risk to take appropriate and timely action to protect their safety.

Colour-coded alerts are used to notify people at risk of status changes in a hazard continuum to enable them to take appropriate action, thus necessitating the need to unify these colour codes to avoid confusion.

G3.21: Communications structure with limited range

ISO/TR 22351:2015 Societal Security - Emergency Management - Message structure for exchange of information

The communications structure responds to needs and functional characteristics within a specific framework: region, function, etc.; generating a large ecosystem of independent communications.

Clear situational awareness is a key factor for an effective emergency response. The development of an operational picture is based on the integration and evaluation of information gathered from different response teams and other sources of information, i.e. primarily on information exchange. The ability to exchange information in a timely, safe and effective manner is fundamental to emergency management.

To this end, a structured message (EMSI: Emergency Management Shared Information) is proposed to facilitate these information exchanges. The message is flexible according to the regulations of nations and organisations. It helps the exchange of information between organisations, especially when they have different terminologies or languages, allowing all organisations involved to cooperate with a high level of interoperability.

G3.22: Cross-border exercise schedule without elements of continuous improvement

ISO 22398:2013 Societal security — Guidelines for exercises

The scope of the exercises carried out does not develop elements with consequences for improvement in joint activities and procedures.

Exercises are an important management tool to identify errors and areas for improvement, as well as to determine the effectiveness of response and recovery strategies. In addition to measuring the competence of the organisation and its personnel, exercises are excellent tools for assessing the completeness, relevance and accuracy of revised plans and modified programmes.

G3.23: Existence of regulatory agreements not linked to operating procedures for the development of cross-border emergency management activities

ISO 22396:2020 Security and resilience — Community resilience — Guidelines for information exchange between organizations

Commitments included in agreements between different agencies and organizations are not included in the operating procedures.

In order to improve and support protection measures, multiple actors in both the public and private sectors need to be able to effectively and securely share information to enhance social security and improve resilience.

Sharing information on potential liabilities, risks and vulnerabilities can improve effectiveness and efficiency and precise boundaries need to be established between organisations with regard to information sharing. Responsibility for coordination is also difficult to define as coordination in these areas requires special solutions tailored within a sector, for each region or nation.

G3.24: Interferences due to participation of international volunteers

ISO 22319:2017 Security and resilience - Community resilience - Guidelines for planning the involvement of spontaneous volunteers

Complicated coordination of volunteer resources

A spontaneous volunteer (SV) is an individual who is not affiliated with existing incident response organisations but is motivated to contribute unpaid work during and following incidents.

SVs may have expressed an interest in volunteering prior to or during an incident and may therefore be called upon to participate depending on the needs of the incident and their specific skills. SAs may volunteer as individuals or as groups, may arrive at the incident to volunteer in person or contribute remotely, and may be self-employed professionals (e.g. retired emergency responders), digital volunteers, or any other qualified or unqualified members of the public.

SAs can provide a significant resource of timely manpower, skills and abilities to enhance the capacity of incident response organisations, provide valuable local knowledge, and customise response and recovery in an area by members of their local community. However, in large numbers, SAs can overwhelm incident response organisations, interfere with operations and create additional risks. SVs providing relief outside of official operations can put themselves and those they are intended to assist at risk.

It is important to understand and implement best practices for engaging and mobilising civilian responders, and the integration of civilian responders into response and recovery activities must be carefully managed.

G3.25: Convergence of cross-border emergency plans with response to landslides or similar

ISO 22327:2018 Security and resilience — Emergency management — Guidelines for implementation of a community-based landslide early warning system

Identification of appropriate resources and response in coordination with other emergency documents.

Importance should be given to people and communities who are vulnerable to landslides to act in a timely and appropriate manner to reduce the possibility of injury, loss of life, and damage to property and the environment.

Landslide mitigation should be carried out through structural and non-structural efforts. Structural mitigation includes adjustment of slope geometry, slope reinforcement, and protection and improvement of the drainage system, all of which would require high cost. Meanwhile, relocation is not possible for residents living in landslide-prone areas. In this condition, the most effective disaster risk reduction effort is non-structural mitigation through improving community preparedness by implementing an early warning system.

G3.26: current procedures do not receive information from social networks

ISO 22329:2021 Security and resilience — Emergency management — Guidelines for the use of social media in emergencies

Information produced without control in social media.

Social media is a valuable opportunity to reach people who may be of interest. The speed with which information can be made available also means that social platforms are an invaluable means of providing updates in the event of an emergency.

Unfortunately, the wrong information can spread just as quickly, with potentially disastrous consequences. So make the best use of the wide range of platforms available today and get the right information to the right people at the right time.

In a crisis, it is essential to ensure that information is reliable. In addition to guidance on the use of social media in emergency management, as well as helping organisations and the public to effectively use and interact with social media before, during and after an incident.

G3.27: Defining non-uniform hierarchical structures

ISO 22325:2016 Security and resilience - Emergency management - Guidelines for capability assessment

Complex assignment of hierarchical levels between different organizations.

Any organisation should consider guidelines for assessing its emergency management capability.

A capability assessment can be used to:

- Ensure regulatory compliance, reduce risk and meet the public's expectations for safety;
- Improve organisational processes;
- Improve partnership, coordination and cooperation within an organisation and with other agencies and sectors;
- Sharing best practice;
- Promote continuous improvement.

The context should be defined to enable a proper assessment of its emergency situation and management capacity. This context can be expressed by identifying appropriate activities in relation to prevention, mitigation, preparedness, response and recovery. All emergency management functions should be provided and should be clear and concise.

G3.28: Risk identification process with difficulty in adapting new risks in time

ISO 22326:2018 Security and resilience - Emergency management - Guidelines for monitoring facilities with identified hazards

Non-shared risk identification process and periodic reviews not optimized for a highly dynamic context.

In recent years, there has been a growing awareness of the risks and consequences of natural hazards and industrial disasters. Hazard monitoring can reduce potential losses through better prevention, mitigation, preparedness and more effective response to incidents resulting from hazards.

Effective monitoring can provide public and private sector emergency management with timely, accurate and easily understandable monitoring data to support decision-making in emergency management situations.

Safety standards are continually evolving and improving. Advances in monitoring technology provide opportunities to further improve these guidelines and for their development and implementation of innovative monitoring solutions.

The purpose is to contribute to an overall emergency management framework that seeks to reduce risk to people, operations, property and the environment.

G3.29: Recognition of a vulnerable person during an event with multiple victims

ISO 22395:2018 Security and resilience - Community resilience - Guidelines for supporting vulnerable persons in an emergency

Vulnerability recognition procedure during the accident, having already been evaluated in an organization

Identify the people most vulnerable to an emergency and know how to include them in preparedness, response and recovery for events, incidents and emergencies. Emergencies have different effects on people; for example, some individuals will be less able to anticipate, cope with, resist or recover from the impacts of an emergency. An individual is not defined as vulnerable by nature but by their personal circumstances at the time of the emergency. A person's vulnerability to an emergency is influenced by many factors and can vary in different environmental, political, cultural and social contexts. It is widely recognised that people who are vulnerable to an emergency require specific types of assistance. However, there is less understanding and guidance on how to recognise people who are vulnerable in different emergency situations and how to support them. This may be because vulnerability changes over time, so people move in and out of being vulnerable, even to the same event, incident or emergency. Factors include age, economic security, language and health, but also the effects of wider processes such as climate change, international security and national political trends.

G3.30 Development of national emergency management master document with non-standard structure

PLANO NACIONAL DE EMERGÊNCIA DE PROTEÇÃO CIVIL

Difficulty in adapting national plans across countries

An emergency plan is the planning and human organization for the optimal use of the technical means provided in order to minimize the possible human and/or economic consequences that could arise from the emergency situation.

From the definition, it can be deduced that the emergency plan seeks to optimize the available resources, so its implementation implies having previously provided material, technical and other necessary resources depending on the characteristics of the incident and where it occurred. This in turn implies having previously carried out an identification and analysis of risks or deficiencies, essential to know the provision of prevention-protection means that are required in it.

It is for all this, that in the case that several countries have to intervene, everything is coordinated and they act with the same methodology and resources, in order to be able to intervene as soon as possible in a unilateral manner and avoid possible negative consequences.

G3.31 Objectives of fire protection plans of different scope

Plan de Lucha contra Incendios Forestales de la Comunidad Autónoma de Extremadura (Plan INFOEX)

National plans respond to national management and there may be different priorities in the objectives of the plans.

For emergency management, different action plans are developed that take into consideration the resources identified and the organisational structure associated with the scope of the plan.

In a cross-border emergency context it is appropriate that the plans have commonalities in their development in order to achieve synergy between the participating countries and facilitate coordination of activities and resources.

G3.32 Operational procedures have a maximum scope at the national level.

PR-GNR-02 PROTOCOLO DE ACTUACIÓN EN EMERGENCIAS

Operational procedures are limited to the area of creation, leaving aside the possibility of working with third entities and organisations, and cross-border environment.

Correct attention to Incidents with multiple victims constitutes one of the most important challenges of an Emergency Service, not only in terms of on-site care for patients, but also the need for coordination and organization among the care resources themselves the Emergency Coordination Service and other health and non-health institutions.

Depending on the magnitude of the incident and the number of victims affected, the incident becomes a catastrophe, having to give an immediate response.

Emergency plans must involve the participation of different stakeholders. From volunteers to the participation of third parties and companies.

G3.33 Statement of resources needed to establish communication between third parties in a cross-border context

Methodological instruction which establishes a system of mutual communication when addressing the consequences of MCI

The resources used to communicate information, as well as the information to be communicated, must be pre-established at the time of the accident.

Establish a mutual communication system in the event of a mass accident involving people or to deal with a situation in which there is an immediate threat that there is a direct threat to the life or health of citizens or public health, an instruction must be issued methodology that establishes a communication system according to the situation and that coordinates all the possible actors involved.

G3.34 Heterogeneity in documentary structure according to ISO standards

PRO 22 - Management, spheres of action, responsibilities, operational strategies, information and decision-making flows, use of resources, victim management and collaboration

Faced with the need for rapid response in a cross-border emergency event, the provision of documents without a standardised structure can generate organisational noise that detracts from the efficiency of such a response, with direct and indirect victims being the most affected.

Each entity generates useful information for its own risk management and taking into account its organisational and social culture. These documents are learned and trained by the staff associated with this entity. An amalgamation of documentary structures generates an added difficulty in the actual operation of the emergency.

In the cross-border scenario, whose impact on society is high but whose frequency is very low, adequate prior planning is required to optimise the response when necessary.

G3.35 Adequate allocation of resources for the development of the SOP

PRO 22 - Management, spheres of action, responsibilities, operational strategies, information and decision-making flows, use of resources, victim management and collaboration

Operating procedures should express the resources, tasks and objectives to be achieved according to international standards.

Protocols, instructions and similar documentation should respond to the achievement of explicit objectives in the document. In order to achieve the objectives, the necessary resources must be allocated and described in such a way that the document is consistent.

4.4.2. Opportunity Analysis

Once the GAPS have been recognized, for each one of them, we identify the opportunities that we estimate could be relevant in order to improve the process:

O3.1-G3.1: Unify the colors of road ambulances according to the European standard

UNE 179002:2018 Health services. Quality management system (QMS) for health care transport organization.

Increase the safety of patients and operators through the unique identification of ambulances in Europe.

Distinction or unique identification for ambulances within the European framework, either by means of colours, a specific logo or similar, both for the vehicle and for its medical staff. In order that there is no confusion and all have the same technical characteristics as well as medical equipment and staffing, complementing the applicable legislation in force in each country.

O3.2-G3.2: Stablish standard EWS

ISO 22328:2020-1 Security and resilience - Emergency management - Guidelines for the implementation of a community-based disaster early warnings system

Improvement of joint response in cases of disasters.

Effective disaster risk reduction or mitigation is implemented through various approaches, by improving community preparedness and consequent resilience through the implementation of an early warning system (EWS).

A comprehensive and effective EWS consists of four key interrelated elements:

- risk awareness;
- monitoring and warning service; c) dissemination and communication
- dissemination and communication;
- response capacity.

EWS incorporates not only engineering, but also social aspects such as demographics, economics and culture.

Uniformity in the development and implementation of EWS should be promoted. Improving the preparedness of communities and stakeholders vulnerable to disasters and/or incidents, considering the different channels of communication, legal requirements, and allocation of responsibilities as well as final decision making and communication.

O3.3-G3.3: Repository vocabulary

ISO 31073:2022(en) Risk management — Vocabulary. 2022

It is necessary to understand the same terms in the same way by each member to ensure effective communication.

A mutual and consistent understanding and a coherent approach to the description of risk management activities should be fostered. Similarly, exposing the use of uniform risk management terminology in processes, frameworks and methodologies dealing with risk management is highly beneficial.

O3.4-G3.4: Harmonization for training exercises

ISO 22398:2013 Societal security — Guidelines for exercises

Establish requirements, skills, procedures to train joint actions in cross-border disasters

A generic approach should be given to planning, conducting and improving exercise programmes and projects. In order to:

- Provide a basis for understanding, developing and implementing an effective exercise programme.
- Provide guidelines for planning and conducting exercises.
- Assist in developing and evaluating exercise capability in a consistent and risk-assessed manner that reflects good practice.
- Enable continuous improvement in exercise programmes.

Exercises are an important management tool to identify gaps and areas for improvement, as well as to determine the effectiveness of response and recovery strategies. In addition to measuring the competence of the organisation and its staff, exercises are excellent tools for assessing the completeness, relevance and accuracy of revised plans and modified programmes.

Exercises can be used to validate policies, plans, procedures, training, equipment and cross-organisational agreements; test information and communication technology disaster recovery systems; clarify and train staff on roles and responsibilities; improve coordination and communications between organisations; identify resource gaps; improve individual

performance; identify opportunities for improvement; and provide a controlled opportunity to practice improvisation.

The main objectives of these exercises are:

- Orientation/demonstration: simulation of the experience of an expected situation to increase awareness of vulnerabilities and the importance of effective action in response to the simulated conditions.
- Learning: improving the knowledge, skills or capabilities of staff with the aim of mastering specific competencies.
- Cooperation: providing an opportunity for people to work together as a team to achieve a common end result.
- Experiment: to try out new or existing methods and/or procedures with the intention of perfecting them.
- Test: evaluation of a method and/or procedure to assess which components are sufficiently developed.

O3.5-G3.5: Standardization of different classes of ambulances

EN 1846-1:2011 Firefighting and rescue service vehicles - Part 1: Nomenclature and designation

Optimize resources and exchange of information through unification of criteria.

The European Standard EN 1789 regulates medical transport vehicles and their equipment; specifying the requirements for the design, testing, performance and equipment that all road ambulances used for medical transport must meet. It is mandatory to accredit compliance for some countries.

This norm is a standard that sets the manufacturers and transformers of this type of vehicles how the medical vehicles and their equipment should be. We are talking about the dimensions of the patient compartment, tests for the fastening systems of elements, seats, belts and anchorages, etc. As soon as second-stage manufacturers start to produce according to this standard, the scope for configuration of an ambulance is reduced to what is exclusively approved. This is why the standardisation of these vehicles is here to stay.

O3.6-G3.6: Multi-technological operability of devices for information processing

ISO 13606-1:2019 Health informatics — Electronic health record communication — Part 1: Reference model

Use of different technological solutions that allow the communication of patient health records

In disasters, victims may have moved from one country to another, and may not be in their country of origin, so they need to seek health care or obtain the dispensing of a medicine or health product. When this happens, professionals, in order to provide an adequate service, need a system that allows them to consult clinical information regardless of where it has been generated.

O3.7-G3.6: Standardization of roles related to patient data management

ISO 13606-1:2019 Health informatics — Electronic health record communication — Part 1: Reference model

Uniformly designate the resources that interact in health activities in a cross-border setting

CEN/ISO EN13606 is a standard for semantic communication and interoperability of parts of the electronic health record (EHR) or the entire EHR between EHR systems, or between other applications or systems that need to access EHR data. The standard consists of a dual model based on the idea of separating information from knowledge managed by IT systems:

- The reference model, for the representation of clinical information. It provides the building blocks (generic classes and structures) for the EHR.
- The archetype model, in charge of representing clinical concepts of higher semantic level. Valid combinations of building blocks with a specific meaning are defined. Archetypes do not contain data, but only define a template.

O3.8-G3.7: Set severity levels for all events

ISO 22328:2020-1 Security and resilience - Emergency management - Guidelines for the implementation of a community-based disaster early warnings system

Consistent responsiveness across all participating countries

Disasters such as earthquakes, tsunamis, volcanic eruptions, high river flows (e.g. flash floods), landslides, storm surges and hurricanes, as well as slow-onset events such as drought, extreme temperatures, heat waves or soil erosion can have devastating effects. Disasters can happen at any time to anyone living in a disaster-prone area. These disasters injure and kill people and result in huge economic, social and environmental losses. Disasters can be caused by natural hazards and/or by human beings.

Disaster mitigation can be carried out using various approaches, including the construction of prevention and protection works, which require a high investment of cost and time. In addition,

Disasters can have a wide and varied range of impacts, which means that implementing these measures may not be effective. Therefore, effective disaster risk reduction is implemented through various approaches, by improving community preparedness and consequent resilience through the implementation of an early warning system (EWS).

A community-based disaster EWS is proposed to empower people and communities living in hazard-prone areas to be more alert, react or evacuate in sufficient time and reduce disaster losses such as injuries, loss of life and damage to property, the economy and the environment.

Improved preparedness can be achieved through the implementation of an EWS, as well as improved dissemination and communication of disaster early warning knowledge at local, national, regional and international levels.

O3.9-G3.7: Establish communication protocols for accidents and disasters

ISO 22328:2020-1 Security and resilience - Emergency management - Guidelines for the implementation of a community-based disaster early warnings system

Optimum management of communications between all governmental and non-governmental entities and with citizens, improving response capacity

A comprehensive and effective EWS consists of four key interrelated elements:

- Risk awareness;
- Monitoring and warning service;

- Dissemination and communication;
- Response capacity.

All of these elements are strongly correlated with the implementation of a community-based EWS.

EWS incorporates not only engineering, but also social aspects such as demographics, economics and culture. This document encourages active community response to disasters and considers social aspects in general. Further dissemination and communication of knowledge to the community is carried out by the authority at local and national level.

By referring to the four key elements of a community-based EWS, this document promotes uniformity in the development and implementation of an EWS. It will improve the preparedness of communities and stakeholders vulnerable to disasters.

Community-based disaster EWS considers the different channels of communication, legal requirements and allocation of responsibilities as well as final decision-making and communication.

03.10-G3.8: Protocols for coordinated action in cross-border scenarios

ISO 22315:2014 Societal security - Mass evacuation - Guidelines for planning

Coordinated action and availability of resources adapted to cross-border needs.

It is appropriate to carry out planning for mass evacuations, that is, the movement or transfer of people from a designated area. An evacuation is characterized by the need for multi-agency collaboration and resources. Typically this means a larger number of people or a broader area at risk. It is difficult to define mass evacuation in terms of numbers or scale because disasters, communities, and response capabilities differ. However, it can be considered in terms of the number of evacuees that exceed a daily scale of response such as the evacuation of a city, region, or large populated area.

The need for evacuation can arise from natural events, human-induced events (both intentional and unintentional), and events caused by technological failures. Some events require immediate evacuation while others give advance notice.

Effective planning is important to help save human lives and reduce suffering. Planning helps to achieve an effective response and is part of emergency management. Mass evacuation plans should be developed, support decision-making, increase the potential for an effective response, and strengthen public and organizational preparedness. There are also barriers that could make it difficult for people to evacuate, such as concerns about pets, valuable possessions, or livelihood items.

Some general aspects for planning a mass evacuation would be:

- Prepare the public to react effectively
- Understand and visualize an area at risk and/or an affected area and provide decision makers with information that allows them to decide whether to request an evacuation.

- Making the decision to request an evacuation, aims to ensure that the decision-making process, the objectives and the participants are appropriate.
- Warn the public of the need to react as advised, consider communication protocols and community-based alert systems.
- Analysis of the movement of evacuees to a security area, for example, to understand the needs, demands and availability of transport.
- Evaluate shelter requirements for evacuees. For example, they can identify the demand for shelters and establish agreements to provide shelters.
- Evaluate and continually improve evacuation plans.

O3.11-G3.9: Harmonized technology security protocols

ISO/IEC 27010:2015 Information technology - security techniques - Information security management for inter-sector and inter-organizational communications

Establish protocols and requirements for the secure control of sensitive information

Information security is a fundamental piece since the data that is handled is essential for the future of the disaster. In addition, it must also be taken into account that information security must face risks, analyze them, prevent them and find quick solutions to eliminate them if necessary.

Information security, as a concept, is based on four pillars: availability, integrity, confidentiality and authentication.

- Availability: Access to information when required, taking privacy into account. Avoid system "crashes" that allow illegitimate access that prevent access to mail...
- Confidentiality: Information accessible only to authorized personnel. The information should not reach people or entities that are not authorized.
- Integrity: Correct information without unauthorized modifications or errors. It protects against external vulnerabilities or possible human errors.
- Authentication: Information from a user who is who they say they are. It is verified and must be guaranteed that the origin of the data is correct.

O3.12-G3.10: Cloud computing service standard

ISO 19941:2017 Information Technology - Cloud Computing - Interoperability and portability

Establish an international standard that includes the requirements, needs and services necessary for emergency response management in a cross-border environment

Cloud computing is a new way of providing information processing services. A cloud computing solution allows the user to optimize the allocation and cost of resources associated with their information processing needs. There is no need to invest in infrastructure, but instead uses the one made available by the service provider, guaranteeing that situations of lack or excess of resources are not generated, as well as the extra cost associated with said situations.

In a cloud computing environment, information management is virtually in the hands of of the client who hires cloud services, who treats it through the Internet, accessing database solutions, email, or any type of application according to your needs.

ISO/IEC 19941:2017 specifies the types of cloud computing interoperability and portability, the relationship and interactions between these two cross-cutting aspects of cloud computing, and common terminology and concepts used to discuss interoperability and portability, particularly in relation to cloud services.

O3.13-G3.10: Cloud computing service standard for devices

ISO 19941:2017 Information Technology - Cloud Computing - Interoperability and portability

Establish an international standard where the requirements, needs and services necessary for devices used in emergency management in a cross-border scenario.

Cloud computing is a new way of providing information processing services. A cloud computing solution allows the user to optimize the allocation and cost of resources associated with their information processing needs. There is no need to invest in infrastructure, but instead uses the one made available by the service provider, guaranteeing that situations of lack or excess of resources are not generated, as well as the extra cost associated with said situations.

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O3.14-G3.11: Database with high precision maps

ISO 19128:2005 Geographic information — Web map server interface (WMS)

Dynamic management of high-precision routes communicated to available resources in emergency management.

The operations of a WMS service can be invoked through a web browser that sends a request in the form of a URL - Uniform Resource Locator. This request is received and processed by the WMS server which, in response, returns an image to the client in screen quality, in image format such as JPEG, GIF, PNG, etc.

As indicated above the maps return in an image format such as PNG, GIF or JPEG, and occasionally as vector graphics in SVG or KML format. Using image formats that support transparent backgrounds (eg GIF or PNG) allows underlying layers to be visible.

The maps generated by the WMS can be viewed through viewers that run within a web browser, such as Internet Explorer, Firefox, Opera, etc.; or through an application installed on a computer such as QGIS, ArcGis, GvSIG or Google Earth. Both types of clients include visualization operations such as: activating and deactivating layers, changing their order and transparency, zooming in and out, moving on the map, panning, etc.

One of the characteristics of WMS is overlapping, that is, individual layers from different servers can be requested from a server, producing overlapping layers from different sources. Therefore, the information layers can be stored in different servers located in different remote places. Therefore, the information does not necessarily have to be stored on the same computer.

WMS have the ability to read the data in their original formats (dgn, ESRI shp, geotiff, ecw, connections with Postgis databases, Oracle Spatial, ESRI arcSDE, etc.), and generate an image in png, gif, jpg, tiff, etc. format as output product.

The geographic information layers must be georeferenced, in order to superimpose layers from different sources, but they do not necessarily have to be in the same Spatial Reference System. WMS have the ability to reproject geographic information “on-the-fly”. The data remains in its original frame of reference, but the server generates the output image in the frame of reference that we select, so that the layers overlap correctly.

The displayed maps can overlay each other, as long as the geographic parameters and output size are the same. The use of formats that allow a transparent background (for example, GIF or PNG) facilitates the simultaneous visualization of these maps. Through the superimposition of maps obtained from different servers, clients will be able to make personalized compositions.

The international standard ISO 19128 defines two modes of operation, one for a basic WMS, and another for a query WMS. The basic WMS must support the basic parameters of the service operations (version, HTTP requests and responses, numeric and boolean values, certain output formats, coordinate systems, query and response parameters, and exceptions), the GetCapabilities operation, and the GetMap operation. It classifies the information it has into “Layers” and offers a certain number of “Styles”, with which these layers can be displayed. The query WMS must satisfy all the requirements of a basic WMS and also support the GetFeatureInfo operation.

03.15-G3.13: Harmonization of international procedures for assistance in cross-border emergencies

Decision No 1313/2013/EU on a Union Civil Protection Mechanism

Facilitate international regulation to optimize resource management. A harmonized recognition of bilateral and international collaborations is understood to improve the mutual recognition of resources, communication channels and hierarchical references.

The Union Civil Protection Mechanism will aim to strengthen cooperation between the Union and the Member States and facilitate coordination in the field of civil protection in order to improve the effectiveness of disaster prevention, preparedness and response systems natural or of human origin.

The protection that the Union Mechanism must ensure will cover above all people, but also the environment and property, including cultural heritage, against all types of natural and man-made disasters, including the consequences of acts of terrorism, catastrophes of a technological, radiological or environmental nature, marine pollution, hydrogeological imbalance and serious health emergencies that occur inside or outside the Union. In the case of the consequences of acts of terrorism or catastrophes of a radiological nature, the Union Mechanism may only cover preparedness and response actions.

The Union Mechanism shall promote solidarity between Member States through practical cooperation and coordination, without prejudice to the primary responsibility of Member States to protect the population, the environment and property, including cultural heritage, on their territory, against disasters, and to provide their disaster management systems with sufficient

capacity to enable them to adequately and consistently prevent and deal with disasters of a nature and magnitude that can reasonably be expected and for which they can prepare.

O3.16-G3.14: International rapid response cross-border emergency management plan

ISO 22320:2018 Security and resilience - Emergency management - Guidelines for incident management

Improve the identification and management of resources for responding to cross-border emergencies

In recent years, there have been many disasters, both natural and man-made, and other major incidents that have demonstrated the importance of incident management in saving lives, reducing harm and damage, and ensuring an adequate level of business continuity essential social functions.

Such functions include health, telecommunications, food and water supply, and access to electricity and fuel. While in the past the focus of incident management has been national, regional or within single organizations, today and for the future there is a need for a multinational and multi-organizational approach. This need is driven by the relationships and interdependencies between governments, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), civil society organizations (CSOs) and the private sector internationally.

Factors such as increased urbanization, critical infrastructure dependencies and interdependencies, socioeconomic dynamics, environmental change, animal and human disease, and the increased movement of people and goods around the world have increased the potential for disruptions and disasters that transcend geographic and political boundaries and impact incident management capacity.

Guidance is needed for organizations to improve their handling of all types of incidents (for example, emergencies, crises, interruptions and disasters). Multiple incident management activities are often shared between organizations and agencies, with the private sector, organizations and governments having different levels of jurisdiction. Therefore, there is a need to guide all parties involved in how to prepare and implement incident management.

O3.17-G3.15: Determine communications procedures

ISO 22320:2018 Security and resilience - Emergency management - Guidelines for incident management

Optimize decision-making for proper management of resources and victims of the incident

Assistance between organisations, regions or borders during incident management is expected to be appropriate to the needs of the affected population and be culturally sensitive. Therefore, multi-stakeholder engagement, which focuses on community involvement in the development and implementation of incident management, is desirable where appropriate. The organizations involved require the ability to share a common approach across geographic, political, and organizational boundaries.

All of this is applicable to any organization responsible for preparing for or responding to incidents at the local, regional, national and possibly international level, including those that

- Are responsible for and participate in the preparation of incidents,

- Provide guidance and direction in incident management,
- Are responsible for communication and interaction with the public, and
- Research in the field of incident management.

03.18-G3.16: Standard cross-border emergency management procedure

ISO 22320:2018 Security and resilience - Emergency management - Guidelines for incident management

Joint activation of the cross-border incident management procedure

Organizations benefit from using a common approach to incident management, as this enables collaborative work and ensures more coherent and complementary actions between organizations.

Most incidents are local in nature and are managed at the local, municipal, regional, state or provincial level.

03.19-G3.17: Uniform alert policy for cross-border incident management

ISO 22322:2015 Security and resilience - Emergency management - Guidelines for public warnings

Uniform support system for all types of organizations and societies for alarm management in incidents and emergencies

A Common Warning System should provide guidelines for the development, management and implementation of warning before, during and after incidents or emergencies.

The alarm system must be known and communicated to any organization responsible for public alert and applicable at all levels, from local to international.

Before planning and implementing the public warning system, the risks and consequences of possible hazards are assessed.

Must integrate a uniform set of protocols, processes and technologies based on public alert policy to deliver notifications and alert messages in an ongoing emergency situation to people at risk and to first responders.

03.20-G3.18: Comprehensive technological solution for all types of organizations capable of generating and receiving public alarm and emergency systems

ISO 22322:2015 Security and resilience - Emergency management - Guidelines for public warnings

Establish software with acceptable requirements among the community with the functions required for a public alarm system

The purpose of an alert is to draw people's attention to an ongoing emergency situation stimulate their auditory, visual, and tactile senses to take appropriate safety measures and seek additional information.

The alert dissemination function must guarantee that the alert receives the maximum attention, taking into account the characteristics and conditions of the people at risk, including the requirements of vulnerable groups.

The alert dissemination function should determine the appropriate alert methods taking into account the following factors:

- The time necessary to allow people to follow the instruction (opportunity);
- Availability, efficiency and technical reliability;
- How easily people can access the transmitted message, including vulnerable people.

The alert broadcast function must consider the capacity of the communication range and channels to provide maximum coverage and timely distribution.

The communication channels are the following:

- Public multipurpose person to person (telephone, FAX, cell phone);
- Public broadcasting (TV, radio, cell broadcast);
- Print media (newspapers);
- Dedicated alert systems (sirens, smoke detectors, interior receiver, loudspeakers, vehicles with public address public address systems);
- Media based on information and communication technologies (ICT) (web pages, email, SMS and social media);
- Direct personal communication (neighbor to neighbor, workplaces).

The alert broadcast function should use multiple communication channels simultaneously and free of charge.

New and emerging communication channels should be considered as they become available.

The alert dissemination function should monitor the communication channels used to maintain the quality of alert dissemination and perform periodic assessments of effectiveness and consistency.

O3.21-G3.19: Comprehensive assessment system for cross-border incidents

ISO 22322:2015 Security and resilience - Emergency management - Guidelines for public warnings

Creation of a standard evaluation system for cross-border events

A framework should be designed based on two functions: hazard monitoring and alert dissemination. The responsibility for issuing public warnings should be assigned to stakeholders who are individual experts, expert groups or organizations in the public or private sectors at the local level, up to the international level. Those who contribute to both functions should

- Be familiar with the possibilities and capabilities of the public alert system so that it is relevant, accurate, reliable and timely alerts will be disseminated,
- Make a continuous effort to increase and maintain public awareness, and
- Specify security actions within the warning.

In addition, the performance of hazard monitoring and alert dissemination should be evaluated on a regular basis. The evaluation findings should be used to identify possible improvements.

The evaluation processes must be carried out at regular intervals not exceeding five years.

The alert dissemination function should assess the content and timeliness of notifications and alerts, as well as the choice of communication channels.

The evaluation processes must be activated whenever the people at risk have not taken the expected security actions.

03.22-G3.20: Create a uniform coding system for alarms and signalling

ISO 22324:2015 Security and resilience - Emergency management - Guidelines for colour-coded alerts

Create a uniform alarm system between public and private organizations based on signaling standards. Coherent and uniform response among member states to the same events.

Common and general guidelines should be provided for the use of color codes to inform people at risk as well as first responders about the danger and to express the seriousness of a situation, being applicable to all types of danger in any situation place.

It would also be interesting to describe a common method for displaying color codes, detailed ergonomics, and considerations related to displaying screens or safety signs covered by ISO 3864-1.

03.23-G3.21: Determine standard EMSI for cross-border events

ISO/TR 22351:2015 Societal Security - Emergency Management - Message structure for exchange of information

Identify key messages to facilitate and standardize communications between organizations of any type

It would be interesting to establish structured messages (EMSI: Emergency Management Shared Information) to facilitate these exchanges of information.

An EMSI describes a part of the operating image at a certain time. It is exchanged to transfer information and describes events, resources, and missions.

An EMSI can be used peer-to-peer at the same level of the command hierarchy or up and down the hierarchy. This information contributes to the situational awareness of the organizations involved to facilitate the coordination of plans and actions.

03.24-G3.22: Prepare reviews to improve intervention procedures

ISO 22398:2013 Societal security — Guidelines for exercises

Creation of a shared repository of improvement opportunities and lessons learned

The findings of the evaluation carried out through the simulation exercises should be used to identify possible improvements. According to the estimated programming for the realization of the drills, these must be carried out in simulated situations of any kind or emergency, as well as in any place. The results of the same, must be analyzed and considered in common, and take

them into account for any other circumstance, leaving registration and stand available to whoever needs it.

O3.25-G3.23: Establishment of general principles and an operational framework for procedures

ISO 22396:2020 Security and resilience — Community resilience — Guidelines for information exchange between organizations

Development of procedures as part of the deployment of the different international regulatory and/or contractual commitments (or other scope) of the different public/private organizations

Organizations that participate in information sharing agreements can increase their knowledge and understanding with the aim of improving resilience. Effective information sharing arrangements can provide other benefits to these participating organizations, including:

- Clarify to organizations that they cannot normally gain access in the usual ways;
- Improve capabilities by unlocking information that would otherwise be restricted;
- Create a centralized information exchange to support the exchange;
- Increase the capacity for information distribution;
- Create a sense of community through caring and sharing.

O3.26-G3.24: Rapid evaluation of spontaneous volunteers

ISO 22319:2017 Security and resilience - Community resilience - Guidelines for planning the involvement of spontaneous volunteers

Spontaneous Volunteer Participation Evaluation Methodology

The organization should:

- Put in place a strategy to make the best use of the VS that are selected;
- Develop and implement a structured approach to select, accept, induct and train VS to perform assigned tasks;
- Accept svcs for the tasks for which they are suitable

For all this, common selection methodologies for volunteers should be implemented, depending on the help they can provide.

O3.27-G3.25: Standardization of emergency plan for all types of emergencies

ISO 22327:2018 Security and resilience — Emergency management — Guidelines for implementation of a community-based landslide early warning system

Creation of uniform criteria for alarms and emergency notifications

Dissemination and communication of knowledge provides understanding to the community regarding the possibility of a landslide disaster. Based on preliminary disaster data and its risk assessments, dissemination and communication methods and materials should be developed.

The community should receive information about the types of landslide disasters, how and why they occur, the factors that control and trigger the event, and the structural and non-structural factors, strategies to mitigate the consequences, including an early warning system, alert and signaling levels.

Dissemination and communication of knowledge should use clear language, provide useful information, identify the authoritative agency, and provide multiple methods of communication to ensure the maximum number of people is reached.

Effective dissemination provides a better understanding and how to minimize risks once early warning systems are in place.

The dissemination of information can lead to the identification of key individuals with an interest in participating in a disaster preparedness team.

03.28-G3.26: Treatment of information generated in social networks

ISO 22329:2021 Security and resilience — Emergency management — Guidelines for the use of social media in emergencies

Treatment of information during emergency management from digital media

Correct use of social networks must be made in emergency management. Have guidance on how organizations and the public can use and interact through social media before, during and after an incident and how social media can support the work of emergency services.

With the increase in digitization, there are an increasing number of social media platforms and channels available, and the selection and popularity is continually changing. Social networks are available worldwide, but access to some platforms and channels may be restricted in some countries. Some platforms and channels focus on exchanging text messages, others focus on sharing photos or videos, and some allow the exchange of text, photos, and videos. Many may include links to any content stored on the Internet.

There is a connection between social networks and other media such as websites, newspapers, radio and television. People also share news articles and information on social media.

That is why you should:

- Consider the role of social media in the context of the overall communication strategy, including crisis communication and how the social media strategy is implemented in the organization;
- Understand that the extent to which information is shared depends on the application in which it was shared and the privacy settings of the user who shared the content;
- Understand that social networks are operated by private companies and are governed by their own terms of service or user agreement.

03.29-G3.27: Hierarchical level standardization

ISO 22325:2016 Security and resilience - Emergency management - Guidelines for capability assessment

Homogenization by levels for hierarchical structures

The organization must use the four-level evaluation model to classify its emergency management capacity. This is subject to the functions, scope and authority of an organization and the operating context.

Emergency management capacity should be assessed using indicators that reflect the scope, role and authority of the organization:

- Leadership;
- Resource management;
- Information and communication;
- Risk management;
- Coordination and cooperation;
- Emergency management planning;
- Exercise program;
- Incident management system.

O3.30-G3.28: Non-shared risk identification process and periodic reviews not optimized for a highly dynamic context

ISO 22326:2018 Security and resilience - Emergency management - Guidelines for monitoring facilities with identified hazards

Risk assessment for data management related to emergency management processes

Guidelines for monitoring hazards as part of an emergency management and continuity program should be provided by establishing the process for hazard monitoring at facilities with identified hazards.

Develop and operate systems for the purpose of monitoring facilities with identified hazards. Cover the entire monitoring process of the installations.

O3.31-G3.28: Improvement of communication for different hierarchical scales between organizations

ISO 22326:2018 Security and resilience - Emergency management - Guidelines for monitoring facilities with identified hazards

Contribution of information to organizations and stakeholders identified based on a risk level framework

The monitoring process involves the reception, integration, generation, analysis, transfer and output of data. The process involves the owner of the facility, the authorities responsible for security and other stakeholders interested in obtaining monitoring data.

The monitoring process should provide data to facility owners, authorities and interested parties by using pre-established data sharing procedures.

The monitoring process should:

- Monitor hazards and critical indicators,
- Include information resulting from human intervention in the modes of operation of the facility,
- Provide a continuous, reliable, trustworthy service (independent of the maintenance of the installation), dynamic critical indicators applicable to the identified hazards,
- Provide real-time data transfer on changes of critical indicators,
- Prioritize the use of automated and manual systems, and

- Evaluate the results of related maintenance for possible improvements to the monitoring process.

O3.32-G3.29: Information shared between organizations regarding vulnerable personnel

ISO 22395:2018 Security and resilience - Community resilience - Guidelines for supporting vulnerable persons in an emergency

Preparation of procedure to identify and manage vulnerable people

In large numbers and in different contexts, vulnerable people are not always recognised, or there are too many of them and could overwhelm emergency response teams. In addition, there are other types of support and structures for vulnerable people, but these can break in an emergency. It is important to understand and implement best practices to recognize and include vulnerable people in all phases of emergency preparedness, response and recovery. In particular, this requires an understanding of what creates vulnerability to ensure that people are not ignored or further negatively impacted through emergency management.

O3.33: Development of the association agreement process for cross-border emergency management

ISO 22397:2014 provides guidelines for establishing partnering arrangements among organizations to manage multiple relationships for events impacting on societal security. It incorporates principles and describes the process for planning, developing, implementing and reviewing partnering arrangements.

Creation of procedures with the statement of necessary requirements for linking agencies and organizations within a cross-border emergency management consortium.

The world has become a global community of interdependent societies. Changes in technical and economic relationships have resulted in cross-border and jurisdictional interdependencies for vital functions and assets of society. The safety and well-being of people increasingly depend on the continuity of the vital functions of organizations, local communities, nations and the global community.

The impact of incidents has increased the need to improve preparedness, response, and recovery programs. There are many different roles and responsibilities within and between public, private, and nonprofit organizations. Some roles and responsibilities are primarily the responsibility of individuals, while others can be adequately addressed only by multiple organizations in order to manage risk. In a complex and changing world, organizations should consider partnering. Association is the alliance or consortium with others in an activity or area of common interest in order to achieve individual objectives and collective objectives.

O3.34-G3.30: Unified strategic plan for cross-border emergency management

PLANO NACIONAL DE EMERGÊNCIA DE PROTEÇÃO CIVIL

Uniform emergency plan for coordinated solution in cross-border emergency management

For the optimal planning, organization and use of the technical means provided for any type of incident, and in the event that several countries have to intervene, and that everything is coordinated and that they act with the same methodology and resources, in order to be able to intervene as unilaterally as soon as possible and avoid possible negative consequences.

O3.35-G3.31: Uniform objectives of protection plans

Plan de Lucha contra Incendios Forestales de la Comunidad Autónoma de Extremadura (Plan INFOEX)

Emergency plans should state the same objectives and scope for optimal joint action.

The creation of protocols, procedures and other emergency management tools are generated at different levels, from small regions to the national level. These needs are born out of risk studies. It is desirable to articulate a structure of uniform procedures for the most likely risks between neighbouring countries and those that already have collaborations enshrined in legislation. This procedural basis needs mutual recognition of principles, responsibilities, resources and objectives.

O3.36-G3.32: Standard operating procedures with recognition of task performance in cross-border environment with different stakeholders

PR-GNR-02 PROTOCOLO DE ACTUACIÓN EN EMERGENCIAS

Operational procedures should respond to real cross-border scenarios and anticipate responses to the most likely events."

Emergency medical services develop their interventions together with professionals from other sectors in a cross-border context, and most likely in other settings. For this reason, procedures must include the participation of third parties. In a multi-victim scenario, the voluntary participation of other victims, law enforcement and other entities is likely. Procedures should be developed in such a way as to provide the necessary guidelines and process flows to respond to the various eventualities that may arise.

Responsibilities and organisational structures must also be taken into account for the correct transmission of orders and tasks between the different actors involved. There is an opportunity to generate unified emergency response procedures with mutual recognition of information structures, responsibility, policies and shared use of resources.

O3.37-G3.33: Uniform definition of the characteristics of the information to be transmitted and the resources required

Methodological instruction which establishes a system of mutual communication when addressing the consequences of MCI

Operational procedures should explicitly address the characteristics of the messages in a structured way and the different means of communication.

The initial information to be transmitted once the emergency has occurred is very important and crucial since, depending on its reliability and certainty, the different operations that must intervene depending on the magnitude of the event can be organized.

O3.38-G3.34: SOPs use standardised colours and with the expected function according to international standards

PRO 22 - Management, spheres of action, responsibilities, operational strategies, information and decision-making flows, use of resources, victim management and collaboration
Standardised information helps any receiver of the information to interpret the message appropriately.

Information is a critical element in emergency management. Useful information is that which is necessary for the development of processes related to emergency management. Bearing this in mind, it is necessary to consider that in a cross-border scenario this information comes from various sources and may be housed in various structures. It is equally important to underline that part of the information is confidential and sensitive since it belongs to the health and related sectors.

All this information must be adequately secured and structured for shared use at the required times and for the required roles, complying with national and international legal requirements and computer security.

Finally, the information provided to third parties must be analyzed and structured prior to communication to society as a whole by any means of communication.

O3.39-G3.35: Detailed description of resources, tasks and objectives for SOPs

PRO 22 - Management, spheres of action, responsibilities, operational strategies, information and decision-making flows, use of resources, victim management and collaboration
Operational procedures should be consistent and responsive to the objectives set out in a unified framework for cross-border emergency management.

The consistency of the procedures consists of maintaining their operation, fulfilling their objectives in any circumstance. The identified standards open an opportunity to create operating procedures that are resilient in the cross-border context. The approval by all the parties involved of the contents of the documents together with the commitments to deploy them configures a valid tool to have an adequate solution when faced with a need for a joint response.

4.4.3. GAP/OPP Evaluation

As it has been possible to verify, there are numerous specific regulations that can be applied to cases of disasters and/or emergencies exposed or of any type, with a lot of information, forms of management and methodologies to be applied, regardless of the given situation or the phase in to be found

That is why what is advised is to carry out or prepare a standard or common operating procedure where all these situations and/or stages are covered, so that all devices and organizations (whether public or private) can act accordingly the same way in case of cross-border collaboration or even within the same country or locality.

For the elaboration of this procedure, finally we proceed to carry out a selection of all the possible opportunities detected, opting for those that are considered key for the elaboration of said operating procedure and discarding those that we consider may be expendable.

For this, an evaluation has been carried out taking into account two factors:

- *Feasibility (F)*: ability to carry out the opportunity according to the available means, knowledge and economics.
- *Impact (I+)*: level of positive footprint that would be in the event of implementation of the opportunity.

For each of the opportunities, both items have been valued from 0 to 10, and those that obtain a score >14 points will be valued:

<i>Opportunity</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>I+</i>	<i>Result</i>
O3.1-G3.1: Unify the colors of road ambulances according to the European standard	4	5	9
O3.2-G3.2: Stablish standard EWS	8	7	15
O3.3-G3.3: Repository vocabulary	7	2	9
O3.4-G3.4: Harmonization for training exercises	8	8	16
O3.5-G3.5: Standardization of different classes of road firefighting vehicles	4	5	9
O3.6-G3.6: Multi-technological operability of devices for information processing	6	9	15
O3.7-G3.6: Standardization of roles related to patient data management	6	9	15
O3.8-G3.7: Set severity levels for all events	7	5	12
O3.9-G3.7: Establish communication protocols for accidents and disasters	8	7	15
O3.10-G3.8: Protocols for coordinated action in cross-border scenarios	8	8	16
O3.11-G3.9: Harmonized technology security protocols	7	9	16
O3.12-G3.10: Cloud computing service standard	6	7	13
O3.13-G3.10: Cloud computing service standard for devices	6	7	13
O3.14-G3.11: Database with high precision maps	5	7	12
O3.15-G3.13: Harmonization of international procedures for assistance in cross-border emergencies	6	7	13
O3.16-G3.14: International rapid response cross-border emergency management plan	5	7	12
O3.17-G3.15: Determine communications procedures	7	8	15
O3.18-G3.16: Standard cross-border emergency management procedure	6	7	13
O3.19-G3.17: Uniform alert policy for cross-border incident management	6	7	13
O3.20-G3.18: Comprehensive technological solution for all types of organizations capable of generating and receiving public alarm and emergency systems	7	8	15
O3.21-G3.19: Comprehensive assessment system for cross-border incidents	5	7	12
O3.22-G3.20: Create a uniform coding system for alarms and signalling	5	7	12
O3.23-G3.21: Determine standard EMSI for cross-border events	5	8	13
O3.24-G3.22: Prepare reviews to improve intervention procedures	7	6	13
O3.25-G3.23: Establishment of general principles and an operational framework for procedures	6	7	13

<i>Opportunity</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>I+</i>	<i>Result</i>
O3.26-G3.24: Rapid evaluation of spontaneous volunteers	8	8	16
O3.27-G3.25: Standardization of emergency plan for all types of emergencies	8	8	16
O3.28-G3.26: Treatment of information generated in social networks	8	7	15
O3.29-G3.27: Hierarchical level standardization	5	6	11
O3.30-G3.28: Non-shared risk identification process and periodic reviews not optimized for a highly dynamic context	7	8	15
O3.31-G3.28: Improvement of communication for different hierarchical scales between organizations	5	7	12
O3.32-G3.29: Information shared between organizations regarding vulnerable personnel	6	7	13
O3.33 Development of the association agreement process for cross-border emergency management	5	6	11
O3.34 G3.30 Unified strategic plan for cross-border emergency management	7	8	15
O3.35 G3.31 Uniform objectives of protection plans	8	8	16
O3.36 G3.32 Standard operating procedures with recognition of task performance in cross-border environment with different stakeholders	6	8	14
O3.37 G3.33 Uniform definition of the characteristics of the information to be transmitted and the resources required.	5	8	13
O3.38 G3.34 SOPs use standardised colours and with the expected function according to international standards.	7	5	12
O3.39 G3.35 Detailed description of resources, tasks and objectives for SOPs	7	8	15

Table 5 - Opp evaluation

4.5. Unification/ harmonization: Univeral framework cross-border emergency

After the evaluation of the different ISO standards, a set of current standards has been compiled that together can configure a reference framework for the comprehensive management of cross-border emergencies.

The selected reference standards are:

- ISO 22328:2020-1 Security and resilience - Emergency management - Guidelines for the implementation of a community-based disaster early warnings system
- ISO 22398:2013 Societal security — Guidelines for exercises
- ISO 13606-1:2019 Health informatics — Electronic health record communication — Part 1: Reference model
- ISO 22328:2020-1 Security and resilience - Emergency management - Guidelines for the implementation of a community-based disaster early warnings system
- ISO 22320:2018 Security and resilience - Emergency management - Guidelines for incident management
- ISO 22322:2015 Security and resilience - Emergency management - Guidelines for public warnings
- ISO 22319:2017 Security and resilience - Community resilience - Guidelines for planning the involvement of spontaneous volunteers

- ISO 22327:2018 Security and resilience — Emergency management — Guidelines for implementation of a community-based landslide early warning system
- ISO 22329:2021 Security and resilience — Emergency management — Guidelines for the use of social media in emergencies
- ISO 22326:2018 Security and resilience - Emergency management - Guidelines for monitoring facilities with identified hazards

4.6. Unification/ harmonization: Development of a harmonized procedure

From the analysis carried out, the needs for harmonization of the SOPs have been detected, establishing the criteria for action and the minimum common information necessary to carry out a unified SOP.

The operational procedures consulted show great heterogeneity and highlight the difficulties in developing joint activities between different entities, regardless of their sector, size and nature of their activity.

That is why it is interesting to create a reference model or template that helps to create all kinds of procedures, that is, a standard approach to having a template for standard operating procedures. This basic information responds to the basic needs of any operating procedure, whatever its objective and tasks, being adaptable in content depending on the process / plan to which it is assigned. This uniform structure will allow easy reading and understanding for all the participants in the procedure, since its structure will be familiar to them. An example is the documents associated with the management systems or the identification of ISO international standards that are carried out by families, such as the ISO 9000.

Figure 4 – Proposed cover of the Procedure

	GENERAL EUROPEAN CROSS-BORDER EMERGENCY PLAN	Edition: 00 Version: 00
		Page 2 of 2

- 1. PURPOSE AND SCOPE**
- 2. REFERENCES**
- 3. RESPONSIBILITIES**
- 4. DEFINITIONS**
- 5. INTRODUCTION**
- 6. DESCRIPTION OF PERFORMANCE**
 - 6.1. Incident statement
 - 6.1.1. Type
 - 6.1.2. Severity
 - 6.1.3. Location
 - 6.1.4. Necessary resources
 - 6.1.5. Coordination/ organization
 - 6.2. Activations alerts/ warnings/ communications
 - 6.3. Coordination/ organization
 - 6.4. Arrival at the incident site (Real analysis of the situation)
 - 6.5. Coordination/ organization
 - 6.6. Attention to victims (rescues, assessments, triage, evacuation, transfers, etc.).
 - 6.7. Final assessment
- 7. ANNEXES**
 - 7.1. Flowcharts
 - 7.2. Tables/ formats

Figure 5 – Procedure index proposal

5. Conclusions

The identification of a unified framework for the comprehensive management of cross-border emergencies with multiple victims based on international ISO/EN standards highlights the path still to be traveled by the different necessary actors, such as nations, organizations and, through special involvement, health emergency services.

Despite the constant appearance of different international standards that ensure the effective and efficient management of activities for any entity, they conflict with other areas of special relevance such as the legislative framework, cultural differences between business organizations, technological developments and access to it, and awareness of the principles for the necessary collaborative work.

From Valkyries, after the analysis of information dedicated to international standards and standard operating procedures, these possible improvements are proposed:

- Creation of a common reference framework with minimum technological levels for devices
- Identification of ethical, health, political and social principles for the proactive management of cross-border emergencies
- Designation of internationally recognized roles with a uniform deployment of responsibilities. Standardization of roles, functions and responsibilities of professionals and non-professionals assigned to cross-border emergencies

The standard operating procedures are subject, due to their nature, to the internal policies of their master documents (processes, plans, etc.) that include the permissions for consultation and distribution of information, which, by not contemplating to a large extent the joint activity with third parties is a barrier.

These standard operating procedures within a unified system of response to cross-border emergencies with multiple victims must be recognized within a working environment with third parties with the point that all types of entities must comply with the requirements, principles and processes of unified management of cross-border emergencies with multiple victims. As a consequence and by virtue of the recognition of Valkyries, the technology, software and resources must meet pre-established requirements and the minimum data set recognized in other Valkyries WP.

Within the policy, it must be accepted that every organization and entity, regardless of size or nature, must find the necessary legislative and/or regulatory framework to implement this methodology.

The objectives to be recognized within the unified standard operating procedures must be consistent with the objectives, policies and principles declared in the processes and procedures that are necessary in the comprehensive management of cross-border emergencies with multiple victims, as well as having the objectives of the procedure created, for example, the comprehensive management of emergencies in cross-border forest fires.

Finally, it should be noted that the ultimate goal of this methodology and the analysis carried out with the international ISO/EN standards consists of achieving the best operational result and the ability to save lives of all the resources necessary for the management and activity of the integral management of the emergency.

6. Annex A - References and bibliography

- H2020_Valkyries_Sec1-3
- VALKYRIES Requirement Card-WP3
- VALKYRIES - D2.8
- VALKYRIES - D2.5
- VALKYRIES - D2.12
- ISO 22320:2018, ISO 22322:2015, ISO 22324:2015, ISO/TR 22351:2015 and others

7. Annex B - Glossary

Acronym	Description
DRR	Disaster Risk Reduction ISO 22392:2020
EMSI	Emergency Management Shared Information ISO 22351:2015
EWS	Early Warning System ISO 22328:2020
GML	Geography Markup Language ISO 19136:2007
HER	Electronic Health Record ISO 13606-1:2019
ISMS	Information Security Management System ISO 27001:2022
ISO	International Organization for Standardization (www.iso.org)
PII	Personally Identifiable Information ISO 27018:2019
SOP	Standard Operating Procedure ISO 9000
SV	Spontaneous Volunteers ISO 22319:2017
UML	Unified Modeling Language ISO 24156:2008
WFS	Web Feature Service ISO 19142:2010
WMS	Web Map Server interface ISO 19128:2005
XML	Extensible Markup Language ISO 19136:2007

Table 6 - Glossary